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First report describing the status of the legislative framework, future perspectives and recommendations both in pilots and followers

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Table 1: Table of abbreviations.

AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
BOD	Biochemical Oxygen Demand
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
CMCs	Component Material Categories
CMR	Carcinogenic, Mutagenic, Reprotoxic
CRPM	Code Rural et de la Peche Maritime
CSR	Chemical Safety Report
DG ENV	Directorate-General for Environment
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EEA	European Environment Agency
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
EQS	Environmental Quality Standards
EQSD	Environmental Quality Standards Directive
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FPR	Fertilising Products Regulation
GAEC	Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KEMI	Kemikalieinspektionen - Swedish Chemicals Agency
KRMs	Key elements of Risk Management
MRD	Mutual Recognition Declaration
NMI	Nutrient Management Institute
NVZs	Nitrate Vulnerable Zones
PBT	Persistent, Bioaccumulative, and Toxic
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PGRAR	Reclaimed Water Risk Management Plan
POPs	Persistent organic pollutants
RDs	Royal decrees
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals
RISE	Research Institutes of Sweden
SIEF	Substance Information Exchange Forum
SS	Suspended solids
SSD	Sewage Sludge Directive
UVCBs	Unknown or Variable Composition, Complex Reaction Products or Biological Materials
UWWTD	Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive
vPvB	very Persistent and very Bio-accumulative
WFD	Waste Framework Directive
WISE	Water Information System for Europe

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WSR	Waste Shipment Regulation (EU) 2024/1157
WRR	Water Reuse Regulation

1 Executive Summary

This interim legislative report focuses on the key regimes applicable to the recovery of nutrients from human excreta (specifically, faeces and urine) for use in agriculture, focussing on waste, water reuse and fertilising products, with some consideration of organic agriculture therein. It primarily considers the EU regimes, but in light of approaches within Member States and complemented by consideration of the domestic authorisation regimes and mutual recognition processes within each of the pilot and follower regions in P2Green.

P2Green and similar products and activities have significant potential to contribute to the circular economy, zero pollution and food security, all of which are essential goals of the EU. However, a key element that is reflected throughout much of this interim legislative report is that human excreta is not a major express focus of EU law. As a result, there are limited pathways supporting the use of human excreta in agricultural production in EU or domestic legislation. There are several issues across the three key areas examined that might be suitable for potential reform.

The **waste regime** poses several significant challenges, including the lack of certainty regarding whether faeces is excluded from the EU waste regime or not, the scope of 'waste waters', the impact of the lack of discharges, the potential for 'waste water' to be collected privately via large-scale systems, and in what circumstances a product can cease to be waste where there are no express applicable criteria. Besides the lack of certainty, there is limited implementation of Article 6 of the Waste Framework Directive at the EU level or domestically and more fundamental questions arise about whether the term 'waste' should be applicable at all or not in the circumstances.

More positively, the EU has now established a coherent legal framework for water reclamation through the **Water Reuse** Regulation, providing a harmonised set of minimum requirements and a governance structure intended to ensure safety, transparency and public trust. While the Regulation is relatively new and some implementation pathways are still maturing, it nonetheless creates a clear regulatory backbone upon which Member States and stakeholders can build. This framework is further supported by a range of complementary guidance documents aiming to facilitate the practical uptake of water-reclamation technologies.

However, the potential for Member States to opt out of applying the Regulation or adding their own requirements or standards introduces variability and potential fragmentation in the EU's approach to water reuse. Further, even traditionally water-abundant regions are now encountering episodes of scarcity, increasing the need for water reuse in agriculture and elsewhere.

Consideration of **fertilising products** highlights several oddities and incoherencies. Despite the existence of an EU Fertilising Products Regulation (FPR), it does not provide

broad harmonisation here but instead operates in parallel to the domestic regimes (also considered herein, along with mutual recognition). The FPR and related EU regimes reflect inconsistencies in treatment between animal and human excreta, as well as the significant rigidity of the FPR's Component Material Categories with respect to both ingredients and treatments. Despite positive indications within the first Circular Economy Action Plan and other EU policy statements and documents, the FPR does not facilitate innovative fertilising products such as those developed by P2GreeN. However, it has the potential to be expanded and has important characteristics such as the CE-mark leading to marketability across the EU and also end-of-waste status.

The domestic fertilising product regimes vary considerably, for instance, with some largely mirroring the content of the FPR and others being seemingly more flexible without restrictions on input types. Sweden is a particularly unusual case, where there is no specific prior authorisation regime, but regulatory hurdles still exist.

Some potential reforms are identified across the three themes, primarily at an EU level. These will be considered further and developed, where appropriate, into recommendations in the project's final legislative report (D3.10), due in May 2026. Further, the report herein identifies some potential actions for P2GreeN actors and other stakeholders, e.g. through identifying which of the legal interpretations or avenues is most desirable for them, and through providing input to and collaborating with EU and national bodies such as WISE, the JRC, or CEDEX. This could be through, for instance, stakeholder meetings, calls for evidence or more informal processes.

This report is undertaken within an area that is undergoing considerable policy and legislative reforms on multiple fronts, e.g. with the review of the Fertilising Products Regulation and the Urban WasteWater Treatment Directive, as well as the proposal of an EU Circular Economy Act. The report is therefore based on our research of the law as of 14th of November 2025.

2 Introduction

The EU's general aims and ambitions include as a priority establishing and enhancing the circular economy, net-zero greenhouse emissions and zero pollution. These are fundamental needs, which are emphasised in the context of the twin biodiversity and climate crises. Simultaneously, food security, along with energy security and resilient supply chains are essential for the EU and its population – again, emphasised in the context of the environmental crises, with major climate impacts increasing, but also in the context of growing populations and the impacts of the war in Ukraine. The greening of the agri-food industry is central to these multifaceted concerns. P2GreeN and other organisations undertaking similar innovations have the potential to contribute positively to address these concerns.

P2GreeN's focus is on developing and implementing innovative methods to reclaim nutrients (Nitrogen and Phosphorous) and water from human excreta (specifically, faeces and urine) for use in agricultural production. The aim is to develop safe, environmentally friendly, bio-based fertilising products and nutrient-enriched reclaimed water for irrigation (or 'fertigation'). In doing so, P2GreeN takes something (human excreta) that is typically considered a problem that must be dealt with and instead sees it as a valuable resource that can help address the challenges noted above. P2GreeN and similar activities have the potential to:

- reclaim valuable nutrients for use as fertilising products, and enhanced water for irrigation or 'fertigation', in line with the concept of 'reduce, reuse, recover';
- establish resilient, guaranteed short supply chains of fertilising products;
- divert nutrients from undergoing costly waste-treatments that would destroy and thereby truly 'waste' the nutrients;
- ensure the application of these nutrients where needed and in a manner that minimises pollution and eutrophication;
- apply enhanced treatments and standards to human excreta, e.g. with respect to contaminants such as pharmaceutically active substances and pathogens;
- reduce reliance on chemical fertilisers and livestock-derived fertilisers; and
- reduce reliance on other sources of water, which could instead be used for human consumption.

These potential benefits proffered by P2GreeN and similar activities would contribute significantly to the EU's aims. However, a significant hurdle is to ensure compliance with the existing legal frameworks both when it comes to obligations on, for instance, management of waste, but also to opportunities for commercialisation and use on the land. Many of these frameworks are largely based in EU law, but with the details developed to varying effect through domestic implementation. The legal landscape is highly complex as a result, with a wide range of applicable regimes spread over multiple

levels – many of which are ambiguous and potentially conflicting. It was thereby essential to investigate the applicable legal frameworks across the levels.

Within D3.7, we undertook a scoping review of the applicable legal regimes, highlighting many applicable laws. This included ones on waste, water, air, nature conservation, fertilisers, chemicals and much more, but primarily focussing on the EU level. For this interim legislative report, we have narrowed our focus to consider the law potentially applicable to the initial inputs (human excreta) and to the desired outputs (fertilising products and nutrient-rich reclaimed water for irrigation/fertigation). To this end, we consider three key regimes in this report: waste, water reuse and fertilising products, with some consideration also of organic agriculture. The starting point is with the EU level, but heavily informed by domestic implementation and, in the case of fertilising products, encompassing complementary regimes.

To undertake this research, we primarily undertook desk-based research, examining the legislation, case-law, parliamentary statements, policy documents, literature etc. We also engaged with and were informed by our discussions with P2Green partners and our Advisory Board, along with workshops by and engagements with officials and other researchers, e.g. the Nutriënten Management Instituut (NMI, Nutrient Management Institute) or European Commission events on reviewing the Fertilising Products Regulation.¹ This has included, for instance, providing draft briefing papers on waste law and on organics to our P2Green partners. Likewise, along with colleagues in SunChemicals, we are currently finalising a briefing document with basic information on the regimes governing the placement of fertilising products on the EU market, the overall decision logic on which procedure to follow as well as key procedural information and links for each region on both the domestic authorisation regime for fertilising products within P2Green regions (where relevant) and mutual recognition within that region. For our P2Green partners and any others undertaking similar innovative activities, it is essential that they are familiar with the legislative frameworks at the EU and domestic levels, what challenges and opportunities exist within the existing frameworks and what opportunities there are to feed into and shape discussions on reform.

This report outlines the three selected regimes (waste, water reuse and fertilising products) in some detail, identifying key challenges and opportunities where relevant for P2Green and related activities. Based on this analysis, it proffers some initial suggestions for those undertaking or contemplating such activities, as well as identifying some potential options for reform. Those options will be considered further in our final deliverable on the legislative frameworks, D 3.10, which will include recommendations for law reform. The EU's current focus on developing a Circular Economy Act, alongside elements such as the Bioeconomy Strategy, Water Resilience Strategy, Soil Monitoring Law, revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive etc, all provide an opportunity for the EU to re-think and reform the regimes to enable and strengthen the circular economy,

¹ While we have benefited from the input of numerous others, any omissions or errors are those of the authors. Nothing within this document should be construed as legal advice or relied upon as such.

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achieve zero pollution, increase food security and more generally enhance the environment and human health.

3 Waste

3.1 Significance

The waste regime, encompassing EU and domestic elements, is an essential consideration for P2Green activities and products and those of a similar nature. It impacts on several fronts, from beginning to end. First, if a substance is deemed waste, it is regulated as such and must be managed appropriately in accordance with the relevant regime. This could involve requirements regarding licencing, collection, specific treatments, storage, transportation etc. Exemptions, exclusions and limitations can exist, but these will involve multiple hurdles.² Second, if a substance is deemed waste, it may be possible for it to cease being waste, but the initial classification as waste still has long-term ramifications. It can impact upon what the substance may legally be transformed into, utilised for, and authorised as, including regarding its use as a fertiliser and/or in irrigation. For instance, the EU Fertilising Products Regulation is highly restrictive regarding whether waste or something that has ceased to be waste can be a Component Material Category in an EU fertilising product (some very limited options exist, but they are of negligible relevance to P2Green as discussed in Chapter 5). This is before one even considers the societal or more philosophical implications or considerations of categorising something as waste. Therefore, the waste regime is central to considering the potential of P2Green and similar endeavours.

3.2 Introduction to the regime

The focus here is largely on the EU regime but drawing on, and in light of, the domestic elements where relevant. The EU regime provides the broad framework (at times due to international law, e.g. the Basel Convention),³ including some core objectives, definitions, requirements for management criteria etc. However, it does so primarily through the format of directives rather than regulations, thereby leaving considerable flexibility to the Member States when they are transposing, implementing and enforcing the EU regimes. This flexibility includes the potential to develop or add details, including potentially definitions, where these have not been addressed conclusively at the EU level.

² If the P2Green inputs and/or products are not considered waste, this does not mean however that they would be unregulated. For instance, general environmental, food production and health laws would apply.

³ The Basel Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and Their Disposal, 22 March 1989.

The two key Directives examined here are (i) the Waste Framework Directive (WFD),⁴ which is the overarching piece of legislation that underpins the entire EU waste regime and provides some key definitions and objectives, and (ii) the new revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD),⁵ which is the core legislation focussing on wastewater treatment and the provision of sanitation services. Other waste legislation is also relevant, e.g. regarding the use of sewage⁶ or ‘reclaimed water’,⁷ or the transport of waste.⁸

A key point to note before examining the regime vis-à-vis P2GreeN activities is that the EU waste regime is by no means comprehensive. Further, while some of the legislation has been updated, it largely does not address or provide for innovative or alternative approaches – while not necessarily excluding these either. As shall be seen, there is some significant lack of clarity, confusion and potential gaps arising, that are of particular relevance to P2GreeN and similar endeavours. These can pose challenges but also potentially provide opportunities through flexibility – although whether a legal opportunity equates to a commercial opportunity is a different question.

A final point to note at this stage is that the EU waste regime has been amended to include express mention of the circular economy within its objectives. Thus, Article 1 of the WFD on its ‘subject matter and scope’ now reads:

This Directive lays down measures to protect the environment and human health by preventing or reducing the generation of waste, the adverse impacts of the generation and management of waste and by reducing overall impacts of resource use and improving the efficiency of such use, which are crucial for the transition to a circular economy and for guaranteeing the Union’s long-term competitiveness.

Similarly, Article 1 of the new revised UWWTD makes express reference to the circular economy.⁹ This reflects a shift in EU policy and ambition but also may impact substantively through influencing both domestic implementation and especially the CJEU’s interpretation of the EU waste law. This, however, may only occur incrementally over a long period of time, as the CJEU’s existing purposive approach to interpretation

⁴ Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives [2008] OJ L 312/3, as amended.

⁵ Directive (EU) 2024/3019 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2024 concerning urban wastewater treatment, [2024] OJ L 2024/3019. This Directive replaced the previous UWWTD and came into force in January 2025, with different obligations coming into effect over the forthcoming years.

⁶ Council Directive 86/278/EEC of 12 June 1986 on the protection of the environment, and in particular of the soil, when sewage sludge is used in agriculture, [1986] OJ L181/6. This legislation is quite outdated at this stage.

⁷ Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse, [2020] OJ L177/32.

⁸ Regulation (EU) 2024/1157 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 on shipments of waste, amending Regulations (EU) No 1257/2013 and (EU) 2020/1056 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006, [2024] OJ L2024/1157.

⁹ This Directive replaces the 1991 UWWTD. While the 1991 Directive still has effect until 2027, the focus here is on the revised 2024 Directive.

regarding waste law is well-established. If changes to the waste regime (or related regimes) are desirable, these provisions and the recognition of the significance of the circular economy should be borne in mind.

3.3 Is human excreta waste?

This question is fundamental and may appear to have obvious, conflicting, answers depending on the perspective. However, the starting point legally is that EU law contains a definition of waste, and this definition is binding across all Member States. The EU definition focusses on the holder of the substance and whether they discard, intend to discard or are required to discard the substance.¹⁰ If any of these are true, then the substance is waste (and then can be further categorised, e.g. if it is hazardous or not). A substance may not be waste initially, but once a person receives it and then, for instance, intends to discard it, it becomes waste. Further, if something that is not waste is mixed with waste, the combined mixture is then to be treated as waste. The concept has proven complex and contested in practice,¹¹ with the CJEU playing a key role in its evolution.¹²

Significantly, the CJEU has taken a highly purposive approach to interpreting the WFD, including the definition of waste, in light of the aims of a high level of protection of the environment and human health and, especially, the precautionary principle.¹³ For instance, in *Walloon Waste*, the CJEU noted that ‘with respect to the environment, it is important to note that waste is a matter of a special kind. Accumulation of waste, even before it becomes a health hazard, constitutes a danger to the environment, regard being had in particular to the limited capacity of each region or locality for waste reception.’¹⁴ This leads to a very expansive interpretation of the concept¹⁵ and remains the case even since the amendment of Article 1 of the WFD to include reference to the circular economy.¹⁶ In general, the fact that another person wants the substance or that it holds

¹⁰ Article 3(1) of the WFD. Discarding includes both disposal and recovery operations.

¹¹ E.g., I. Cheyne, ‘The definition of waste in EC law,’ [2002] *Journal of Environmental Law*, 61; and D. Pocklington, ‘Opening Pandora’s Box – the EU Review of the Definition of “Waste”’, [2003] 12 *European Environmental Law Review* 204.

¹² H. Nash, ‘The revised directive on waste: resolving legislative tensions in waste management,’ [2009] *Journal of Environmental Law*, 139; and D. Pocklington, ‘The Significance of the Proposed Changes to the Waste Framework Directive,’ [2006] 15 *European Environmental Law Review*, 75-87.

¹³ Numerous cases reflect this, including ones regarding stone residue from quarrying and usable excavated topsoil, e.g. Case C-9/00 *Palin Granit* [2000] ECR I-3533 and Cases C 206/88 & C-207/88 *Vessoso & Zanetti* [1990] ECR I-1461 and I-1509.

¹⁴ Case C-2/90 *Commission v Belgium (Walloon Waste)* [1992] ECR I-4431, para 30.

¹⁵ E.g. the CJEU in Case C-235/02 *Saetti & Frediani* ECLI:EU:C:2004:26, para 36, refers to ‘the obligation to interpret the concept of waste widely in order to limit its inherent risks and pollution’ and states at para 40 that ‘whether something is in fact waste must be determined in the light of all the circumstances, regard being had to the aim of the directive and the need to ensure that its effectiveness is not undermined’.

¹⁶ E.g. Case C-629/19 *Sappi Austria Produktions-GmbH & Co. KG v Landeshauptmann von Steiermark* EU:C:2020:824, para 43, ‘As regards the meaning of the term ‘discard’, it also follows from the Court’s

commercial value, does not prevent it being waste¹⁷ – although limited exceptions do exist.

Of note, a type of substance might be waste in one context (e.g. where the holder intends to discard of it) but not in another (e.g. where it is being used with no intention or need to discard), but once an individual item is deemed to be waste then it remains as waste unless it fulfils the specific requirements under Article 6 of the WFD (discussed below).

Applying these considerations to human excreta (faeces, urine and a mix thereof) provides for what appears initially to be a clearcut conclusion that they are waste, but where ambiguities exist and arguments can be made. Human excreta are originally held by the person who produces them. Individuals excrete (separate and discharge or eliminate) from their bodies substances that would prove toxic to them if retained for too long. There is a strong case therefore for saying that we are required to discard such substances and that they are always waste,¹⁸ even if they are gathered at source for converting into a fertiliser or an irrigation product. This interpretation is strengthened by the CJEU's expansive approach to the definition, based on its purposive approach to-date.

However, alternative arguments could be made, e.g. that they are by-products under Article 5, but this includes criteria that 'the substance or object is produced as an integral part of a production process' and 'can be directly without any further processing other than normal industrial practice'.¹⁹ Even if the creation of energy in the human body were

settled case-law that that term must be interpreted in the light of the aim of Directive 2008/98, which, in the words of recital 6 thereof, is to minimise the negative effects of the generation and management of waste on human health and the environment, having regard to Article 191(2) TFEU, which provides that EU policy on the environment is to aim at a high level of protection and is to be based, in particular, on the precautionary principle and the principle that preventive action should be taken. It follows that the term 'discard', and therefore the concept of 'waste' within the meaning of point 1 of Article 3 of Directive 2008/98, cannot be interpreted restrictively (judgment of 4 July 2019, *Tronex*, C-624/17, EU:C:2019:564, paragraph 18 and the case-law cited).¹⁷ Article 1 was amended in 2018 and the CJEU at para 68 made a reference to the circular economy more generally, but without expressly drawing on it further within the judgment.

¹⁷ Cases C 206/88 & C-207/88 *Vessoso & Zanetti* [1990] ECR I-1461 and I-1509, paras 8 and 12. See also Case C-629/19 *Sappi Austria Produktions-GmbH & Co. KG v Landeshauptmann von Steiermark* EU:C:2020:824, para 48, stating: 'The system of supervision and control established by Directive 2008/98 is intended to cover all objects and substances discarded by their owners, even if they have a commercial value and are collected on a commercial basis for recycling, reclamation or re-use (see, to that effect, judgments of 24 June 2008, *Commune de Mesquer*, C-188/07, EU:C:2008:359, paragraph 40, and of 3 October 2013, *Brady*, C-113/12, EU:C:2013:627, paragraph 42 and the case-law cited).'

¹⁸ Although dealing with waste waters rather than excreta per se, the point by the CJEU in Case C-629/19 *Sappi Austria Produktions-GmbH & Co. KG v Landeshauptmann von Steiermark* EU:C:2020:824, at para 59 is nonetheless worth noting: 'It is common knowledge that residential or municipal waste water is to be regarded as a substance which its holder discards.' The 'common knowledge' aspect could be applied similarly to excreta.

¹⁹ This reflects the earlier jurisprudence of the CJEU, e.g. in *Saetti & Frediani*, para 36, it stated that 'having regard to the obligation to interpret the concept of waste widely in order to limit its inherent risks and pollution, recourse to the reasoning applicable to by-products should be confined to situations in which the further use of goods, materials or raw materials is not a mere possibility but a certainty, without any prior processing, and as an integral part of the production process'.

deemed a 'production process', use of human excreta in fertilisers or irrigation products is currently not a normal industrial process and requires significant processing. Consequently, classification as by-products appears off the table.

A further alternative is a more fundamental one, which is simply to claim first that the faeces or urine are not 'discarded' by the human body but instead are produced. If one starts from that point, then the next step is to claim that they are likewise not discarded (or intended or required to be discarded) if individuals, for instance, urinate purposefully into special containers that are used as a step in producing fertilisers. This could be supported by reference to, for instance, providing a urine sample for medical tests. Urine in a toilet entering a sewer to undergo waste treatment or on the street is waste, but urine placed in a container by the person who created it – perhaps not? This is a tempting line of thought and could be argued, but the weakness of this argument is that the WFD and CJEU focus on the holder of the substance. If the individual creating the excreta is using it to water or fertilise their own plants, then they would be using and not discarding the excreta (equivalent to urine for medical tests). If they give it as a gift to a friend or neighbour, or use it themselves to create a commercial fertiliser for sale, this again could provide a strong basis to say no discarding takes place.²⁰ However, in the case of P2GreeN-style activities, even where collected separately, it is being given by the original producer/holder to others for them to transform into a product for third parties. The last is more akin to plastic containers that a householder places for recycling, where such plastic containers are clearly considered waste as the householder is discarding of them, even if they are of value and will be used in future by others. The CJEU seem unlikely to agree with this exclusion considering their expansive approach to interpreting the concept of waste, even in light of the reference to circular economy now inserted within Article 1. If starting from a blank canvas, they might have been more willing to exclude such excreta from the concept, provided that they were assured of its certain use and a high level of environmental and human health protection.

However, this nonetheless creates a significant difficulty. It is possible that, in light of the opacity and with no clarifying decision by the Commission or the CJEU and no relevant implementing EU legislation, Member States might not treat such substances as waste – thereby excluding them from the scope of the waste regime and leaving them to be regulated (or not) by other regimes. While the CJEU would be likely to classify it as waste, this might take considerable time. This could be seen as an opportunity in the relevant Member State, but it is due to legal uncertainty and this could have significant practical and financial ramifications in future, e.g. if the Member States were forced to then regulate the substances as waste and required all relevant infrastructure to be ripped up and re-installed accordingly.

²⁰ E.g. compare Case C-238/21 *Porr Bau GmbH v Bezirkshauptmannschaft Graz-Umgebung*, EU:C:2022:885 regarding high quality soil; and an earlier case regarding animal manure (prior to legislative developments): Case C-416/02 *Commission v Spain* [2005] ECR I-7487.

One final alternative must be noted, which is under Article 2(1)(f) of the WFD. Article 2(1) provides for some substances that would otherwise potentially be deemed waste to be excluded entirely from the scope of the WFD. This effectively means that the substances would not be deemed waste under EU law. We addressed Article 2(1)(f) within the original scoping review, but it merits noting again. Article 2(1)(f) excludes 'faecal matter, if not covered by paragraph 2(b), straw and other natural non-hazardous agricultural or forestry material used in farming, forestry or for the production of energy from such biomass through processes or methods which do not harm the environment or endanger human health.' 'Paragraph 2(b)' refers to animal by-products. It is debatable whether 'faecal matter' applies to human faeces or not. For instance, on the one hand, human faeces is not an animal by-product for the purposes of the relevant EU law but is clearly a form of 'faecal matter' and would therefore on the face of it appear to be covered by Article 2(1)(f). There is no express exclusion of human faeces. On the other hand, we would also note that 'faecal matter' here appears to be presented as part of a list, i.e. a) faecal matter, b) straw, and c) other natural non-hazardous agricultural or forestry material used in farming. While not definitive, there are strong arguments that 'faecal matter' should be read therefore in light of the rest of that list, which includes 'straw and *other* natural non-hazardous agricultural or forestry material...' (emphasis added).²¹ This would lead to the conclusion that all substances within the list should be 'natural non-hazardous agricultural or forestry material', i.e. derived from agricultural or forestry activities or products.²² However, human faeces do not derive from either agricultural or forestry activities/products and therefore the provision would seem to be too restrictive here to facilitate the exclusion of human faeces from the WFD. It would also create an inconsistent situation where human faeces were excluded entirely, subject to the caveats regarding their safe use for specific purposes, whereas urine or faeces with some urine or other substances such as toilet paper would still be waste and regulated under EU waste law. This highlights a practical issue for P2Green and similar activities, as, for instance, faeces may be composted together with some limited urine and toilet paper. While the CJEU might be willing to avoid interpreting 'faecal matter' in light of the rest of the list and consider that a purposive interpretation is fulfilled due to the condition of not harming the environment or endangering human health, the resulting potential exclusion is uncertain and limited in practice. It could however signal a potential basis for interpreting the regime more flexibly or for reforming the regime and adding further exclusions.

For the purposes of the rest of this document, we are going to presume that human excreta do indeed fall within the concept of waste and the EU waste regimes. This is also the logical approach for the time being for P2Green partners as, even if the faeces exclusion applies in principle, the addition of other substances (urine/used toilet paper)

²¹ Note the syntax: specifically, there is no 'and' or 'or' between 'faecal matter' and 'straw and other... material'. Without the additional details it reads as 'faecal matter..., straw and other natural non-hazardous agricultural or forestry material...'.
²² Other language versions of the Directive support the interpretation that the 'other... material' must derive from agriculture or forestry, e.g. in French it states '...issues de l'agriculture ou de la sylviculture...'.

that are waste would likely prevent the exclusion applying in practice. The next question is, therefore, which waste regime is applicable?

3.4 Applicable waste regime

Typically, within the EU, human faeces and urine enter a toilet bowl or urinal and are flushed down into the sewage system. Exceptions exist, but this is the norm. As demonstrated below, the EU waste regime is focussed on this norm and the need to provide for treatment of the contents of the sewage system – along with, for instance, more individualised septic tanks. It does not directly contemplate or address alternatives that arise in the case of P2GreeN activities, e.g. where the systems are decentralised, where the excreta are not flushed but are collected at source. This poses numerous challenges in determining which of the waste regimes is applicable, with the potential for conflicting approaches arising across the Member States and ones where the EU might subsequently clarify or amend the current legal framework.

Once a substance is identified as waste, then the starting point is that the WFD applies unless the substance is excluded from its scope in part or entirely. Apart from Article 2(1)(f) discussed above, the key provision of relevance is Article 2(2)(a) WFD. This provision excludes ‘waste waters’ ‘*to the extent* that they are covered by other Community legislation’ (emphasis added), which in this case primarily entails the (revised) UWWTD.²³ If something is a wastewater and not (fully) covered by other EU law, the elements that are not covered fall back within the WFD. This raises key questions over the scope of the UWWTD and its potential applicability to P2GreeN-style activities, which in turn requires us to consider the concept of ‘wastewater’ and the UWWTD’s focus on discharges and infrastructure. In considering these, it is important to reflect on the nature of the WFD and UWWTD. As both pieces of EU legislation are directives, they leave the Member States considerable leeway in their implementation. Further, some elements are not expanded upon or addressed within the Directives.

²³ It is worth noting that the CJEU has expressly considered whether waste waters and sewage sludge are excluded entirely from the WFD, with the conclusion that they are not. Case C-629/19 *Sappi Austria Produktions-GmbH & Co. KG v Landeshauptmann von Steiermark* EU:C:2020:824, para 36: to be excluded, other EU legislation ‘must contain precise provisions organising the management of waste and ensure a level of protection which is at least equivalent to that resulting from that directive’. The case discusses the issue that the UWWTD does not provide for the treatment or management of the residual sludge and that the Sewage Sludge Directive only focusses on the use of sludge in agriculture. The CJEU did not consider the SSD further, but, as an aside, it is questionable whether the SSD at this stage provides an adequate level of protection considering issues over heavy metals, pharmaceuticals, infectious components etc. The caveat of ‘to the extent that they are covered...’ acts as a failsafe to uphold the objectives of the WFD and in particular environmental protection and human health: G. Van Calster, *EU Waste Law*, (OUP, second edition, 2015), p.40.

3.4.1 Waste water?

Significantly, waste waters or wastewater (the two terms are used within both EU and domestic implementing legislation)²⁴ are left undefined by both the WFD and the UWWTD, including within the revised renditions. Of note the UWWTD defines ‘domestic wastewater’ as ‘wastewater from residential settlements, services and institutions which originates predominately from the human metabolism or from household activities, or from both’. This reference to the human metabolism would imply that wastewater typically includes human excreta. However, this is not always the case and, further, not all excreta will necessarily be part of wastewater. Conceptually, there is the vague idea of impure, contaminated or sullied water that is being discarded or required to be discarded, but without any such language or specificity in the legislation. The liquids or gloop leaving a house via the general drains, e.g. from sinks, toilets and showers, would clearly qualify, but other substances are more challenging to categorise – in particular, if one keeps them separate.

Urine is largely comprised of water and therefore it would seem logical to consider it a form of wastewater, but the same could be said of juices or milk and yet it is unlikely that they would be considered such until they are poured down the sink, enter the drain and become part of the general wastewaters found therein. Is it the pouring down the drain or the mixing with other substances within it that makes them wastewater or both? If water is added to them first, is the liquid now diluted juice or milk or dirty water or both? What if cleaning products are then added? What if nothing is added, but simply they have gone bad or are unwanted and are liquids that need to be thrown out? In each case (except for the diluted juice/milk) they would be waste, but it is challenging to determine at what point precisely they are ‘wastewater’. This normally does not matter as individuals will simply pour the liquids down the sink (or into the toilet for urine) and once in the sewer, they are considered part of the overall wastewater.

Returning to urine, which as discussed would currently usually appear to be waste as defined by the WFD, there are different arguments to be made depending on how and when it is collected. If the normal practice is followed and an ordinary toilet is used and the urine and/or faeces is flushed and enters a drain/sewer, this would be deemed part of wastewater. At the other end of the scale, if urine is collected entirely separately and not mixed with any other waste (e.g. tissues, faeces, wastewater in drains) or any clean/uncontaminated water used for flushing, then there is a case to be made that it is not wastewater but a different form of waste to be regulated separately. And yet, it is by no means definite.

In the case of ‘yellow water’, where urine is mixed with water, i.e. flushed, but then collected separately, it would seem more logical to consider this to be wastewater; the

²⁴ It should be noted that the terminology in both the EU legislation and domestic implementing legislation varies across different languages, e.g. with versions that translate more closely to ‘used waters’.

urine is effectively contaminating²⁵ the water. However, again, this is not entirely definite – how is this different from a very well-hydrated individual urinating? A somewhat stronger argument could be made regarding combined urine and faeces separated at source (before entering the general drains/sewage systems and without mixing with other substances), as the faeces would effectively be contaminating the liquid/water.

In contrast, where faeces are separated at source, e.g. via a dry compost toilet or through filtering, this would seem to fall outside the scope of wastewater and therefore be regulated by the WFD.²⁶

However, it must be emphasised: the UWWTD does not address these matters expressly and the law is unclear. Further, the Member States are responsible for the transposition and implementation of the EU law, which leaves considerable flexibility to them in developing elements. Germany provides an interesting case in point. It adopts the term found in the German language version of the EU laws, which is 'Abwässer'. This has a slightly different connotation and, while it can translate as 'wastewater', it can also translate as 'used water' which mirrors the French term 'eaux usées'. §54 of the Federal Water Act (Wasserhaushaltsgesetz, WHG), provides a very wide, flexible definition of wastewater that focusses on changes in properties of the water due to its previous use.²⁷ The German definition even includes run-off from precipitation from paved or built-up areas, whereas this is considered something distinct in France.²⁸ While EU definitions of terms in EU law take precedence over any domestic definitions, the issue here is that the EU does not provide a definition of 'wastewater' itself. Member States seeking simply to manage waste and comply with their EU obligations are likely to consider any partially or largely liquid waste and any waste in a sewer to be 'waste water' (or the equivalent in other EU languages), but also will likely choose the approach that suits their infrastructure and organizational structures best. This is not necessarily an issue for P2Green activities in principle, as (a) ambiguity can provide flexibility that could be helpful and (b) the UWWTD may not apply to most activities in question due to its focus on 'discharges' (see below), but it may pose a significant challenge in practice. The practical challenge is that where ambiguity exists in the law, local authorities may take a different interpretation of the law or be unwilling to accept that flexibility exists, and/or be reluctant to make a decision or support innovative approaches. If it is unclear as to which regime is applicable,

²⁵ Contaminating here is being used only in so much as the water is no longer simply water.

²⁶ Yet, note the French approach discussed below with respect to connecting dry toilets, which may be used to treat faeces by drying (and thereby separating them from urine at source) or to treat both faeces and urine together to create compost. The provisions are found within the domestic law on waste water.

²⁷ The first paragraph therein states: '(1) Abwasser ist 1. das durch häuslichen, gewerblichen, landwirtschaftlichen oder sonstigen Gebrauch in seinen Eigenschaften veränderte Wasser und das bei Trockenwetter damit zusammen abfließende Wasser (Schmutzwasser) sowie 2. das von Niederschlägen aus dem Bereich von bebauten oder befestigten Flächen gesammelt abfließende Wasser (Niederschlagswasser). Als Schmutzwasser gelten auch die aus Anlagen zum Behandeln, Lagern und Ablagern von Abfällen austretenden und gesammelten Flüssigkeiten.' This indicates that wastewater includes water whose properties have changed due to (domestic or other) use.

²⁸ Refer to: <https://www.drieat.ile-de-france.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/les-eaux-usees-de-quoi-parler-t-on-a3466.html?lang=fr>.

it may be unclear as to who is responsible for making decisions or undertaking actions, e.g. who is the competent authority to grant a licence? This can make it easier for authorities to avoid the issue and keep 'passing the buck', by saying 'it's not my decision'.

3.4.2 What if there are no discharges?

The obligations and components of the UWWTD are discussed below, but it is essential to note here that the primary focus is on regulating 'the collection, treatment and discharge of urban wastewater...'.²⁹ The treatments envisaged within the UWWTD are focussed on ensuring that any discharges into water bodies will be safe for the environment and human health. There is an implication that the treatments are not required if there will be no discharges, which would be of direct relevance for P2Green processes (with the exception of Spain's focus on creating reclaimed water enriched in nutrients for irrigation). In such a case, it would appear that even where a substance is 'wastewater', it would not fall within the scope of the UWWTD and would instead fall back within the WFD.³⁰

This is also supported by a distinction that can be made between an obligation on the Member States to ensure that appropriate infrastructure is in place to gather the wastewater and the lack of an obligation on individuals to, for instance, flush human excreta down the toilet. This is highlighted by research undertaken by Legrand et al in France.³¹ Reflecting the UWWTD, French water law distinguishes between collective sanitation (wastewater, including human excreta, is collected in a public sewer) and non-collective sanitation³² (a private sewer or 'autonomous wastewater treatment system' may be used – which can include the treatment of faeces separated at source via a dry toilet).³³

²⁹ Article 1 in full states: 'This Directive lays down rules on the collection, treatment and discharge of urban wastewater, to protect the environment and human health, in line with the One Health approach, while progressively reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to sustainable levels, improving the energy balance of urban wastewater collection and treatment activities and contributing to the transition towards a circular economy. It also lays down rules on access to sanitation for all, on transparency of the urban wastewater sector, on the regular surveillance of relevant public health parameters in urban wastewater and on the implementation of the polluter-pays principle.'

³⁰ There is still of course the potential for a Member State to grant permits under the WFD that are heavily informed by the UWWTD provisions.

³¹ [M. Legrand et al., 'The Emergence of Systems for the Source Separation and Valorization of Human Waste in Greater Paris: from necessity to implementation', Second International Conference « Water, Megacities and Global Change », 1-4 December 2020](#), accessed 14 November 2025. Also, see: [Marine Legrand, Aurélie Joveniaux, Alessandro Arbarotti, Bernard de Gouvello, Esculier Fabien, et al., Séparation à la source et valorisation des excréta humains du Grand Paris : des filières émergentes. TSM. Techniques Sciences Méthodes – Génie urbain, génie rural, 2021, 9 \(9\), pp.103-118.](#)

³² E.g. <https://www.service-public.fr/particuliers/vosdroits/F447>.

³³ The inclusion of dry faeces is provided for by Ministerial Decree on "technical requirements" of 7 September 2009, as amended by the Ministerial Decree of 7 March 2012. See Articles 17-19 of Arrêté du 7 septembre 2009 fixant les prescriptions techniques applicables aux installations d'assainissement non collectif recevant une charge brute de pollution organique inférieure ou égale à 1,2 kg/j de DBO5, available

However, again reflecting the EU's UWWTD, French law focusses on connection, rather than use – agglomerations of the relevant size must be connected to an appropriate collecting system. As per Legrand et al, the Minister in charge of sanitation has expressly stated that the installation of dry toilets is possible in a collective sanitation zone.³⁴ This leads to the situation where a building might have two or more systems in place (e.g. a dry toilet for faeces or faeces and urine, along with a urinal to collect yellow water, with suitable treatment facilities linked to them, and a general toilet linked to the public sewer) but only operate one or some of them. As per Legrand et al, 'source separation clearly emerges as a hybrid system that is not properly taken into account in French law'.³⁵

Consequently, if a Member State ensures that the relevant connections are in place and, if there will be discharges, that the relevant treatments are applied (see below), then the key obligations will be complied with. Therefore, for P2Green operators or those undertaking similar activities, even where the substance is deemed 'wastewater', they can install separate systems to collect human faeces and, if there will be no discharges from their activities, then the UWWTD obligations will not apply. Instead, the 'wastewater' will fall back within the WFD and corresponding implementing measures domestically – even if this might be substantively informed by the UWWTD. What is not clear from the French Ministerial response, French law or the UWWTD is whether the separate system for gathering human excreta could be a large-scale collective system, e.g. a private sewer system just for these substances and toilet paper, provided that the buildings were also connected to the public sewer system. Due to the ambiguity of the regime, this is likely open to the Member States to determine for the time-being.

3.5 Regulating human excreta as waste

Once human excreta are identified as waste and it falls within the scope of the WFD or the UWWTD, the regime creates a range of obligations for those holding and transporting such waste, as well for the Member States and their local authorities (e.g. the municipalities). As noted, these are Directives and so the Member States add significant details and operational frameworks in their implementation. Nonetheless, the EU

at <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/LEGITEXT000021125886/>. Discussed in Legrand et al, (2020), section 2.3.

³⁴ Assemblée Nationale, Parliamentary question No.73941 of 16 March 2010, <https://questions.assemblee-nationale.fr/q13/13-73941QE.htm>. Besides referring to the provisions on dry toilets in the 2009 Arrete, the Minister in part of the response refers to French building laws that require the installation of a toilet in buildings, without specifying what type of toilet: ' L'article R. 111-3 du code de la construction et de l'habitation précise en effet que « le logement doit être pourvu d'un cabinet d'aisances intérieur au logement et ne communiquant pas directement avec les cuisines et les salles de séjour », sans en préciser la nature.'

³⁵ See n31 above. Also see [Marine Legrand, Aurélie Joveniaux, Alessandro Arbarotti, Bernard de Gouvello, Esculier Fabien, et al.. Séparation à la source et valorisation des excréta humains du Grand Paris : des filières émergentes. TSM. Techniques Sciences Méthodes – Génie urbain, génie rural, 2021, 9 \(9\), pp.103-118.](#)

frameworks provide an important initial starting point.³⁶ A key focus of the legislation as mentioned is a high level of protection of human health and the environment and that, along with other legislative objectives such as the circular economy, should be borne in mind when reviewing and considering the obligations therein.

3.5.1 General obligations on Member States

The EU legislation imposes a range of obligations on Member States, e.g. to ensure the creation of a network of waste disposal and recovery installations;³⁷ to ensure appropriate waste management (including transport);³⁸ to ensure that urban wastewater in agglomerations of over 1,000 people is subject to appropriate treatments (with varying deadlines applying and some exemptions);³⁹ to therefore ensure appropriate infrastructure; to monitor and enforce the EU legislation⁴⁰ etc. It is also worth noting that the Member States must comply with the ‘waste hierarchy’,⁴¹ and that they are ‘to provide incentives for its application’. As part of this the Member States are to ‘take measures to prevent waste generation’, including ‘targeting products containing critical raw materials to prevent that those materials become waste’.⁴²

While our focus is on the obligations on those holding, managing and transporting waste, it is worthwhile to bear these in mind, as they influence the domestic approach to implementing the legislation and also highlight the broad framework within which P2GreeN and similar activities operate. Currently, the mainstream approach is typically the municipalities’ treatment of waste in the form of sewage. Nutrient recovery is an outlier and, while it could be highly beneficial on multiple fronts and is reflected in the legislation, Member States in the short term also need to comply with their other EU obligations and ensure the basic management and treatment of human excreta/sewage.

Any potential reforms would also need to bear this in mind and the current domestic infrastructure – without curbing ambition or crystalising outdated methods, any changes would need to consider the practical challenges and the desirability (or lack thereof) of large-scale overhauls of the regimes. This is similar to the issues of classification of human excreta as wastewater or not.

³⁶ It should be noted that other regimes overlap here, e.g. regarding the management, storage and handling of hazardous substances or chemicals, as well as ones to do with urban planning.

³⁷ Article 16 of the WFD.

³⁸ E.g. Articles 15 and 17 of the WFD.

³⁹ See Articles 3 and 4 of the Revised UWWTD, along with Articles 6-8.

⁴⁰ Reflected across numerous provisions, but also within the general duty of sincere cooperation.

⁴¹ Article 4 of the WFD.

⁴² Article 9(1)(c) of the WFD. Phosphorous is considered a critical raw material.

3.5.2 Basic management and treatment of waste

The management⁴³ of waste generally is provided for primarily by the WFD, but with recognition of the possibility for other legislation to regulate specific streams of waste, including 'wastewaters'. As mentioned, this brings into play the UWWTD in particular, as well other legislation subsequently, including the Water Reuse Regulation and Sewage Sludge Directive. Before considering these, it is worth highlighting the prominence of environmental protection and human health within the legislation, but also the introduction of concepts such as the circular economy (now in Article 1 of the WFD and also of the revised UWWTD)

Besides the WFD's Article 13 requiring that all waste management be undertaken 'without endangering human health or harming the environment',⁴⁴ the WFD's Chapter III addresses waste management and Chapter IV the related 'permits and registrations'. Article 15 provides for the Member States to 'ensure that any original waste producer or other holder carries out the treatment'⁴⁵ of the waste or has some other suitable person or entity do so. Articles 17 to 20 address hazardous waste, including distinguishing that produced by households from other sources. Interestingly, the hazardous characteristics outlined in Annex III of the WFD include being 'infectious', with the 'waste containing viable micro-organisms or their toxins which are known or reliably believed to cause disease in man or other living organisms'. This would seem logically to include human excreta. However, Article 7 provides for the Commission to create a 'list of waste', including identifying those wastes deemed hazardous and those not. Substances such as 'septic tank sludge' and 'sludges from treatment of urban wastewater' are not

⁴³ Defined under Article 3 of the WFD as 'the collection, transport, recovery (including sorting), and disposal of waste, including the supervision of such operations and the after-care of disposal sites, and including actions taken as a dealer or broker'. While storage is not expressly included therein, 'collection' encompasses temporary storage and the Annexes I and II include 'storage pending any of the operations numbered...'. The WFD also addresses the storage of hazardous wastes.

⁴⁴ The full article provides: Member States shall take the necessary measures to ensure that waste management is carried out without endangering human health, without harming the environment and, in particular: (a) without risk to water, air, soil, plants or animals; (b) without causing a nuisance through noise or odours; and (c) without adversely affecting the countryside or places of special interest.

⁴⁵ As per Article 3(14) of the WFD, treatment 'means recovery or disposal operations, including preparation prior to recovery or disposal'. Article 3(15) states that "recovery" means any operation the principal result of which is waste serving a useful purpose by replacing other materials which would otherwise have been used to fulfil a particular function, or waste being prepared to fulfil that function, in the plant or in the wider economy. Annex II sets out a non-exhaustive list of recovery operations'. The concept therefore encompasses P2GreeN style activities and Annex II also includes 'recycling/reclamation of organic substances which are not used as solvents (including composting and other biological transformation processes)'.

considered hazardous within this list.⁴⁶ It would appear therefore that the EU considers human excreta as non-hazardous (despite the Annex III criteria).

Crucially, Article 23 mandates that 'Member States shall require any establishment or undertaking intending to carry out waste treatment to obtain a permit from the competent authority'. However, Member States may exempt those undertaking 'recovery of waste',⁴⁷ where it creates general rules for such exemptions (including types and quantities of waste and treatment methods) and specific conditions for any hazardous waste and informs the Commission of such rules.⁴⁸ Even where an exemption is granted, the competent authority must still keep a register of those with exemptions.⁴⁹ The Commission may also create minimum standards for waste treatment activities.⁵⁰ Relevant establishments and undertakings must also keep appropriate records and be subject to inspections.⁵¹ Member States are also responsible for providing for penalties for infringement of the Directive and ensuring compliance through effective enforcement.⁵² However, the Directive, in accordance with subsidiarity, leaves much of the detail to the Member States to develop in their transposition and implementation.

The UWWTD aims to improve water quality (through a range of stricter water treatment); ensure access to sanitation for everyone; promote circularity (through water reuse and recovery of resources, including nutrients); and address climate change (with both mitigation and adaptation measures). The primary focus is on regulating 'the collection, treatment and discharge of urban wastewater...'.⁵³ This is to be achieved through a network of 'collecting systems'⁵⁴ and, as a derogation where appropriate, 'individual systems'.⁵⁵ Conditions apply for both types of systems, with the Commission required to specify minimum requirements for the individual systems by 2 January 2028.⁵⁶ Although,

⁴⁶ Commission Decision of 3 May 2000 replacing Decision 94/3/EC establishing a list of wastes pursuant to Article 1(a) of Council Directive 75/442/EEC on waste and Council Decision 94/904/EC establishing a list of hazardous waste pursuant to Article 1(4) of Council Directive 91/689/EEC on hazardous waste (notified under document number C(2000) 1147) [2000] OJ L226/3 as amended. This is confirmed in Commission notice on technical guidance on the classification of waste C/2018/1447, [2018] OJ C124/1.

⁴⁷ Article 24.

⁴⁸ Article 25.

⁴⁹ Article 26.

⁵⁰ Article 27.

⁵¹ Articles 34 and 35.

⁵² Article 36.

⁵³ Article 1 in full states: 'This Directive lays down rules on the collection, treatment and discharge of urban wastewater, to protect the environment and human health, in line with the One Health approach, while progressively reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to sustainable levels, improving the energy balance of urban wastewater collection and treatment activities and contributing to the transition towards a circular economy. It also lays down rules on access to sanitation for all, on transparency of the urban wastewater sector, on the regular surveillance of relevant public health parameters in urban wastewater and on the implementation of the polluter-pays principle.'

⁵⁴ Article 3.

⁵⁵ Article 4.

⁵⁶ Article 4(4).

as noted above, the existence of a system does not necessarily mean that such a system needs to be used by individuals for all human excreta.

Article 11 of the UWWTD imposes requirements regarding energy sources for UWWT plants (and the 'collecting systems connected to them') 'treating a load of 10 000 p.e. and above', with an eventual obligation of 'energy neutrality' by 2045. This means that energy must be produced from renewable sources 'by or on behalf of the owners or the operators of such urban wastewater treatment plants' equating to 20%, 40%, 70% and eventually 100% of the total annual energy used in such plants, even if the energy produced is not used on-site. The renewable energy specifically 'shall not comprise purchased renewable energy'. As treating wastewater, including for the purposes of recovering nutrients or water for use in agriculture, is an energy-intensive operation, this is a significant obligation. Some limited derogations are available, on an exceptional basis.

The key criteria are within Articles 6-8 of the UWWTD, which provide for secondary,⁵⁷ tertiary⁵⁸ and quaternary treatment⁵⁹ – with specific requirements about the applicability of these treatments across a staggered timeline depending on the type and size of system. Derogations are possible, but generally speaking over a staggered timeline: all discharges from urban wastewater treatment plants for agglomerations of 1,000 people and above must satisfy the requirements of secondary treatment;⁶⁰ all discharges from urban wastewater treatment plants for agglomerations of 150,000 and above must satisfy the requirements of tertiary treatment;⁶¹ all discharges to areas⁶² that are sensitive to eutrophication (including both phosphorous and nitrogen sensitive areas), from urban wastewater treatment plants for agglomerations of 10,000 and above, must satisfy the requirements of tertiary treatment;⁶³ all discharges from urban wastewater treatment plants for agglomerations of 150,000 and above must satisfy the requirements of quaternary treatment;⁶⁴ and all discharges to areas⁶⁵ where 'the concentration or the accumulation of micropollutants from urban wastewater treatment plants represents a risk for the environment or human health' from urban wastewater treatment plants for

⁵⁷ Part B and Table 1 of Annex 1.

⁵⁸ Details in Part B and Table 2 of Annex 1.

⁵⁹ Part B and Table 3 of Annex 1.

⁶⁰ Article 6. As per Article 2(12) this 'means treatment of urban wastewater by a process generally involving biological treatment with a secondary settlement or another process which reduces biodegradable organic matter from urban wastewater'. Article 2(11) states that primary treatment 'means treatment of urban wastewater by a physical or chemical process, or both, involving settlement of suspended solids, or other processes in which the BOD5 of the incoming wastewater is reduced by at least 20 % before discharge and the total suspended solids of the incoming wastewater are reduced by at least 50 %'.

⁶¹ Article 7. As per Article 2(13) this 'means treatment of urban wastewater by a process which reduces nitrogen or phosphorus, or both, in urban wastewater'

⁶² Including the surrounding catchment area.

⁶³ Article 7(3).

⁶⁴ Article 8. As per Article 2(14) this 'means treatment of urban wastewater by a process which reduces a broad spectrum of micropollutants in urban wastewater'. However, this is also complemented by Article 9's provisions on 'extended producer responsibility', whereby relevant producers are to cover substantial costs involved in compliance with Article 8.

⁶⁵ Article 8(4).

agglomerations of 10,000 and above must satisfy the requirements of quaternary treatment. Individual systems must, at a minimum, be 'designed, operated and maintained in a manner that achieves the same level of environmental and human health protection as the secondary and tertiary treatments'.⁶⁶ Annex I, Part B's section on discharges also notes that 'Requirements that are more stringent than those set out in Tables 1, 2 and 3 shall be applied where necessary to ensure that the receiving waters fulfil the requirements laid down in Directives 2000/60/EC, 2008/56/EC, 2008/105/EC and 2006/7/EC.' Further, Article 18 provides for risk assessments and for the potential need for Member States to take additional measures, including the requirement for the treatments to be applied to individual systems and to plants for agglomerations below the relevant thresholds.

The tertiary treatment bears highlighting in some greater detail. Article 7 refers to Annex I, Table 2, which outlines the levels of reductions required for phosphorous and/or nitrogen. These reductions are significant (varying between 80 and 90%) and are largely dependent on the population the plants cater for as well as the concentration levels of the nutrients. The focus on removal of these nutrients is primarily to address concerns over water pollution and specifically eutrophication. However, it is a very significant burden and emphasises removal rather than recovery or circularity. There is little clarity here as to what should be done with such nutrients, with the potential for them to be further 'wasted'. Further, it does not, on first appearances, facilitate the option of 'fertigation' and the potential desirability of enhanced water for irrigation.

However, Article 15(1), which focusses on the reuse of water and especially in agriculture,⁶⁷ states that 'where treated urban wastewater is reused for agricultural irrigation, Member States may derogate from the requirements for tertiary treatment in

⁶⁶ Article 4(2).

⁶⁷ The entire clause is worth including here in full: 'Member States shall systematically promote the reuse of treated wastewater from all urban wastewater treatment plants where appropriate, especially in water-stressed areas, and for all appropriate purposes. The potential for the reuse of treated wastewater shall be assessed in a manner that takes into account the river basin management plans established under Directive 2000/60/EC ('river basin management plans') and Member States' decisions under Article 2(2) of Regulation (EU) 2020/741. Member States shall ensure that, when treated urban wastewater is reused or if the reuse is planned, it does not endanger the ecological flow of the receiving waters and there is no adverse effect for the environment or human health. Where treated wastewater is reused for agricultural irrigation, it shall comply with the requirements of Regulation (EU) 2020/741. Where strategies on water resilience at Member State level are available, measures on promoting the reuse of treated wastewater and on the reuse itself shall be considered in those strategies. Where treated urban wastewater is reused for agricultural irrigation, Member States may derogate from the requirements for tertiary treatment in Part B and Table 2 of Annex I, for the fraction of treated urban wastewater that is exclusively destined for reuse in agricultural irrigation, where all of the following can be demonstrated: (a) the nutrient content in the fraction reused does not exceed the nutrient demand of the targeted crops; (b) there are no risks for the environment, particularly in relation to eutrophication of the waters in the same catchment area; (c) there are no risks to human health particularly in relation to pathogenic organisms; (d) the urban wastewater treatment plant has enough capacity to treat or store urban wastewater, in order to avoid discharges into receiving waters of urban wastewater which do not meet the requirements set out in Part B and Table 2 of Annex I in accordance with the methods for monitoring and evaluation of results laid down in Part C of Annex I.'

Part B and Table 2 of Annex I, for the fraction of treated urban wastewater that is exclusively destined for reuse in agricultural irrigation, where all of the following can be demonstrated: (a) the nutrient content in the fraction reused does not exceed the nutrient demand of the targeted crops; (b) there are no risks for the environment, particularly in relation to eutrophication of the waters in the same catchment area; (c) there are no risks to human health particularly in relation to pathogenic organisms; (d) the urban wastewater treatment plant has enough capacity to treat or store urban wastewater, in order to avoid discharges into receiving waters of urban wastewater which do not meet the requirements set out in Part B and Table 2 of Annex I in accordance with the methods for monitoring and evaluation of results laid down in Part C of Annex I.' I.e. treated water for agricultural irrigation does not need to be subject to reductions in phosphorous or nitrogen where these conditions are fulfilled. This is complemented by 'note 2' in Table 2 of Annex I, which provides that: 'If a fraction of treated urban wastewater is used for agricultural irrigation, nutrients in that fraction may be included in the calculation of the influent load and be excluded from the discharged load.' Interestingly, the implication is also that such use is not considered a 'discharge' and it also provides the plant operators with further leeway regarding the remaining wastewater as the twin inclusion-exclusion approach enables agricultural irrigation to impact significantly the calculation of any reductions for the purposes of Table 2/Article 7.

Finally, Article 20 addresses sludge management and resource recovery, in particular focussing on phosphorous and nitrogen. Article 20(1) states that 'Member States shall encourage the recovery of valuable resources and take the measures necessary to ensure that sludge management conforms to the waste hierarchy provided for in Article 4 of Directive 2008/98/EC. Such sludge management shall: (a) maximise prevention; (b) prepare for reuse, recycling and other recovery of resources, in particular phosphorus and nitrogen, taking into account national or local valorisation options; and (c) minimise the adverse effects on the environment and human health.' Article 20(2) then provides for the Commission to create by 2 January 2028 'delegated acts... specifying a combined minimum reuse and recycling rate for phosphorus from sludge and from urban wastewater not reused under the derogation of Article 15(1), taking into account...' a range of considerations including being harmless to the environment and human health. Interestingly, Article 20 does not directly engage with the Sewage Sludge Directive, but the use of sewage sludge, including the recovery of phosphorous and nitrogen, clearly encompasses its use on agricultural land as a fertiliser.

Thus, subsequent to treatment under the UWWTD, besides general discharges, the legislation envisages two key substances or pathways for human excreta to be used in agriculture:⁶⁸ the use of reclaimed water as a form of irrigation and the spreading of the

⁶⁸ The legislation does not clearly address other options, e.g. the extraction of solid substances (e.g. faeces) other than sewage sludge, or if treated water is to be used in agriculture other than as irrigation (e.g. as fertiliser). Provided that the substances have been treated in accordance with the UWWTD, it seems feasible that a Member State could enable such approaches – akin to a discharge from the UWWT plan. However, if they have been treated accordingly, they may have had much of the nutrients removed.

sewage sludge as a form of fertiliser (whether certified as such or not). These pathways are based in the Water Reuse Regulation, the Sewage Sludge Directive and the Fertilising Products Regulation – all discussed below.

3.6 Next steps post-treatment

Following treatment of the waste, different possibilities arise. First, as mentioned, the EU provides for the regulated use of certain waste products in some contexts, typically where these have been subject to further treatments. Three options are of great relevance to P2GreeN and similar activities: sewage sludge for spreading on land, reclaimed water for irrigation, and the use of waste products/substances derived from waste in a fertilising product. Second, in principle, EU legislation provides that a substance can cease to be waste if specific conditions are fulfilled. However, there are very few pathways at the EU-level to achieve this in practice and instead it is largely left to the Member States to implement – creating further uncertainty and variations across the EU. Again, in principle, there is potential for overlap between these possibilities, e.g. a waste product can be regulated for use and simultaneously could meet relevant criteria such that it would no longer be deemed waste.

3.6.1 Regulated use of waste in agriculture

Three key pieces of EU legislation are of relevance here – the Sewage Sludge Directive (Directive 86/278)⁶⁹, (SSD) the Water Reuse Regulation – Regulation (EU) 2020/741⁷⁰ (WRR) and the Fertilising Products Regulation- Regulation (EU) 2019/1009⁷¹ (FPR). Both the SSD and the WRR address substances post-treatment under the UWWTD and are effectively a continuation of the waste regime.⁷² The FPR is not a piece of waste legislation but permits the use of some waste or substances derived from waste in the manufacturing of EU fertilising products. All three are addressed in more detail in Chapters 4 and 5 below. The purpose here is to outline briefly the approach within the three laws to the substances as waste. These are directly relevant to some, but not all, P2GreeN

⁶⁹ Council Directive 86/278/EEC of 12 June 1986 on the protection of the environment, and in particular of the soil, when sewage sludge is used in agriculture [1986] OJ L 181

⁷⁰ Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse [2020] OJ L 177

⁷¹ Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products and amending Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003 [2019] OJ L 170

⁷² They also enable the substances to continue to fall outside the scope of the WFD, courtesy of the exclusion under Article 2(2) of the WFD.

and similar activities – together, they can also provide broader insights for potential reforms.

The SSD (discussed in 5.4) addresses the residual sludge post-treatment under the UWWTD – while there might appear to be significant similarities, it does not address mixed urine and faeces removed at an earlier stage.⁷³ This sludge is expressly permitted to be spread on agricultural land, with the aim being to encourage ‘the correct use’ and avoid harm to humans or the environment.⁷⁴ This is distinct from the EU fertiliser legislation, which we will return to shortly. The SSD imposes a range of criteria, depending on the source of the sludge,⁷⁵ e.g. regarding heavy metal concentrations,⁷⁶ requirements for further treatment,⁷⁷ and controls on where spreading may occur (linked to the type of land and crops). However, it is worth highlighting that this legislation was created in 1986 and is now outdated, with a clear need, for instance, to enhance standards, address new pollutants and avail of modern technologies. In particular, the sludge tends to have relatively high concentrations of heavy metals and other contaminants. It compares poorly from an environmental and health perspective with the WRR, which contains extensive requirements. There is also poor uptake of this pathway across most Member States, as discussed in Chapter 5. Finally, this is a piece of EU waste legislation and the sludge remains as ‘waste’ for the time-being,⁷⁸ unless it simultaneously meets the conditions under Article 6(1) WFD discussed below.⁷⁹

The WRR creates minimum standards and procedural requirements for Member States for the (re)use of reclaimed water in agriculture. This is water that has been treated under the UWWTD and then is subject to further treatments to meet the requisite standards. These standards include ones listed within the Regulation and then an extensive range incorporated by reference to other legislation, e.g. via reference to the Environmental Quality Standards Directive.⁸⁰ There are criteria regarding quality, monitoring and risk management plans, which are discussed in detail in Chapter 4. Those producing and supplying such water must be subject to a permit, with Member States able to require permits also for those using the water.⁸¹ Of note, despite being a Regulation, the WRR does not mandate uptake by Member States – Member States may opt-out from the

⁷³ It is therefore of limited relevance to P2Green, but still is worth addressing briefly for more general insights.

⁷⁴ Article 1 states: ‘The purpose of this Directive is to regulate the use of sewage sludge in agriculture in such a way as to prevent harmful effects on soil, vegetation, animals and man, thereby encouraging the correct use of such sewage sludge.’

⁷⁵ Article 3.

⁷⁶ Articles 4 and 5 and Annexes IA, IB and IC.

⁷⁷ Article 6 – unless injected or worked into the soil.

⁷⁸ This is reflected in the original preamble to the Directive, which noted the applicability to sewage sludge of EU legislation on toxic and dangerous waste – that legislation has since been repealed and replaced by the WFD, but the point remains relevant. It is also reflected in the discussion in *Sappi*.

⁷⁹ The potential for this is noted in *Sappi*, but the environmental and human health conditions in particular are highlighted as being central.

⁸⁰ See Articles 4 and 5 of the WRR, in conjunction with Annexes I and II.

⁸¹ Article 6 of the WRR.

system, provided that they justify it. Alternatively, they allow it but can add their own extra criteria or higher standards. As discussed in Chapter 4, the WRR does not expressly address whether the reclaimed water is still a form of waste (or, more specifically, waste water) or not, but it may nonetheless suffice for Article 6(1) WFD in practice.

While the FPR (discussed in Chapter 5, especially 5.5) is not a piece of waste legislation, it merits highlighting very briefly here. Beyond the FPR's inclusion of sewage sludge as an ingredient, it also provides for a range of other wastes to be ingredients (e.g. biowaste) and potentially substances extracted from human excreta (e.g. precipitates). Of great significance, the FPR also provides that final products created from waste products are to no longer be deemed waste legally once certified under the FPR, which has significant legal and commercial ramifications. Currently it does not offer viable pathways for P2Green, but amendments to the FPR could provide important new pathways for P2Green or similar products.

3.6.2 Article 6 – end-of-waste status

The purpose of waste legislation is largely to manage resources and avoid harmful effects to the environment and human health, with an express mention to the 'circular economy' introduced to Article 1 through a subsequent amendment. Article 6 reflects these ideas, by creating frameworks and procedures that could enable a substance to cease to be waste for the purposes of the WFD.⁸² Article 6(1) mandates that 'Member States shall take appropriate measures to ensure that waste which has undergone a recycling or other recovery operation is considered to have ceased to be waste if it complies with the following conditions:

- (a) the substance or object is to be used for specific purposes;
- (b) a market or demand exists for such a substance or object;
- (c) the substance or object fulfils the technical requirements for the specific purposes and meets the existing legislation and standards applicable to products; and
- (d) the use of the substance or object will not lead to overall adverse environmental or human health impacts.

Significantly, Article 6(5) imposes an obligation on 'the natural or legal person who: (a) uses, for the first time, a material that has ceased to be waste and that has not been placed on the market; or (b) places a material on the market for the first time after it has ceased to be waste, shall ensure that the material meets relevant requirements under the applicable chemical and product related legislation. The conditions laid down in paragraph 1 have to be met before the legislation on chemicals and products applies to

⁸² Introduced in the current 2008 WFD, it sought to respond to and codify some of the earlier approaches by the CJEU.

the material that has ceased to be waste.’ i.e. anyone receiving and using or marketing such a product for the first time has an onus to check and ensure compliance with Article 6(1), as well as all relevant chemical and product related legislation.

Turning back to the procedure for ceasing to be waste, alongside the obligation in Article 6(1), Article 6, as amended, expressly provides for ‘*detailed* criteria’ (emphasis added) to be established at the EU level or national level (where the EU has not set relevant criteria),⁸³ or for Member States to take ‘case-by-case decisions’ regarding specific waste. Further conditions apply to each of these, with express focus points on the environment and human health. Any EU criteria must ‘ensure a high level of protection of the environment and human health and facilitate the prudent and rational utilisation of natural resources.’⁸⁴ In creating them, the Commission must also ‘take account of the relevant criteria established by Member States in accordance with paragraph 3 and ... take as a starting point the most stringent and environmentally protective of those criteria.’ Slightly lesser obligations apply to the Member States, but the environment and human health remain central throughout. Indeed, the CJEU has stated in *Sappi* that the sewage sludge being discussed there must be ‘harmless’ and ‘free from any dangerous substance’.⁸⁵ It is worth noting that the CJEU has also highlighted that the environmental benefits, including the preservation of natural resources and the development of a circular economy are valid considerations in evaluating the overall environmental and human health impacts.⁸⁶

However, the conditions in Article 6(1) remain central to the development of any EU or national criteria, along with the WFD’s objectives. The CJEU in *Porr Bau*, in a reference from Austria, stated that national legislation would be precluded if it would only grant end-of-waste status when the substances (in this case, soil ‘of the highest quality class’) ‘are used directly as a substitute and their holder has satisfied the formal criteria which are irrelevant for the purposes of environmental protection, if those criteria have the effect of undermining the attainment of the objectives of that directive’.⁸⁷ Of note, the original requirement in Article 6(1) that the substance or object was ‘commonly used’ was removed, but there is still a requirement that a market or demand exists. While a substance remains waste and before end-of-waste criteria are established, it may be very difficult to demonstrate a market or demand. Yet, if the substance ceased being waste, this might in itself facilitate such a demand. Thus, this condition within Article 6 conflicts with the aims of circularity and may undermine its purpose.

It is also essential to highlight the nature of the obligations and permissions within Article 6 regarding the creation of criteria. While Member States must ‘take appropriate

⁸³ This option for national criteria was newly introduced since the WFD was created – previously the Article only provided for EU-level criteria or national case-by-case decisions.

⁸⁴ Article 6(2).

⁸⁵ Para 66.

⁸⁶ *Sappi*, para 67 and 68.

⁸⁷ Para 77.

measures' as per Article 6(1),⁸⁸ Member States 'may establish detailed criteria' where the EU has not set relevant criteria,⁸⁹ or 'may decide on a case-by-case basis, or take appropriate measures to verify, that certain waste has ceased to be waste' (emphasis added) where neither the EU nor the Member State has set relevant criteria. Both statements are enabling, rather obligatory.⁹⁰ However, since the Member States must take appropriate measures, one can argue that, if the EU has not created relevant criteria, then the Member States should create their own criteria to implement this provision effectively and the conditions therein. However, this would not necessarily mean for all or even most – as Article 6 uses the phrase 'appropriate measures' and also provides for the Commission to create EU-wide criteria (with specific elements to be included) and for a case-by-case approach where criteria have not been set at either level. What this means however is that, if there are neither EU nor national criteria, then in principle the Member State must make a case-by-case decision on the end-of-waste status of a substance based on Article 6(1).⁹¹

In contrast with the provision on national criteria and complementing the national obligations more generally, Article 6(2) states that 'the Commission shall monitor the development of national end-of-waste criteria in Member States and assess the need to develop Union-wide criteria on this basis. To that end, and where appropriate, the Commission shall adopt implementing acts in order to establish detailed criteria on the uniform application of the conditions laid down in paragraph 1 to certain types of waste.' This does not mandate the creation generally of EU-level end-of-waste criteria and it is most likely to be triggered by the development of contrasting criteria in a few or several Member States. Yet, objectively, the introduction of transitioning to a circular economy in Article 1 should inform the Commission's assessment of the need for EU-level criteria – including the *lack of* development of national criteria and, for instance, the status of substances as comprising or containing critical raw material (and not necessarily just

⁸⁸ This targeted obligation contrasts with the original version of Article 6(1).

⁸⁹ Article 6(3).

⁹⁰ Although, where Member States set criteria, they must inform the Commission of these criteria. Where the decision is on a case-by-case basis, this is not required to be informed.

⁹¹ This is supported implicitly by the CJEU in *Porr Bau*, at paras 76 and 77, with the national court being obliged to hold that the end-of waste status of the substance has been achieved if the conditions of Article 6(1) have been fulfilled, despite the existence of further, unnecessary conditions in national law. I.e. there were no EU-level criteria and the national criteria were excessive, so the court was to make a determination based on Article 6(1) conditions. However, such an interpretation is dependent on the amended version of Article 6(1), which places a mandatory obligation on Member States, in contrast with the original version of the provision. See the flagging of this variation as one of future significance in Johansson, O. (2023). The End-of-Waste for the Transition to Circular Economy: A Legal Review of the European Union Waste Framework Directive. *Environmental Policy and Law*, 53(2-3), 167-179.

strategic raw material)⁹² or simply the abundance of the waste. Of note, phosphorous is considered a critical raw material.⁹³

Yet, there has been very limited development of end-of-waste criteria at the EU level, with only a handful to-date, e.g. glass cullet, and copper, iron, steel and aluminium scrap metal.⁹⁴ Of note, the Commission's Joint Research Centre undertook research on a methodology for developing end-of-waste criteria that was published in 2009.⁹⁵ This included a case-study on compost, which included compost derived from sewage sludge. It proposed potential end-of-waste criteria and a set of data to support EU-level action. However, no such criteria (identical or amended) have been adopted by the Commission. While recycled plastics and textiles are the focus of the development of potential EU end-of-waste criteria,⁹⁶ a JRC 2022 report placed 'bio-materials and materials recovered/produced from bio-materials' (including residual sludge from UWWT and phosphorous) midway in the priority for development of end-of-waste criteria.⁹⁷ The report stated that development was 'supported by industry representatives, but reported as not a priority stream by one or more Member States' representatives' – scoring therefore a 2 out of 3.⁹⁸

The EU's FPR is an oddity relative to these implementing measures, as it is a much broader piece of legislation that is the central Regulation in the fertiliser regime and is not primarily targeted at implementing Article 6. Yet, it does exactly this. Article 19 on 'end-of waste status' states that the 'Regulation lays down criteria in accordance with which material that constitutes waste, as defined in Directive 2008/98/EC, can cease to be waste, if it is contained in a compliant EU fertilising product. In such cases, the recovery operation under this Regulation shall be performed before the material ceases to be waste, and the material shall be considered to comply with the conditions laid down in Article 6 of that Directive and therefore to have ceased to be waste from the moment that the EU declaration of conformity was drawn up.' This includes where sewage is used, but, as discussed elsewhere in this report, the approach to human excreta within the FPR is generally very restrictive. Further, the Regulation only provides for the material to cease

⁹² Regulation (EU) 2024/1252 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1724 and (EU) 2019/1020, [2024] OJ L2024/1252, ...

⁹³ Annex II, Section 1. The difficulty in increasing production is one criterion for determining if the material should be considered strategic instead. This expressly takes into account the difficulty in increasing global annual production. As the list of considerations is not exhaustive, one could expect that access should also be a factor, with issues such as the war in Ukraine and the impacted relationship with Russia therefore be significant considerations when it comes to evaluating the significance of phosphorous.

⁹⁴ See more details in the [Waste Framework Directive – Europa](#).

⁹⁵ [Delgado Sancho L, Catarino A, Eder P, Litten D, Luo Z, Villanueva Krzyzaniak A. End-of-Waste Criteria. EUR 23990 EN. Luxembourg \(Luxembourg\): European Commission; 2009. JRC53238.](#)

⁹⁶ Refer to the following: [Waste Framework Directive – Europa](#) and [End-of-waste - JRC](#).

⁹⁷ [Orveillon, G., Pierri, E., Egle, L., Gerbendahl, A., Wessman, P., Garcia John, E. and Saveyn, H., Scoping possible further EU-wide end-of-waste and by-product criteria, EUR 31007 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-49046-3, doi:10.2760/067213, JRC128647.](#)

⁹⁸ Ibid, Table 4 on p.18.

to be waste when the final product is created, has successfully passed the conformity assessment and the EU Declaration of conformity is signed by the manufacturer– the substances are still waste while they are ingredients (unless they have previously complied with relevant criteria in the relevant Member State and been granted end-of-waste status there).

Nationally, the current norm appears to be the facilitation of case-by-case decisions – perhaps because initially the WFD did not expressly provide for national criteria to be established or because of the heavy burden of creating criteria for a wide range of substances, in contrast with letting the individual/company provide all of the initial evidence. By March 2023, there were approximately 74 set of criteria across 27 Member States,⁹⁹ which only equates to under three per Member State. Several of these are also now redundant, as they related to, for instance, scrap metal, where the EU has since established its own criteria. While it is harder to identify and map authoritatively the case-by-case decisions, as these do not need to be notified, there is evidence to indicate a relatively much greater number of these. For instance, within Ireland, there is one national set of criteria for recycled aggregates, 14 individual decisions, plus 4 further individual applications that were withdrawn due to the creation of the criteria for recycled aggregates.¹⁰⁰ Of the 14 current decisions, a further 4 of them are plastics, which would become redundant if and when the EU's criteria are established.¹⁰¹ Thus, in Ireland, the Irish Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA's) draft policy document in this field, state that 'the Agency does not currently have plans to lead on establishing any 'generic' end-of-waste criteria'.¹⁰² Yet, the EPA states alongside this that it 'encourages' groups or organisations to apply to establish criteria that would apply 'for an entire sector and for the benefit of all parties operating within it', which 'can efficiently deliver the objectives of a circular economy'. Thus, the competent authority is effectively saying that it is happy to create national criteria if industry takes the lead through providing the requisite evidence. Alternatively, the EPA states that it will facilitate case-by-case decisions.

From the P2Green regions, Sweden is an example worth highlighting, where there are no end-of-waste criteria and no intention¹⁰³. Instead, the conditions from Article 6(1) have been transposed into Chapter 15, Section 9(a) of the Environmental Code¹⁰⁴. The

⁹⁹ Johansson, O. (2023). The End-of-Waste for the Transition to Circular Economy: A Legal Review of the European Union Waste Framework Directive. *Environmental Policy and Law*, 53(2-3), 167-179.

¹⁰⁰ Refer to [End-of-waste criteria in Ireland](#).

¹⁰¹ As an aside, there is no obligation on the EU to take into account the individual decisions when developing EU-wide criteria, although where they are aware of these decisions it is likely to influence whether EU-wide measures are needed or not.

¹⁰² Available at [End-of-Waste-Guidance Document \(EPA\)](#), p.11.

¹⁰³ [Board of Agriculture's 2023 Report](#), at Section 1.5.5 on p.95.

¹⁰⁴ Available at [Miljöbalk \(1998:808\)](#), "När avfall upphör att vara avfall 9 a § Avfall som har genomgått ett återvinningsförfarande upphör att vara avfall om 1. ämnet eller föremålet ska användas för ett visst ändamål, 2. det finns en marknad för eller efterfrågan på sådana ämnen eller föremål, 3. ämnet eller föremålet uppfyller tillämpliga krav i lag och annan författning, och 4. användningen av ämnet eller föremålet inte leder till allmänt negativa följder för människors hälsa eller miljön. Lag (2020:601)." Accessed 16th November 2025.

Swedish EPA notes that the core responsibility is on the operator to self-assess as to whether waste has ceased to be waste in accordance with these provisions, with the supervisory authority then providing a statement of non-compliance/disagreement with the assessment or a *de facto*¹⁰⁵. One potential mechanism to help operators evidence compliance with Chapter 15, Section 9(a) of the Code/Article 6(1) WFD would be to comply with a relevant tailored voluntary certificate. This is something being investigated currently by a P2Green partner and their collaborators in Sweden.¹⁰⁶

Interestingly, the French approach for waste in fertilisers is somewhat similar to the FPR, whereby under L255-12 of the Code Rural et de la Peche Maritime, once a substance is authorised as a fertiliser within France, it ceases to be waste – subject to meeting the criteria in L541-4-3 of the Code de l' Environnement, which include the core conditions in Article 6(1) of the WFD.¹⁰⁷

However, it is essential to highlight a key limitation with Article 6, where the Commission has not created EU-level criteria, as implicitly recognised in the French environmental law:¹⁰⁸ a substance or object might be deemed to no longer be waste in one Member State, but then still be considered waste in other Member States. This impacts on the management and marketability of the products, as it can impact upon both where the product is sold or used and where it can travel through. While it is open to other Member States to recognise the end-of-waste status granted/recognised in the originating Member State, this might not be appealing where, for instance, there are no national criteria either and the procedure for obtaining end-of-waste status is a self-assessment or only loosely supervised.

Thus, while the provision seemingly opens up several pathways for a substance to cease to be waste, it is somewhat unclear and quite limited in practice. Widespread use of the provision and legal certainty relies on development of criteria nationally or, preferably, at the EU level, rather than use of the case-by-case option.

3.7 Transport of waste

Transport of waste within an individual Member States is largely addressed by the Member State's implementation of the relevant EU legislation, e.g. within the waste management permits for the WFD or within the rules regarding collecting wastewater for

¹⁰⁵ See [Guidance](#) from the Swedish EPA on when waste ceases to be waste:. The EPA have actively decided not to make a decision – saying that the assessment could change, e.g. depending on the market context.

¹⁰⁶ See for instance "[Five projects granted seed funding at SLU Urban Futures](#), accessed 28 October 2025.

¹⁰⁷ The provision also provides for the competent authority to establish criteria indicating how the conditions may be met, e.g. including pollutant limit levels. L541-4-3 is complemented then by Articles D541-12-4 to D541-12-14, introduced by décrets, which provide (akin to Article 6 of the WFD) for further criteria to be established).

¹⁰⁸ See L.541-4-3 IV of the Code de l'Environnement, regarding the potential continued applicability of the EU legislation regarding shipments of waste.

UWWT plants.¹⁰⁹ However, once the substances are intended for shipping across borders, the law becomes more complicated. Factors include: a) what is the substance being shipped?; b) where is the substance being shipped?; c) for what purposes (e.g. for disposal or recovery operations)?; and d) is it hazardous or not? Notably, these procedures remain relevant even if the substance has gone through a recovery operation and can be used usefully without further treatment unless either the EU or all relevant Member States¹¹⁰ consider the substance to no longer be waste (see the following section regarding ceasing to be waste). If the substance is no longer deemed waste by the EU, then these rules are inapplicable.

The currently applicable law is Waste Shipment Regulation, Regulation 1013/2006, which will continue to apply in part until 2027. It is being replaced by the new Waste Shipment Regulation (EU) 2024/1157 (WSR),¹¹¹ which will involve a more centralised and electronic approach intended to simplify procedures. While the law addresses imports and exports to and from the EU,¹¹² of most relevance for P2Green activities and similar currently is the potential to move waste and treated substances within the EU.

A key point to note is that 'shipments of waste waters' covered by the UWWTD or other relevant EU legislation are excluded from the scope of the new WSR.¹¹³ Again, the definition of 'waste water' becomes central to the applicability of the law, with further insights provided by the Regulation's Preamble – which states duplication of applicable EU law should be avoided and that 'collection and conduction of wastewater through sewage systems pursuant to relevant Union legislation should not be considered as transport of waste under this Regulation.'¹¹⁴ The implication therefore is that the Regulation would not apply to wastewaters that are within 'collecting system' regulated under the UWWTD but would otherwise still fall within this Regulation. Similarly, human excreta that are not part of the wastewaters would still be subject to the Regulation, including pre- and post-treatment, unless no longer deemed waste at an EU-level.

For waste within the scope of the Regulation and that is destined for disposal or is deemed hazardous, as well as most mixed waste that is intended for recovery operations, there is an applicable prior notification and consent procedure.¹¹⁵ Prior consent is therefore needed from the competent authorities in all relevant States, including transit States.

¹⁰⁹ This is complemented by a general obligation to create a suitable regime for the 'supervision and control of the transport of waste' within a Member State, imposed under Article 36 of the 2024 Waste Shipment Regulation discussed below.

¹¹⁰ i.e. the sending and receiving Member States and all transit Member States.

¹¹¹ Regulation (EU) 2024/1157 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 on shipments of waste, amending Regulations (EU) No 1257/2013 and (EU) 2020/1056 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1013/2006, [2024] OJ L2024/1157.

¹¹² The law distinguishes between the EU, the rest of the OECD and non-OECD countries. Consideration of transport to/from non-EU countries is not included within the analysis here, but exports to OECD countries would seem feasible (with further criteria to be met) and highly challenging to non-OECD countries.

¹¹³ Article 2(2)(e).

¹¹⁴ Recitals 12 and 13 of the 2024 Waste Shipment Regulation.

¹¹⁵ Article 4.

However, for ‘green-listed’, non-hazardous wastes being transported within the EU for the purposes of recovery operations, only general information requirements apply.¹¹⁶ These must be provided in advance and include details regarding the nature of the waste, the intended recovery operation, destination etc, but crucially are not subject to prior consent. There is also a limited derogation provided for wastes intended for ‘experimental treatment trials’, where specific criteria are fulfilled, whereby there is a general information requirement but no need for prior consent.¹¹⁷

Of note, the EU’s List of Wastes created under the WFD is not the sole determining factor of (i) whether a substance is deemed hazardous or not for the purposes of this Regulation and (ii) whether prior consent is required or not. For instance, Article 4(2) outlines a list of reference points for determining whether a substance requires prior written notification and consent, of which the List of Wastes established under Article 7 is only one.¹¹⁸ The EU’s List of Wastes includes sewage sludge as non-hazardous, however, it is included within the ‘amber listed’ waste (requiring prior consent) in Annex IV, Part 2 under Code AC270 - Article 4(2)(a) expressly includes ‘wastes listed in Annex IV’. The Regulation does not expressly address human faeces or substances derived from human excreta (other than sewage sludge) such as compost or reclaimed water. However, it has what appears to be a catch-all in Article 4(2)(b) which applies the requirement for prior consent to: ‘wastes not classified under one single entry in either Annex III, Annex IIIB or Annex IV’.

Significantly, the Regulation provides that in the case of ‘classification issues’ where there is a conflict between the competent authorities in the dispatch and destination Member States, they shall be resolved as follows, for the purposes of the Regulation: if no agreement on whether waste or not waste, to be treated as waste; if no agreement on whether the substance is destined for recovery or disposal, to be treated as if being shipped for disposal; if no agreement ‘on the classification of waste destined for recovery as being listed in Annex III, Annex IIIA, Annex IIIB or Annex IV, or not listed in any of those Annexes, the shipment of that waste shall be subject to Article 4(2)’, i.e. prior consent.

¹¹⁶ Article 4(4).

¹¹⁷ Article 4(5).

¹¹⁸ Article 4(2) states: Shipments of the following wastes destined for recovery shall be subject to the procedure of prior written notification and consent, laid down in Chapter 1: (a) wastes listed in Annex IV; (b) wastes not classified under one single entry in either Annex III, Annex IIIB or Annex IV; (c) mixtures of wastes, unless listed in Annex IIIA; (d) waste classified as hazardous in the list of waste established pursuant to Article 7 of Directive 2008/98/EC; (e) wastes listed in Annex III or Annex IIIB and mixtures of wastes listed in Annex IIIA contaminated by other materials to an extent which: (i) increases the risks associated with the wastes sufficiently to render them appropriate for submission to the procedure of prior written notification and consent, when taking into account the list of waste referred to in Article 7 of Directive 2008/98/EC as well as the hazardous properties listed in Annex III to that Directive; or (ii) prevents the recovery of the wastes in an environmentally sound manner; (f) wastes or mixtures of wastes containing or contaminated with persistent organic pollutants (POPs) within the meaning of Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 in quantities meeting or exceeding a concentration limit indicated in Annex IV to that Regulation, which are not classified as hazardous waste.

Applicability to P2Green (and similar) activities and products: for any substances deemed wastewater and within a collecting system/sewer, this Regulation does not apply. For other human excreta inputs that fall outside the definition of wastewater or that are not within a sewer, it would seem likely that the Regulation applies. P2Green activities are likely to be deemed recovery operations (covering from collection through to application on the land or the point of ceasing to be waste, where applicable). Based on the EU's List of Wastes, the substances would seem to be considered non-hazardous. However, the Regulation goes beyond the List of Wastes and mandates prior consent for other substances, including for instance sewage sludge and 'wastes not classified under one single entry in either Annex III, Annex IIIB or Annex IV'. Consequently, it would seem likely that, other than for wastewater in a sewer, human excreta in its original or treated form requires prior consent for transport, while it is deemed to be waste in at least one of the relevant Member States.

It should also be noted that once the waste has arrived in the receiving Member State, it will likely be necessary to apply for a waste management permit or similar in that country.

The law on transboundary shipments of waste aspect of the law is reasonably sensible and is largely due to the need to implement the Basel Convention but is highly complex and burdensome. It is potentially unduly complex and burdensome where, for instance, a substance has already gone through a recovery operation and poses no risks to the environment or human health but is still deemed to be 'waste' in either the sending or receiving Member State.

3.8 Post-waste applicable Regulations – REACH

After the materials has ceased to be waste and is qualified as a product, e.g. a fertilising product, other regimes would need to be checked and complied with e.g. the Regulation (EC) 1907/2006 (REACH)¹¹⁹ and Regulation (EC) 1272/2008 CLP¹²⁰ Regulation. A detailed analysis of the two frameworks can be found in the previous deliverable - D3.7("Scoping review" describing the status of the legislative framework)¹²¹. Both

¹¹⁹ Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), establishing a European Chemicals Agency, amending Directive 1999/45/EC and repealing Council Regulation (EEC) No 793/93 and Commission Regulation (EC) No 1488/94 as well as Council Directive 76/769/EEC and Commission Directives 91/155/EEC, 93/67/EEC, 93/105/EC and 2000/21/EC [2006] OJ L 396, as amended

¹²⁰ Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures, amending and repealing Directives 67/548/EEC and 1999/45/EC, and amending Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 [2008] OJ L 353

¹²¹ Czarnik et al, D3.7 "Scoping review" describing the status of the legislative framework 2023, P2Green Consortium. Accessible at www.p2green.eu

Regulations apply only once materials have ceased to be waste within the meaning of the Waste Framework Directive, unless they are explicitly excluded from their scope.

Under the REACH Regulation, a chemical substance cannot be manufactured in or imported into the EU/EEA unless it has been registered with the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA). This obligation applies to companies manufacturing or importing one tonne or more of a substance per year, whether the substance is placed on the market on its own, in a mixture, or in an article.

REACH defines a substance as “*a chemical element and its compounds in the natural state or obtained by any manufacturing process, including any additive necessary to preserve its stability and any impurity deriving from the process used, but excluding any solvent which may be separated without affecting the stability of the substance or changing its composition*”. Under REACH¹²² substances can be categorised into:

- (a) monoconstituent substances (made up mostly of one main component with a few impurities),
- (b) multi-constituent substances (several main components) and
- (c) UVCBs (Unknown or Variable Composition, Complex Reaction Products or Biological Materials that cannot be identified by a precise chemical formula).

Given its nature, the material obtained after treatment of urine would most likely be considered a UVCB.

To register a substance, companies must provide information to ECHA on its properties, hazards and safe uses. This is submitted in a technical dossier, containing data on physicochemical, toxicological and ecotoxicological properties, generated through validated testing methods (in vitro studies, modelling, read-across, or, *in vivo* studies where no alternative exists). The aim is to demonstrate that the substance can be used safely throughout its life cycle.

For manufacturers or importers of 10 tonnes or more per year, a Chemical Safety Report (CSR) is also required. The CSR contains a detailed assessment of risks to human health and the environment and where relevant (depending on the hazards), it may include exposure scenarios for all identified uses, such as use as a fertiliser.

If a substance has already been registered, any new manufacturer or importer must join the existing Substance Information Exchange Forum (SIEF) and contribute to the costs of the testing that has already been performed. If the substance has never been registered, the first company to submit a registration becomes the Lead Registrant and is responsible for generating the required data and establishing a SIEF for future co-registrants. For urine-derived materials, the latter scenario applies, resulting in significant testing and data-generation costs for the initial registrant. Furthermore, if more than one

¹²² Under the CLP Regulation (as amended by Regulation (EU) 2024/2865), categories (a) (whenever the impurities or additives influence the classification), (b) and (c) fall under the concept of More Than One Constituent Substances (MOCS). In these cases, the hazardous properties of the material must be assessed at the level of each constituent rather than at the level of the substance as a whole.

urine-derived material exists, the need for separate registrations would depend on whether they can be considered the same substance based on the Substance Identity Profile (SIP) and the manufacturing process. If they do not meet the relevant criteria, multiple registrations may be required.

If a material is classified as waste under the WFD, REACH obligations apply only after it is no longer considered waste; therefore, determining this point in the process is essential. As EU-level end-of-waste criteria for human excreta are not available, the End-of-waste status may be achieved :

- (a) through compliance with national end-of-waste criteria (set by each Member State),
- (b) by case-by-case decisions nationally or
- (c) automatically at the product level when incorporated into an EU fertilising product that complies with the Fertilising Products Regulation (FPR)¹²³.

The potential for variations across Member States and waste streams also leads to the potential for considerable variation as to the timing of end-of-waste status.

However, it is worth noting that Annex V, Entry 12 of REACH exempts compost from registration when it is no longer waste.¹²⁴ This provision does not provide any clear indications that a relevant limiter should apply that would exclude faeces and specifically human faeces. So, according to our research this exemption likely applies to compost derived from human faecal matter as well. Although REACH registration may not be required, the relevant toxicological and ecotoxicological data for hazard classification of the product under CLP must be still produced. However, no such similar exemption exists within REACH for other P2Green products.

For instance, in principle, urine could cease to be waste at several stages:

- (a) immediately after collection at source,
- (b) after transport to the treatment facility, or
- (c) after treatment is complete.

The most practical and logical interpretation, considering also the WFD end-of-waste criteria, is that it would cease to be waste after treatment, when the final product is obtained. Where a manufacturer claims an exemption (i.e. that the material remains waste until that point), the burden of proof lies with the manufacturer.

¹²³ As stated in art. 10 of the FPR. Also, relevant explanations are available in the “Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 – the Fertilising Products Regulation- Frequently Asked Questions” document (e.g. question no 1.8 in version 16.06.2025.)

¹²⁴ Entry 12 of Annex V stating that "This exemption covers compost when it is potentially subject to registration, i.e, when it is no longer waste according to Directive 2008/98/EC, and is understood as being applicable to substances consisting of solid particulate material that has been sanitised and stabilized through the action of micro-organisms and that results from the composting treatment."

The FPR introduces stricter REACH-related obligations (often referred to as “REACH+”) requiring that all substances in EU fertilising products be REACH-registered, even below the ten-tonne or even the one-tonne threshold, with data requirements corresponding to the 10–100 tonne band and a CSR for their use as a fertiliser. Under REACH+, certain exemptions from the REACH registration obligation, as defined under REACH, are retained, but not all. For example, the REACH+ requirements continue to allow the exemptions listed under points 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 (only for magnesia) of Annex V of the REACH Regulation. However, the exemption under point 12 of Annex V, which covers compost, is not included among the accepted exemptions¹²⁵. Compost is not subject to REACH+ though, as there is not a relevant requirement under CMC3 for it, only for the composting additives.

The Chemical Omnibus VI proposal aims to simplify the regulatory frameworks for chemicals, cosmetics, and fertilisers, reducing administrative burdens and enhancing legal clarity¹²⁶. Initially, it proposed removing the REACH+ requirement so that substances in EU fertilising products would again follow the standard REACH rules. However, on 5 November 2025, the European Council adopted its position¹²⁷ to retain REACH+ obligations only for substances with the most severe harmonised hazard classifications (e.g. CMR Cat. 1, STOT RE Cat. 1, ED Cat. 1, PBT, and vPvB)¹²⁸. Trilogue negotiations with the European Parliament are expected to start in late 2025, with final adoption foreseen in 2026.

For P2GreeN partners, the simplification of REACH+ would be highly beneficial, particularly if the materials become permitted inputs under the FPR, because volumes produced in the pilot regions are likely expected to remain below one tonne per year (thus not requiring registration) or below ten tonnes per year (thus not requiring CSR) at least at the early stages of production.

3.9 Overall conclusions regarding waste

The waste regime is highly complex, burdensome and opaque. While some specificities exist within the regime, these do not adequately address P2GreeN-style activities. This limitation resounds throughout each aspect of the regime, at the EU and domestic level. Indeed, the domestic implementation and understanding of the EU laws helps highlight some of the ambiguities and potential for conflict and incoherency. Further concerns from a circular economy perspective relate to the obligations to remove nutrients from wastewater, without the focus being on their recovery for use where needed. This is compounded by the issues with Article 6 of the WFD, as reflected in its provisions and its

¹²⁵ Annex II, Part II, CMC1 (2).

¹²⁶ This [proposal](#) was issued alongside the Chemical Industry Action Plan, aligns with the objectives of the Clean Industrial Deal, and contributes to the broader simplification efforts for the agrifood sector announced in the Vision on Agriculture and Food.

¹²⁷ [Press Release - Council agrees position to simplify requirements for chemical products](#)

¹²⁸ [Council of the European Union, ST-15001-2025-INIT \(Council document, 2025\)](#) last accessed 15.11.2025.

very limited implementation, which has significant knock-on impacts regarding commercialisation and transport.

Innovators, including those in P2GreeN, currently need to identify which existing approach would best suit them and then argue for that to be applied, in light of the flexibility within the regime. To achieve this, they may need to consider which excreta are being collected, how and at what stage, what other substances are being combined with them (if any are waste, the entire mixture is deemed waste), how to demonstrate safety and a high level of environmental protection. While they might be operating within one Member State, it is essential to bear in mind that the EU terms are subject to interpretation by the CJEU and the legal landscape might therefore change not just by legislation but by judicial interpretations by the CJEU.

We will develop recommendations within the forthcoming D3.10 in May 2026, but for the time-being we have some initial suggestions for current actions and potential avenues for law reform. Key options that innovators may wish to argue for domestically are:

- For the application of the exclusion under Article 2(1)(f) if they are just collecting and using faeces and, for instance, straw and are not mixing it with any other 'waste';
- To have the WFD apply and a general waste permit granted, if there are no discharges;
- To have the UWWTD apply, but with the exception of the tertiary treatment as the substances are to be used for irrigation and/or there will be no discharges;
- To be permitted to collect human excreta using a sewer (if practical)/some suitable large-scale system;
- The development of national criteria under Article 6 WFD for the relevant products. These could be after an initial recovery operation has been undertaken that makes the excreta a useful ingredient and safe for human health and the environment.

Alongside these, it appears that the waste regime is an area ripe for reform to deliver on its own stated objectives. Potential reforms could broadly address issues of clarity, the existence of flexibility and the potential for alternative treatments. They could include, for instance:

- Clarifying that human excreta are usually/always deemed waste typically, across the EU (irrespective of the methodology used to collect them (at source, flushed/not flushed, etc)).
- But then expressly excluding human faeces and urine entirely from the concept of 'waste'/the scope of the WFD where they are to be used for agricultural production (e.g. as a fertilising product), provided this is undertaken in a way that does not harm the environment or human health. This would be akin to Article 2(1)(f) but expanded. This could be undertaken with or without a separate regulatory regime to manage such processes. Human faeces and urine that are not going through a

suitable process would still be able to fall back to be managed within the normal EU waste regimes, whether under the WFD or the UWWTD.

- Considering establishing a secondary materials category, akin to the approach to by-products but with greater flexibility and without unnecessary restrictions. (This would go beyond P2GreeN-style activities)
- Revising Article 6 of the WFD to accelerate the development of EU-wide criteria and to facilitate end-of-waste status (and EU-wide recognition of this) where the general conditions are fulfilled. If no EU or relevant national criteria exist, perhaps an EU decision could be made.
- Revising the UWWTD once more to facilitate the recovery of nutrients from wastewater before treatments are complete, e.g. through enabling large scale connections to divert materials and nutrients for recovery rather than sending for destruction at UWWT plants. Such reforms would need to be undertaken carefully to facilitate both P2GreeN-style activities and also the more general management of UWW and avoiding pollution.¹²⁹

Great care would need to be taken to ensure that any reforms respect principles such as subsidiarity, as well as the objectives of a high level of environmental and human health protection, along with the circular economy. In doing so, it must be remembered that most human excreta currently are normally not going to be recovered via P2GreeN-style activities and that any reforms must facilitate the safe treatment of human excreta more generally in the short-term.

¹²⁹ Most of these elements identified tentatively for reform are ones we have similarly noted in the EU's Call for Evidence for the EU Circular Economy Act, submitted on 6th November 2025.

4 Water Reuse

4.1 Water Reuse Regulation – Regulation 2020/741

As a response to increasing evidence that there is less rain in many parts of Europe, the EU is now equipped with a piece of legislation that makes the use of treated wastewater to irrigate crops safe, transparent and accessible to farmers: the Regulation on minimum requirements for water reuse for agricultural irrigation or as commonly known as the Water Reuse Regulation (WRR) – Regulation (EU) 2020/741.¹³⁰ An analysis of the principles of the WRR has been undertaken in the Deliverable 3.7 (“Scoping review” describing the status of the legislative framework)¹³¹ in Chapter 7. The key principles and some additional information are also summarised below.

The WRR was adopted in May 2020 and no dedicated EU framework existed before that. The topic of water reuse was partially and indirectly addressed through Directive 91/271, which is the previous UWWTD, and Directive 2000/60 about establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy. Article 12(1) of the previous UWWTD laid the foundations by stating that “treated wastewater shall be reused whenever appropriate. Disposal routes shall minimize the adverse effects on the environment.”

Article 15 of the revised UWWTD builds on this and endorses the reuse of wastewater, stressing that:

Member States shall systematically promote the reuse of treated wastewater from all urban wastewater treatment plants where appropriate, especially in water-stressed areas, and for all appropriate purposes. [...] Where strategies on water resilience at Member State level are available, measures on promoting the reuse of treated wastewater and on the reuse itself shall be considered in those strategies.

The WRR is a key mechanism to delivering on this. It requires that urban wastewater, which has already been treated in accordance with the UWWTD, is further treated to meet the minimum quality standards of this Regulation to be suitable for agricultural use. Through ensuring that the treated water is safe for reuse in agriculture, it increases the trust of consumers and farmers in this circular approach and thereby reduces the pressures from abstraction on increasingly scarce water resources. It also helps to preserve the water resources needed by the aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. This is

¹³⁰ Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse (Text with EEA relevance) *OJ L 177*, 5.6.2020, pp. 32–55 (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32020R0741>)

¹³¹ Czarnik et al, D3.7 “Scoping review” describing the status of the legislative framework 2023, P2Green Consortium. Accessible at www.p2green.eu

therefore a tool to help protect biodiversity, for achieving zero pollution and adapting to climate change.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the workflow to produce reclaimed water for use in agriculture.

The previous UWWTD established rules for the collection, treatment, and discharge of urban and certain industrial wastewaters to protect the environment and public health. It was recently revised (January 2025) to boost energy efficiency, remove micropollutants, and enhance public health protection.

According to the revised UWWTD Directive, wastewater intended to be discharged into water bodies must go through several levels of treatment (primary, secondary, tertiary and quaternary) depending on factors such as the size of the agglomeration and the sensitivity of the receiving environment in order to be discharged to water bodies. The definitions of the treatments are provided below¹³²:

- ‘primary treatment’ means treatment of urban wastewater by a physical or chemical process, or both, involving settlement of suspended solids, or other processes in which the BOD₅ of the incoming wastewater is reduced by at least 20% before discharge and the total suspended solids of the incoming wastewater are reduced by at least 50%;
- ‘secondary treatment’ means treatment of urban wastewater by a process generally involving biological treatment with a secondary settlement or another process which reduces biodegradable organic matter from urban wastewater;
- ‘tertiary treatment’ means treatment of urban wastewater by a process which reduces nitrogen or phosphorus, or both, in urban wastewater;
- ‘quaternary treatment’ means treatment of urban wastewater by a process which reduces a broad spectrum of micropollutants in urban wastewater.

According to Article 8 of the revised UWWTD, urban wastewater that is reused or planned to be reused must be treated in accordance with the requirements for quaternary treatment set out in Part B and Table 3 of Annex I. However, when a fraction of treated urban wastewater is used exclusively for agricultural irrigation, Member States may

¹³² Art.2 (points 11-14) of the Directive (EU) 2024/3019 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2024 concerning urban wastewater treatment (recast)

choose to exempt it from the tertiary treatment requirements used to remove nutrients if four cumulative, specific conditions are met, as follows:

- (a) the nutrient content in the fraction reused does not exceed the nutrient demand of the targeted crops;
- (b) there are no risks for the environment, particularly in relation to eutrophication of the waters in the same catchment area;
- (c) there are no risks to human health particularly in relation to pathogenic organisms;
- (d) the urban wastewater treatment plant has enough capacity to treat or store urban wastewater, in order to avoid discharges into receiving waters of urban wastewater which do not meet the requirements set out in Part B and Table 2 of Annex I in accordance with the methods for monitoring and evaluation of results laid down in Part C of Annex I.

So, the final effluent directed for water reuse can keep valuable nutrients but will still go through all needed treatments to ensure human health and environmental safety. This deviation is intentional and reflects the broader scope of the WRR, which extends beyond the traditional objectives of wastewater treatment. The last step, the quaternary treatment is a process which reduces by at least 80% a broad spectrum of micropollutants listed in Part C of Annex I, such as common pharmaceuticals (e.g. antibiotics, antipsychotics, anti-inflammatory) and a few industrial chemicals. Quaternary treatment is required when treated wastewater is reused for agricultural purposes, even when the discharges come from agglomerations of below 10 000 p.e..

The WRR generally sets out harmonised minimum quality standards, minimum monitoring requirements, risk management provisions for possible health and environmental risks, permitting requirements and ensures transparency, so that key information about any water reuse project will be available to the public. To recall the quality requirements and their link to permitted uses: after further treatment of wastewater, the resulting water can be classified into one of four categories based on specific parameter values. Each category determines the types of crops that may be irrigated and the irrigation methods that may be applied (Figure 2).

	Class A	Class B	Class C	Class D
	Secondary treatment, filtration & disinfection	Secondary treatment & disinfection	Secondary treatment & disinfection	Secondary treatment & disinfection
E.Coli	≤ 10	≤ 100	≤ 1 000	≤ 10 000
BOD ₅	≤ 10	In accordance with Directive 91/271/EC (Annex 1, Table I)		
TSS	≤ 10	In accordance with Directive 91/271/EC(Annex 1, Table I)		
Turbidity	≤ 5	-	-	-
Legionella spp.: ≤ 1 000 cfu/l where there is a risk of aerosolization/ Intestinal nematodes (helminth eggs): ≤ 1 egg/l for irrigation of pasture or forage				

Food & Feed crops	Class A – in direct contact with reclaimer water (food crops) → All irrigation methods	1. Crop type 2. Contact with crop 3. Irrigation method
	Class B – non direct contact with reclaimer water (crops for milk & meat-producing animals' feed) → All irrigation methods	
	Class C – non direct contact with reclaimer water (crops for milk & meat-producing animals' feed) → Drip irrigation	

Figure 2: A brief presentation of the requirements set out in the WRR and the assignment to quality classes.

Article 5 of WRR stipulates the mandatory inclusion of a risk management plan for the operation of a reclaimed water supply network. The responsibility for conducting the risk analysis and formulating the water reuse risk management plan (RMP) is entrusted to the operator of the reclamation facility. This process is to be conducted in collaboration with other relevant stakeholders, including responsible parties and, where appropriate, end-users. In essence, a RMP shall:

- (a) set out any necessary requirements for the reclamation facility operator, in addition to those specified in Annex I, to further mitigate any risks before the point of compliance;
- (b) identify hazards, risks and appropriate preventive and/or possible corrective measures;
- (c) identify additional barriers in the water reuse system and set out any additional requirements after the point of compliance to ensure that the water reuse system is safe, including conditions related to distribution, storage and use where relevant, and
- (d) identify the parties responsible for meeting those requirements.

The RMP must be compiled according to 11 Key Elements of Risk Management (KRM) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Key elements of Risk Management (KRMs) as outlined in the WRR.

It is important to note that where the destination of a specific type of crop is unknown or where it has multiple destinations, reclaimed water of the highest quality class should be used, unless appropriate barriers are applied which enable the required quality of the reclaimed water to be achieved. These barriers are necessary after the point of compliance to ensure that the water reuse system is safe, including conditions related to distribution, storage and use where relevant, and identify the parties responsible for meeting those requirements.

4.1.1 Implementing the WRR in the Member States

The WRR allows Member States to decide not to practice water reuse in their territory or to limit water reuse in certain areas, for reasons linked to geographical and climatic conditions, to pressures and status of their water resources or due to the environmental and resource costs of reclaimed water and of other water resources. Southern Member States such as Spain and Greece already operate reuse systems, serving as testbeds for broader EU harmonisation. However, some Member States, where freshwater resources are abundant and irrigation demand is low, have planned not to allow water reuse for irrigation in their countries. Some Member States have not yet made a final decision, as resource and infrastructure costs are still being evaluated. The current situation is illustrated in the following map.

Figure 4: Map showing the level of water reuse implementation in the EU member states (<https://water.europa.eu/freshwater/europe-freshwater/water-reuse>)

According to this map water reuse is not allowed in the following Member States: Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Czechia, Slovakia and Austria although more countries could be added to this list later. For P2Green, understanding this uneven adoption landscape is critical: regional diversity determines where demonstration activities may have greatest policy leverage and replicability potential.

The Member States that allow water reuse on their territory have either already incorporated the new rules into their national legislation to regulate the corresponding administrative procedures or are still in the process of preparation. Also, some Member States, like Spain, are regulating water reuse for applications beyond agricultural irrigation under their national regime.

While implementing and complying with the WRR can be complex, there is a wide range of resources available for the Member States and their local authorities, as well as those operators seeking to draft a Risk Management Plan. These include the WRR itself and an implementing Regulation setting out the technical specifications for the key elements of risk management, ensuring that the parties accountable for water reuse projects can design comprehensive risk management plans and guarantee project safety.¹³³

¹³³ Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2024/1765 of 11 March 2024 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to technical specifications of the key elements of risk management [2024] OJ L, 2024/1765

Alongside these, there are several guidance documents, including by the EU's Joint Research Centre (JRC)¹³⁴ and the European Commission.¹³⁵ These instruments together create a coherent operational framework covering the entire chain from treatment to use.

The European Environment Agency (EEA)¹³⁶ and the JRC are jointly involved in the development of the Water Information System for Europe (WISE),¹³⁷ which is a partnership between the European Commission (DG Environment, JRC and Eurostat) and the EEA. As part of the implementation of the Water Reuse Regulation (EU) 2020/741, the EEA is developing a harmonised data model and reporting guidance to standardise how Member States report reclaimed-water production, reuse activities, permits and compliance. According to an EEA presentation in 2023 on the WRR data-reporting model,¹³⁸ this framework will include reporting on points of compliance, non-compliance cases and public information requirements.

In June 2025, the European Commission introduced the Water Resilience Strategy¹³⁹, presenting a comprehensive, cross-sectoral framework aimed at enhancing sustainable water management and promoting water reuse. Within this context, the JRC is expanding stakeholder capacity through initiatives such as the European Water Academy, which supports training on water reuse, risk management and innovation providing support to researchers and innovators in exploring pathways for the commercialisation of emerging technologies.

According to art. 12 (3) of the WRR, the Commission shall assess the feasibility of expanding the scope for reclaimed water intended for other uses, such as industrial. Broader policy discussions also indicate the EU's intention to potentially expand reuse beyond agriculture to industrial and urban applications as part of the emerging Water Resilience Strategy.¹⁴⁰

For P2GreeN, contributing data and methodologies to relevant bodies (JRC, WISE) could position the project as a model for monitoring best practices.

¹³⁴ [Technical guidance water reuse risk management for agricultural irrigation schemes in Europe](#); The guidance translates legal principles into practical methodologies for RMP development, including quantitative microbial risk assessment and stakeholder engagement.

¹³⁵ [Commission Notice Guidelines to support the application of Regulation 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse 2022/C 298/01](#) provide detailed guidelines to help EU Member States, authorities, and operators apply Regulation (EU) 2020/741, covering aspects such as risk management, permitting, monitoring, enforcement, and best practices to ensure safe and sustainable agricultural irrigation.

¹³⁶ Website: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en>

¹³⁷ Website: <https://water.europa.eu/>

¹³⁸The presentation can be found in the following link: <https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/9ab5926d-bed4-4322-9aa7-9964bbe8312d/library/6c031049-932b-400a-b27c-4977d966406a/details>

¹³⁹ COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS European Water Resilience Strategy [2025] COM/2025/280 final

¹⁴⁰ According to an [interview](#) of Dr. Roberta Maffetone (Scientific Project Officer at EU COM JRC) in the Smart Water Magazine.

It should be noted that the WRR is complemented by other legislation, for example, Regulation 852/2004 on hygiene in foodstuffs. While this is technically relevant to food production, it has implications for the use of reclaimed water. The Hygiene in Foodstuffs Regulation requires, for instance, that potable or clean water be used in the production of plant products ‘whenever necessary to prevent contamination’. Clean water is defined as water ‘that does not contain micro-organisms, harmful substances or toxic marine plankton in quantities capable of directly or indirectly affecting the health quality of food’. Therefore, any reclaimed water would need to meet these criteria to be used in plant production ‘whenever necessary to prevent contamination’. Technically this is addressed by the WRR through the implementation of water classes as “low quality” reclaimed water must not come in contact with edible parts of the plant. In a similar vein, Directive 2020/2184 on the Quality of Water Intended for Human Consumption (the Drinking Water Directive) sets out the legal framework for safeguarding human health by ensuring the proper monitoring and treatment of water intended for human consumption. It defines specific microbiological and chemical quality parameters. Although these parameters are not required under the WRR, they may be monitored on a voluntary basis as a best practice measure; the Directive’s 52 parameters including microbiological (such as *Escherichia coli*), chemical (such as acrylamide, PFAS, pesticides) and indicator (such as pH, colour, ammonium) parameters.

Reference should also be made to Directive 2008/105 on environmental quality standards (Environmental Quality Standards Directive – EQSD), in the field of water policy which lays down environmental quality standards (EQS) for priority substances and certain other pollutants¹⁴¹, with the aim of achieving good surface water chemical status and in accordance with the provisions and objectives of Article 4 of Directive 2000/60, the EU Water Framework Directive¹⁴². Key pollutants covered under the directive include heavy metals (e.g., cadmium, mercury, and lead), industrial chemicals (e.g. benzene, dichloromethane), pharmaceuticals (e.g. ibuprofen, erythromycin) and pesticides (e.g., atrazine and chlorpyrifos). Member States are responsible for applying the EQS to bodies of surface water according to specific requirements and have national laws or administrative procedures regarding this. This Directive contains 45 substances at the moment.

More recently, Commission Decision 2025/439 establishes a watch list of substances for EU-wide monitoring in the field of water policy pursuant to Directive 2008/105¹⁴³. The 2025/439 Decision is adopted pursuant to the EQSD, which is itself part of the

¹⁴¹ Directive 2008/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on environmental quality standards in the field of water policy, amending and subsequently repealing Council Directives 82/176/EEC, 83/513/EEC, 84/156/EEC, 84/491/EEC, 86/280/EEC and amending Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council [2008] OJ L 348

¹⁴² Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy [2000] OJ L 327

¹⁴³ Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2025/439 of 28 February 2025 establishing a watch list of substances for Union-wide monitoring in the field of water policy pursuant to Directive 2008/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (notified under document C(2025) 1244) [2025] C/2025/1244

implementation of the Water Framework Directive. The watch list, established under Article 8b of the EQSD, serves as a monitoring tool for emerging pollutants that may pose environmental or health risks but for which there is insufficient data to set binding EQS values. These substances are not yet regulated, but Member States monitor their presence and concentrations in water bodies. The European Commission reviews and updates the list every four years, and substances showing significant risk may later be proposed for inclusion as EQS parameters with binding environmental standards. The 2025 watch list continues to include several pharmaceuticals and antibiotics, in line with the EU Strategic Approach to Pharmaceuticals in the Environment¹⁴⁴ and the European One Health Action Plan against Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR)¹⁴⁵. Their inclusion aims to enhance knowledge about the presence and spread of these substances in aquatic environments, supporting evidence-based management and possible future regulation of these pollutants. The watch list covers a diverse range of pharmaceuticals, pesticides, industrial chemicals, and personal care products that are suspected to pose risks to the aquatic environment or human health but for which data are not yet sufficient to set binding EQS. It includes pharmaceuticals and their metabolites, such as antibiotics (e.g., tetracycline, oxytetracycline, clindamycin, ofloxacin), antidepressants (e.g., fluoxetine, venlafaxine), beta-blockers (e.g., propranolol), and antidiabetic compounds (metformin and its metabolite guanil urea), reflecting growing concern about pharmaceutical pollution and AMR. It also encompasses pesticides and biocides, including insecticides (fipronil, abamectin, etoxazole) andazole fungicides used in agriculture and personal care (bromuconazole, climbazole, itraconazole, ketoconazole), which are monitored for their persistence and ecotoxicity. Industrial transformation products, such as 6PPD and 6PPD-quinone derived from tire wear, represent contaminants from urban runoff and industrial activity. Finally, the list includes personal care and UV filter substances like avobenzene, octocrylene, benzophenone-3, and octisalate, known for their potential endocrine-disrupting effects and bioaccumulation in aquatic organisms.

It is also worth reflecting on FAO Irrigation and Drainage Paper No. 29 – “Water Quality for Agriculture” which is a technical manual published by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations in 1985¹⁴⁶. It provides comprehensive guidelines for assessing and managing the quality of water used in agriculture, with a primary focus on irrigation and livestock watering. The paper explains how various chemical, physical, and biological characteristics of water—such as salinity, sodicity, specific ion toxicity (e.g., chloride, boron), pH, and trace elements—can influence soil properties, crop productivity, and animal health. It establishes recommended

¹⁴⁴ COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL AND THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE European Union Strategic Approach to Pharmaceuticals in the Environment [2019] COM/2019/128 final

¹⁴⁵ COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE COUNCIL AND THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT A European One Health Action Plan against Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) [2017] COM/2017/0339 final

¹⁴⁶ Ayers, R. S., & Westcot, D. W. (1985). Water quality for agriculture (Vol. 29, p. 174). Rome: Food and agriculture organization of the United Nations.

concentrations for potentially harmful elements such as cadmium (≤ 0.01 mg/L) and arsenic (≤ 0.10 mg/L) to prevent inhibition of plant growth and long-term contamination of agricultural soils. It also includes micronutrients like iron (≤ 5 mg/L) and zinc (≤ 2 mg/L), which are essential for plant development but may become toxic at elevated levels. These values are not legal limits but technical guidelines intended to ensure the suitability of water for long-term irrigation use, typically over periods exceeding two decades. The paper emphasizes that actual tolerance levels depend on factors such as crop sensitivity, soil characteristics, irrigation method, and water pH, and therefore recommends periodic monitoring and management practices—like blending, leaching, and crop rotation—to maintain sustainable agricultural productivity and protect environmental quality.

In conclusion, the most common substances found in most sources listed above include Diclofenac, Clarithromycin, Carbamazepine, Citalopram, Venlafaxine, Metoprolol, Hydrochlorothiazide, Benzotriazole, Irbesartan, Candesartan, and PFAS. Most of these substances are human pharmaceuticals such as antibiotics, analgesics, antidepressant/neuroactive and cardiovascular drugs, highlighting the importance of monitoring them from wastewater sources.

4.1.2 Is reclaimed water still a form of waste/wastewater?

Under Article 3(4) of the WRR, 'reclaimed water' is defined as urban wastewater that has been treated in compliance with the requirements set out in the UWWTD and has undergone further treatment in a reclamation facility in accordance with Section 2 of Annex I of that Regulation. As noted, reclaimed water is subject to a rigorous regulatory framework to ensure it is safe for the use in irrigation, with the potential for further requirements under domestic implementation measures.

Nonetheless, while it clearly is no longer subject to the UWWTD if used for irrigation purposes (and not discarded)¹⁴⁷ in accordance with the WRR, it remains unclear what the precise nature of this product is, i.e. whether this upgraded water continues to fall within the broader category of “wastewater” or even “waste” under the WFD or whether it has ceased to be waste and should instead be regarded as a distinct, non-waste resource. This distinction is significant for regulatory purposes for various operations, including transport, cross-border movement, and broader marketability.

Reclaimed water could still be considered a form of “purified” wastewater (further treated “treated wastewater”). According to Article 2(2)(a) of the WFD, wastewaters are excluded from the scope of the Directive to the extent that they are covered by other EU legislation. Since “reclaimed water” is a form of treated urban wastewater and is covered by another

¹⁴⁷ If not used for irrigation, then the purified/further treated wastewater would likely fall back under the UWWTD again, especially if the tertiary treatment to preserve nutrients was omitted.

specific EU legislation (i.e. the WRR), it seems that it is (largely) excluded from the scope of the WFD.

In case this does not apply and reclaimed water is considered waste under the WFD, then the end-of-waste criteria need to be examined, for it to cease being waste. As discussed in Section 3.6.2 above, this is largely regulated by Article 6 of the WFD on end-of-waste status, although with the potential for applicable sectoral laws to address this too. As noted in Section 3.6.1, this latter approach is achieved expressly by the FPR with respect to waste ingredients in fertilising products. In contrast, the WRR does not expressly state that reclaimed water is no longer waste. Nonetheless, there is a strong argument that the WRR implicitly addresses this issue in a manner consistent with the conditions of Article 6(1) WFD. Besides the chosen terminology of ‘reclaimed water’ that excludes ‘waste’ despite its origins in treated wastewater, the WRR clearly provides for a recovery operation that leads to (a) the substance being ‘used for specific purposes’ of irrigation, whereby it will (c) fulfil relevant ‘technical requirements’ and ‘existing legislation and standards’ within the WRR and a vast array of linked laws and thereby (d) ‘not lead to overall adverse environmental or human health impacts’. Regarding the question of (b) ‘a market or demand’, there is a clear need for water for irrigation, whether reclaimed or not. If there were no need, farmers would not further irrigate and thereby damage their crops. That demand for reclaimed water specific is likely to increase in future, due in part to the practical need for increased agricultural production and in the context of severe climate events and in part to shifts in policy and law regarding the need to reuse water more generally. This approach recognises reclaimed water as a resource contributing to circular economy objectives and aligns with, and supports, the overarching goals of the WFD, the UWWTD, and the WRR itself.

Therefore, it would appear that where a Member State implements the WRR and facilitates the use of reclaimed water in irrigation then the WRR, perhaps in conjunction with any additional domestic measures or standards, acts as *de facto* end-of-waste criteria – if not expressly provided for in the national law. How this would operate procedurally might vary from Member State to Member State, but the CJEU in *Sappi* has effectively indicated that a Member State could not refuse end-of-waste status if the Article 6(1) conditions are fulfilled. There remains a further question as to whether the WRR could act as implicit EU-level criteria, akin to the express approach in the FPR, which would have more profound impacts on transboundary elements and marketability.

Clarity on the EU’s interpretation of the legal status of reclaimed water is essential, including to assess whether any implications arise during transport or other stages of handling, as well as ameliorating public perception.

4.1.3 Reclaimed Water and Use in Organic farming

Regulation (EU) 2018/848 on Organic Production does not explicitly address irrigation methods in organic farming, including the use of reclaimed water¹⁴⁸. However, sustainable agricultural practices, such as using treated wastewater for crop irrigation, may be compatible with organic production, provided that the reclaimed water complies with all applicable EU and national legislation, including the regulations on organic farming and water reuse.

It would be useful to obtain clarity on whether reclaimed water may be used in organic farming, as such guidance would support the wider uptake of reclaimed water and improve public acceptance of its use.

4.2 Water Reuse in Spain

4.2.1 Water governance

Spain's water governance is shared between the central government, through the Ministry of Ecological Transition and its river basin authorities, and the 17 regional governments, creating a complex semi-federal system that requires constant coordination and often leads to territorial conflicts. The Central Government (MET) oversees national water management and acts through nine River Basin Authorities (Confederaciones Hidrográficas). Their responsibilities include assigning water to users, monitoring quality and use of water, and generally ensuring compliance with the EU Water Framework Directive. The Regional Governments (17 Autonomous Communities) are responsible for urban planning, agriculture, and natural heritage. Also, in six regions they manage river basins that are entirely within their territory.

Spain's water rights system has long been divided: surface water is public and managed through concessions, while groundwater was historically private and beyond state control. The Water Act No.29/1985¹⁴⁹ attempted to eradicate this private regime by bringing all waters under the public domain, but in practice it allowed many pre-existing private rights to persist. As a result, the historic division between public surface water and privately held groundwater continues today, creating a dual legal system and making regulation far more complex. In Spain, water allocation operates through a concession regime managed by the River Basin Authorities (RBAs) and coordinated with stakeholders. Importantly,

¹⁴⁸ Regulation (EU) 2018/848 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 on organic production and labelling of organic products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007 [2018] OJ L 150

¹⁴⁹ [Ley 29/1985, de 2 de agosto, de Aguas](#), «BOE» núm. 189, de 8 de agosto de 1985, páginas 25123 a 25135 (BOE-A-1985-16661)

this framework applies to both surface and groundwater, meaning that even though groundwater historically had a private character, concessions are now the primary legal mechanism for regulating access and use.

The Water Law (Royal Legislative Decree No.1 of 2001, consolidating the amendments to the 1985 Water Act)¹⁵⁰ also establishes a special legal framework for wastewater and its direct reuse. It determines that any urban or industrial discharge of wastewater into natural watercourses or irrigation channels requires authorisation from the RBA.

4.2.2 Royal Decree 1620/2007

Grounded in the Water Law, the Royal Decree 1620/2007¹⁵¹, of December 7, marked a milestone in promoting the reuse of wastewater in Spain. This decree set the basic regulations in the field, establishing the administrative requirements for obtaining the enabling title, as well as the permitted uses and the required quality criteria. It has since been repealed by the Royal Decree 1085/2024.

4.2.3 Royal Decree 1085/2024

Subsequently, Royal Decree-Law 4/2023¹⁵² adopted urgent measures in agricultural and water matters in response to drought and the worsening conditions of the primary sector due to the war in Ukraine and climatological conditions, as well as promoting the use of public transport by young people and preventing occupational risks during episodes of high temperatures. Of particular relevance here, it modified the Water Law by introducing, among other aspects, the new legal framework for water reuse, which allows the Spanish legal regime for water reuse to be adapted to European regulations.

¹⁵⁰ [Consolidated Real Decreto Legislativo 1/2001, de 20 de julio, por el que se aprueba el texto refundido de la Ley de Aguas](#), «BOE» núm. 176, de 24/07/2001 (BOE-A-2001-14276)

¹⁵¹ [Real Decreto 1620/2007, de 7 de diciembre, por el que se establece el régimen jurídico de la reutilización de las aguas depuradas](#), «BOE» núm. 294, de 8 de diciembre de 2007, páginas 50639 a 50661 (BOE-A-2007-21092)

¹⁵² [Real Decreto-ley 4/2023, de 11 de mayo, por el que se adoptan medidas urgentes en materia agraria y de aguas en respuesta a la sequía y al agravamiento de las condiciones del sector primario derivado del conflicto bélico en Ucrania y de las condiciones climatológicas, así como de promoción del uso del transporte público colectivo terrestre por parte de los jóvenes y prevención de riesgos laborales en episodios de elevadas temperaturas](#), «BOE» núm. 113, de 12 de mayo de 2023, páginas 65810 a 65874 (BOE-A-2023-11187)

Then, in October 2024, Spain adopted Royal Decree 1085/2024¹⁵³, which implements the WRR and modifies various royal decrees (RDs) regulating water management. The purpose of this Royal Decree is to develop the legal framework for water reuse, as established in Chapter III of Title V of the consolidated text of the Water Law, approved by Royal Legislative Decree 1/2001 (TRLA). Its primary objective is to facilitate the substitution of conventional water sources with reclaimed water for existing uses, ensuring such substitution is carried out safely and effectively. This RD also complements the provisions of Regulation (EU) 2020/741 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 May 2020, aligning national standards with European directives on water reuse. Building upon and expanding the scope of Royal Decree 1620/2007 which laid the groundwork for the reuse of treated wastewater in urban, agricultural, and environmental contexts, the RD 1085/2024 introduces more comprehensive and updated measures. It sets strict quality standards and risk management protocols tailored to various reuse purposes, which must be met prior to the application of reclaimed water for activities such as irrigation, industrial processes, or environmental restoration. To promote the use of reclaimed water over natural sources, the RD establishes economic incentives such as subsidies and tariff exemptions, in line with Spain's commitment to advancing a circular economy. Finally, the RD amends previous legislative provisions concerning the management of the public hydraulic domain. These amendments clarify procedures related to concession processing, discharge regulation, and the registration of water use rights.

The RD is structured into eight chapters and three annexes covering topics from risk management to monitoring standards (Table 1). These rules aim to improve both public health protection and environmental conservation through responsible water reuse.

Table 2: Basic structure of the Royal Decree 1085/2024.

Chapter I	General Provisions
Chapter II	Production and supply of reclaimed water
Chapter III	Use of Reclaimed Water
Chapter IV	Quality Requirements and Conformity Assessment
Chapter V	Risk Management
Chapter VI	Promotion of Reuse
Chapter VII	Reports and Transparency
Chapter VIII	Sanctions
Annex I	Quality Requirements for the Use of Reclaimed Water
Annex II	Quality Control of Reclaimed Water

¹⁵³ [Real Decreto 1085/2024, de 22 de octubre, por el que se aprueba el Reglamento de reutilización del agua y se modifican diversos reales decretos que regulan la gestión del agua](#), «BOE» núm. 256, de 23 de octubre de 2024, páginas 135409 a 135460 (BOE-A-2024-21701)

Annex III	Key Elements of Risk Management
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Reclaimed water uses

Certain uses of reclaimed water remain prohibited, including direct human consumption, except in the event of a catastrophe, certain food-related applications, medical facilities, cultivation of filter-feeding molluscs in aquaculture and recreational use such as bathing. Permitted uses include:

- (a) Urban Use,
- (b) Agricultural Use,
- (c) Industrial Use,
- (d) Use in Food Industry and
- (e) Other Uses, such as aquaculture, cooling systems in farms, recreational irrigation of sports fields, specific uses in livestock farming and forestry.

All uses have strict conditions and certain water specifications are defined. This poses a difference with the EU Regulation, which only provides for water reuse in the context of agriculture for irrigation purposes.

Agricultural irrigation – Quality & Risk Management Plans

Reclaimed water must comply with the quality standards set in Annex I and with any additional requirements established in the Risk Management Plan. Other uses not listed as allowed uses in the RD are only allowed with health authority approval, equivalent standards, and clear justification. Also, in case reclaimed water is used for another use in addition to agricultural irrigation, then the strictest quality specifications apply to ensure the highest level of health and environmental protection, unless the RMP specifies additional treatments or barriers addressing safety concerns.

The RD includes the same parameters set out in the Water Reuse Regulation for most of the parts, the classes of reclaimed water, the reclaimed water quality measurements, frequencies for routine monitoring, and validation monitoring. The description of the contents of the Risk Management Plan is the same as the one included in the WRR. Some additional parameters are included in the RD regarding the quality requirements for reclaimed water, as follows:

- Flow and turbidity must be continuously measured for all quality classes, in contrast with WRR where continuous measurement is set only for Class A.
- Determination of *Taenia saginata* and *Taenia solium*, which are species of parasitic tapeworms (flatworms), when the water is used for pasture of meat-producing animals.

- The minimum of three specific genera of intestinal nematodes must be controlled (Ancylostoma, Trichuris, and Ascaris), unless ultrafiltration is used which deems this control unnecessary.
- Regarding Legionella spp. compliance with the provisions of Royal Decree 487/2022, of June 21, which establish the health requirements for the prevention and control of legionellosis, should also be ensured.
- The contaminants limited in the wastewater discharge authorization will be controlled to ensure that the production and supply of regenerated water do not cause harm to the receiving environment, in accordance with Royal Decree 817/2015, of September 11, which establishes the criteria for monitoring and evaluating the state of surface waters and environmental quality standards, as well as Royal Decree 1514/2009, of October 2, which regulates the protection of groundwater against contamination and deterioration.
- Flow and turbidity must be continuously measured for all quality classes, in contrast with the WRR where continuous measurement is set only for Class A.

Permits – Administrative issues

Chapter II establishes that production and supply facilities must obtain an authorization specifying the reclaimed water quality class, permitted volume, and intended use. This authorization requires strict monitoring, reporting, and quality control procedures. Under Chapter III, all reclaimed water users must secure a concession from the competent authority, in accordance with Annex III, which outlines the elements of the Risk Management Plan (RMP). The concession procedure ensures consistency with hydrological planning and compliance with environmental and, where relevant, food hygiene standards.

All entities involved in the reuse system are required to prepare a Reclaimed Water Risk Management Plan, defining their respective responsibilities. The plan, developed jointly and covering one or more reuse systems, must accompany the application, review, or renewal of the production and supply authorization. It is evaluated by the competent authority in collaboration with the health authority. Upon request, responsible parties must provide documentation, records, and summaries demonstrating the development and implementation of the RMP. The plan must follow the risk management elements set out in Annex III and, for agricultural uses, take into account the technical specifications established by the European Commission's delegated act and any future delegated acts under Article 5(5) of the WRR. In conclusion, each responsible party in the reuse system must ensure compliance with both the conditions of the authorization or concession and the applicable sections of the Reclaimed Water Risk Management Plan.

Useful resources

The Water Technologies Department of the CEDEX Hydrographic Studies Centre has developed a set of methodologies and standard documents aimed at facilitating and standardising the implementation of risk management in water reuse systems¹⁵⁴. These tools support the development of specific plans to assess health and environmental risks and to apply the multi-barrier approach effectively. The relevant sources include the following so far:

- Reclaimed Water Risk Management Plan (PGRAR) model

The PGRAR is conceived as a product document, meaning it represents the final deliverable to be submitted to the water authorities when applying for the corresponding permit for the production and supply of reclaimed water. It also serves as an ongoing reference document to support day-to-day management of the reuse system. Therefore, it is not a guide for conducting the studies and actions required to develop the plan, but rather a model of the final approved document.

- Proposed Risk Analysis and Management Sheets, in Excel format

A comprehensive set of risk analysis and management sheets, provided in Excel format with an accompanying explanatory document, serves as an organizational model for identifying, analysing, and managing risks in water reuse systems. The tool is designed to support stakeholders in conducting risk assessments, particularly at treatment plants. It includes a catalogue of potential hazardous events as reference examples, as well as an extensive list of preventive and corrective measures to guide effective risk management.

- Methodological Proposal for Health Risk Assessment

The methodological proposal for health risk assessment has been jointly developed and agreed upon by CEDEX and the Júcar Hydrographic Confederation. It is based on the principle that the risk associated with a hazardous event results from the combination of two factors: the probability of a safe condition being compromised and the severity of the resulting effects. Accordingly, the proposal introduces specific methodologies for assessing probability, severity, and the overall level of risk.

- Analysis Using a Multi-Barrier Approach

The document analyses the multi-barrier approach established in the Regulation and proposes alternative configurations for different crop types, irrigation methods, and water quality classes. It serves as a decision-support tool for both irrigators and water authorities, guiding the selection of appropriate measures and management actions.

- Environmental Risk Assessment Methodology

This is still work in progress and is not published yet.

¹⁵⁴ [Guías para la gestión del riesgo del agua regenerada en regadío](#), CEDEX

4.3 Water reuse in Greece

Greece is one of the Member States that allow the use of reclaimed water. Before the publication of the WRR, the Greek Joint Ministerial Decision 145/116/2011 (modified in 2013) was in force at national level.¹⁵⁵ Currently, the WRR has not been transposed in the national law and the existing Greek regime has not been adapted in light of the EU Regulation.¹⁵⁶

The ministerial decision sets out the measures, conditions, and procedures for the reuse of treated wastewater, including permitted uses, quality standards, obligations of operators and relevant national administrative processes. It addresses the planned reuse of treated wastewater, defined as the intentional, scheduled, and controlled application of treated effluent. Such reuse is authorised for agricultural irrigation, groundwater recharge, urban and peri-urban applications, industrial uses, and water systems supplying drinking water. Under this decision, the following definitions apply:

- wastewater reuse is defined as the overall management of wastewater in such a way that it can be recovered as water for the purpose of reuse
- wastewater is defined as domestic or municipal sewage, as well as industrial wastewater, as referred to in Joint Ministerial Decision No. 5673/400/1997 (Government Gazette B'192), regardless of the size of the industrial facility.

For the reuse of treated wastewater in irrigation, two categories are defined based on crop type: restricted and unrestricted irrigation. Restricted irrigation applies to crops not intended for human consumption, as well as those where the edible part does not come into contact with reclaimed water or soil, or is consumed only after processing (e.g., thermal treatment). This includes crops such as industrial crops and animal feed. Sprinkler irrigation is not allowed, and measures must be taken to restrict access by the public and animals. Unrestricted irrigation, on the other hand, applies to all crop types, including those consumed raw (e.g., vegetables, grapes) and ornamentals. It permits the use of any irrigation method, including sprinklers, and does not require access restrictions.

The Ministerial Decision outlines permissible limits for microbiological, conventional, and other chemical parameters, as well as the desirable agronomic characteristics. They also specify the minimum required treatment, the type and minimum frequency of sampling and analyses. In some cases, limits and monitoring depend on the size of the wastewater treatment plant. Treated wastewater used for irrigation must comply with specific

¹⁵⁵ [Υ.Α. οικ. 145116/2011 \(ΦΕΚ 354/Β' 8.3.2011\) Καθορισμός μέτρων, όρων και διαδικασιών για την επαναχρησιμοποίηση επεξεργασμένων υγρών αποβλήτων και άλλες διατάξεις](#)

¹⁵⁶ Relevant legislation on wastewater is available on the official [website](#) of the Ministry of Environment and Energy:.

standards. While the same key parameters, such as *E. coli*, BOD₅, suspended solids (SS), and turbidity, are monitored for both restricted and unrestricted irrigation, the required wastewater treatment levels and sampling frequencies differ between the two.

The type of irrigation (restricted or unrestricted) affects the values and monitoring frequency of the parameters *E. coli*, BOD₅, suspended solids (SS), and turbidity (parameters also included in the WRR) as well as the needed treatment of the wastewater (e.g. secondary, disinfection step). As an analogy, unrestricted irrigation corresponds to class A, and restricted irrigation corresponds to classes B to D, although some small differences exist (e.g. fruit trees). Therefore, a direct comparison of the limit values is not applicable. However, the requirement for *E. coli* in Class A appears stricter under the WRR (≤ 10 CFU/100 mL for 90% of samples) than under the Greek Ministerial Decision, which allows ≤ 5 CFU/100 mL for 80% of samples and ≤ 50 CFU/100 mL for 95% of samples. Also, since restricted irrigation under the Greek MD corresponds to Classes B to D, the associated microbiological limit values can be either stricter or more lenient than those of the WRR, depending on the specific class being considered.

At the time of the publishing of the Greek MD, the need for a tertiary or quaternary treatment was not in effect in the UWWTD. So, it makes sense that in addition to the aforementioned parameters, maximum allowable concentrations exist in the Greek MD for heavy metals and other potentially harmful elements, including aluminium (Al), arsenic (As), fluoride (F), mercury (Hg). Also, maximum allowable limits exist for various organic substances, including agrochemicals (e.g., chlorpyrifos), industrial chemicals (e.g., polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons), persistent organic pollutants (POPs), and other compounds such as phthalates, as well as for the acute toxicity to the organism *Daphnia magna*. These requirements apply in certain types of UWWTPs, such as the ones serving equivalent population of more than 100,000 inhabitants. However, the pollutants listed in the Greek MD concern environmental contaminants, whereas the UWWTD list includes pharmaceuticals and current-use micropollutants. Therefore, the two lists are distinct and do not overlap. Agronomic suitability is also assessed based on desirable characteristics, which are expressed as acceptable value ranges and associated levels of restriction. These include factors such as salinity (e.g., electrical conductivity), specific ions (e.g., sodium), nitric nitrogen, pH, and bicarbonate (HCO₃).

To irrigate using treated wastewater a study for the design and implementation of the irrigation system must be compiled assessing water and nutrient balance, land needs, water and soil quality monitoring, safety measures (e.g., fencing, irrigation methods), user protection (e.g., automatic systems), and safe distances from water sources. The use of treated wastewater requires a permit, which is issued to either the end user or the entity responsible for managing the reclaimed water. In cases where the user or the managing entity of the reclaimed water is subject to environmental permitting under current regulations, the reuse permit is replaced by the Environmental Terms Approval (ΑΕΠΟ) or the Standard Environmental Commitments (ΠΠ.Δ.). For the issuance of the permit for the reuse of treated wastewater, a relevant application must be submitted by the user or

the managing entity of the reclaimed water to the competent Water Directorate of the Decentralized Administration along with the study.

Although the national framework shares certain similarities with WRR, there are also significant differences, e.g. the water quality groups, the limits of the common parameters and a range of additional contaminants to be considered in the Greek MD. Therefore, national legislation must be amended to fully align with the Regulation's requirements. A new Joint Ministerial Decision is currently being drafted to bring the national framework into closer conformity with the EU Regulation. And in the meantime, users should be aware that the WRR is directly applicable and that the minimum requirements apply where they are stricter than the existing Greek standards.

4.4 Conclusion on Water Reuse

Water Reuse has a substantial, detailed EU framework that applies across the Member States in principle. However, variations arise due to domestic systems being outdated or having developed in parallel or even in advance of the EU law, due to opt-outs and due to the potential for additional criteria. This undermines the regime's effectiveness in delivering on its objectives and also presents hurdles for those seeking to create or use reclaimed water in agriculture.

For P2GreeN and other innovators, it is essential to be aware of the Member States' approach to the WRR, the extensive guidance available, and the opportunities to provide evidence/data to shape policy and guidance. It is likewise necessary to determine which treatments/crop types match and are most suitable for the individual operator and to be aware that the regulated substances are subject to change. A useful practice could be to gather evidence of safety even beyond currently regulated substances, both generally for marketability/reassuring users and also in case of legislative updates.

Potential reforms here will need to be reflected on carefully, but could include elements such as clarity regarding end-of-waste status and use in organic farming. They could also include requiring more detailed and substantiated justifications for opt-outs and the development of national strategies for water reuse.

5 Fertilising Products

A key ambition for P2Green actors and similar innovators is to be able to upscale their activities and a central route to this is the ability to market and thereby commercialise the final products, in particular across the EU. The regulatory landscape here is particularly complex, both generally and in particular for P2Green-style products. The Fertilising Products Regulation (FPR), Regulation (EU) 2019/1009,¹⁵⁷ is the key general piece of legislation in the area, but it has several carve-outs, omissions and also operates alongside numerous other pieces of legislation. For instance, Article 1 indicates that the FPR does not apply to animal by-products subject to Regulation 1069/2009¹⁵⁸ and does not affect the application of a number of other laws which include the Sewage Sludge Directive (Directive 86/278), the Nitrates Directive (Directive 91/676) and the Regulation on Organic Production (now Regulation 2018/848). The legislative framework gives rise to a host of questions that need to be addressed, in part because human excreta as envisaged within P2Green are not directly addressed in this context and therefore it is essential to consider both the core laws on fertilising products and also the broader framework and its approach to comparable materials

- (a) How are animal excreta defined and regulated under EU legislation? The answer to this question requires an examination of Regulation (EU) 1069/2009 - the Animal By-Products Regulation (ABPR).¹⁵⁹
- (b) What are the rules for the application of manure – a product comparable to human excreta? The answer to this question can be found in Directive 91/676, the Nitrates Directive.
- (c) Are manure and chemical fertilisers capable of being used in organic agriculture? The answer to this question requires an examination of Regulation 2018/848,¹⁶⁰ the Regulation on Organic Production and subsequent legislation on fertilisers in this area.
- (d) If these pieces of legislation suggest that it is not possible to use human excreta to support food production, is there any legislation that does so? An answer to this question may be found in Directive 86/278, the Sewage Sludge Directive.

¹⁵⁷ Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products and amending Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003 [2019] OJ L 170.

¹⁵⁸ However, as discussed below, some 'derived products' that have met their 'end points' under Regulation 1069/2009 are permitted as ingredients.

¹⁵⁹ Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 laying down health rules as regards animal by-products and derived products not intended for human consumption and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1774/2002 (Animal by-products Regulation) [2009] OJ L 300,

¹⁶⁰ Regulation (EU) 2018/848 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 on organic production and labelling of organic products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007 [2018] OJ L 150.

- (e) Is it possible to bring human excreta with the scope of FPR as a Fertiliser or a Soil Improver? An answer to this question may be found in the Regulation and if positive, two further questions arise:
- which of the existing Component Material Categories (CMCs) would be the most appropriate to use?
 - if there is no appropriate CMC, should a new CMC or multiple new CMCs be created to facilitate the use of human excreta as a fertiliser and/or a soil improver?
- (f) If it is not possible to use human excreta as an input into an EU fertiliser and/or soil improver, would it be possible to have such a product approved by a Member State under their domestic regimes?
- (g) If approved in one Member States, can it be marketed in other Member States? An answer to this question can be found in an examination of the principle of mutual recognition and its implementation domestically.

These questions are addressed in the following sections of this part of the Legislative Report.

For the purposes of the following analysis, it is important to note that the term “organic” has different meanings depending on the legislative context. Under the FPR, “organic fertiliser/soil improver” refers to materials of biological origin (not simply any material containing organic carbon). In the context of organic farming, the term “organic fertiliser/soil improver” is sometimes used informally to describe inputs permitted in organic production, although EU organic farming regulations do not use this terminology; such authorised inputs may be of inorganic or organic origin. Under the ABPR, the term “organic fertiliser/soil improver” refers specifically to materials of animal origin—namely animal by-products (in their raw or processed form) as well as materials derived from animal by-products, such as hydrolysed proteins.

5.1 Animal Excreta

ABPR indicates that manure “should not need to be disposed of, provided that proper treatment ensures diseases are not transmitted during their application to land”, with Article 3(20) defining manure as “any excrement and/or urine of farmed animals other than farmed fish, with or without litter.”¹⁶¹ The Regulation categorises these “by-products” as Category 2 material by Article 9, with Article 13 indicating how these products should be disposed of or used, for example, paragraph (a) offers incineration as an option and paragraph (f) offers the option that it be:

¹⁶¹ [2009] OJ L 300/1, Recital 34.

applied to land without processing, in the case of manure, digestive tract content separated from the digestive tract, milk, milk-based products and colostrum which the competent authority does not consider to present a risk for the spread of any serious transmissible disease.

Article 20 allows for authorisation of alternative methods of use or disposal, with applications being made by interested parties to the competent authority in the Member States in which the alternative method is to be used. An approval decision is to be informed by a report on its evaluation by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). So, EU farmers may apply manure, which is rich in nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, onto their fields to improve soil structure, enhance fertility, and increase crop yields without relying solely on chemical/synthetic fertilisers. This approach not only recycles valuable organic matter but also supports the principles of sustainable agriculture.

Article 3(22) ABPR provides that “‘organic fertiliser’ and ‘soil improver’ means materials of animal origin used to maintain or improve plant nutrition and the physical and chemical properties and biological activities of soils, either separately or together; they may include manure, non-mineralised guano, digestive tract content, compost and digestion residues.”¹⁶² Article 11(1)(c) goes on to provide that:¹⁶³

... the feeding of farmed animals with herbage, either directly by grazing or by feeding with cut herbage, from land to which organic fertilisers or soil improvers, other than manure, have been applied is prohibited unless the cutting or grazing takes place after the expiry of a waiting period which ensures adequate control of risks to public and animal health and is at least 21 days.

Commission Implementation Regulation 142/2011 in its Annexes outlines options for the disposal of manure including, for example, combustion and composting.¹⁶⁴ Annex XI outlines requirements relating to Organic Fertilisers and Soil Improvers with Section 1 dealing with trade in unprocessed manure. For example, given concerns about human and animal health, trade is not permitted from an area subject to restrictions by virtue of

¹⁶² Ibid.

¹⁶³ Ibid.

¹⁶⁴ Commission Regulation (EU) No 142/2011 of 25 February 2011 implementing Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down health rules as regards animal by-products and derived products not intended for human consumption and implementing Council Directive 97/78/EC as regards certain samples and items exempt from veterinary checks at the border under that Directive Text with EEA relevance [2011] OJ L 54/1. This Regulation has been frequently amended, most recently by Commission Regulation 2020/1720, [2020] OJ L 386/6. Composting is dealt with in Annex V which also addresses biogas production.

a serious transmissible disease.¹⁶⁵ Section 2 of this Annex deals with processed manure and products derived therefrom, providing, for example, specific heat treatment of specific duration so as to reduce toxin formation and the authorisation by the competent authority of “other standardised process parameters” to minimise biological risks based on a risk assessment, which ensures, for example a reduction of *Enterococcus faecalis* and reduction of resistant parasites.¹⁶⁶

However, one issue to be addressed here is the presence of residues from veterinary medicines in animal manure. To promote animal health, livestock may be treated with pharmaceuticals such as antibiotics and anti-parasitics, but these may not be fully metabolised, so trace amounts may persist in animal manure. If this is applied to land, the residues may enter the soil, surface waters, and even crops; this would impact on soil quality, promote antimicrobial resistance, and pose risks to both environmental and human health. Whilst Regulation 470/2009 establishes procedures for limits pharmacologically active substance in foodstuffs of animal origin, it does not address the impact of these substances on the soil.¹⁶⁷ Moreover, the ABPR offers no guidance to the competent authorities on threats to human health and the environment arising from the spreading of manure. These issues could be addressed by an integrated nutrient management strategy but, despite being promised, it has not yet been adopted.

5.2 The Nitrates Directive

The Nitrates Directive (Directive 91/676)¹⁶⁸ establishes guidelines on manure application and other fertilisers containing nitrogen compounds,¹⁶⁹ aiming to prevent water pollution caused by excessive runoff. It also addresses the application of a chemical fertiliser which is defined in Article 2(f) of the Directive as “any fertiliser which is manufactured by an industrial process.”¹⁷⁰ As an industrial process will be used to recycle the human excreta

¹⁶⁵ Ibid, the Annex’s provision on unprocessed poultry manure and specifically mention Newcastle disease and avian influenza.

¹⁶⁶ Ibid, samples are to be taken to ensure standards on *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcaceae* and *Salmonella* are met.

¹⁶⁷ Regulation (EC) No 470/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 May 2009 laying down Community procedures for the establishment of residue limits of pharmacologically active substances in foodstuffs of animal origin, repealing Council Regulation (EEC) No 2377/90 and amending Directive 2001/82/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and Regulation (EC) No 726/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council [2009] OJ L 152/11.

¹⁶⁸ Council Directive 91/676/EEC of 12 December 1991 concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources [1991] OJ L 375

¹⁶⁹ Article 2(e) provides that a “fertilizer”: means any substance containing a nitrogen compound or nitrogen compounds utilized on land to enhance growth of vegetation; it may include livestock manure, the residues from fish farms and sewage sludge’.

¹⁷⁰ Council Directive 91/676/EEC of 12 December 1991 concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources [1991] OJ L 375/1. The Directive has been amended by Regulation 1882/2003 ([2003] OJ L 284/1) and Regulation 1137/2008 ([2008] L 311/1). It has been

to become fertiliser, it could be covered by the Directive as a chemical fertiliser. Annex IV of the Directive noted a method to measure nitrogen compounds and concentrations but this matter is now covered by the FPR – the relevant Directive, Directive 77/535, was repealed by Regulation 2003/2003 which in turn has been repealed by the FPR.¹⁷¹

The Nitrates Directive requires the Member States to define Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZs) i.e. those zones in which, as a result of agricultural activities, the waters are eutrophic or could contain a concentration of more than 50 mg/l of nitrates; Member States can also designate their entire territory as an NVZ.¹⁷² The Member States are required to establish voluntary codes of Good Agricultural Practice to be implemented by farmers and a compulsory action programme to be implemented by farmers within the NVZs that limit the application of nitrogen from manure and other fertilisers. The details for the Codes are laid down in Annex II which include for example, “periods when the land application of fertilizer is inappropriate” and “the conditions for land application of fertilizer near water courses.”¹⁷³ In NVZs, Annex III indicates that the measures shall include rules relating to “periods when the land application of certain types of fertilizer is prohibited” and indicates that the amount of manure to be applied to the land each year is not to exceed 170kg N per hectare per annum. Member States may request a derogation from this rule offering scientific justification but, if granted by the Commission, it does not exempt Member States from the water quality objectives of the Directive. Since 2007, Ireland, for instance, has received an exemption authorising the application of more than 170 kg N; the latest decision set the limit at 220kg N per hectare per annum.¹⁷⁴

Every four years, EU Member States are required to report on matters such as nitrate concentrations in groundwaters and surface waters; the eutrophication of surface waters; and revision of NVZs and action programmes on water quality and agricultural practices. These reports form the basis for a Commission report on the implementation of the Directive. The latest report concluding “the first necessary actions to address and prevent nutrient pollution from agriculture needs to be undertaken through a higher level of

noted that all fertilisers are covered by the Directive, see Case C-322/00 *Commission v Netherlands*, ECLI:EU:C:2003:532, paras 94 and 134 state that the Directive requires all nitrogen inputs and outputs to be taken into account. See also case C-526/08 *Commission v Luxembourg*, ECLI:EU:C:2010:379, para 68.

¹⁷¹ Directive 77/535, [1977] OJ L 213/1. Regulation 2003/2003, [2003] OJ L 304/1. Regulation 2019/1009, [2019] OJ L 170/1.

¹⁷² Ibid, Annex I(A) lays down the criteria for identifying the relevant waters. On designation of NVZs see for example, case C-576/22 *Commission v Spain* ECLI:EU:C:2024:227. See also C-149/14 *Commission v Greece*, EU:C:2015:264.

¹⁷³ Ibid, Annex II (A) paras 1 and 4.

¹⁷⁴ Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/696 of 29 April 2022 granting a derogation requested by Ireland pursuant to Council Directive 91/676/EEC concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources (notified under document C(2022) 2596), [2022] OJ L 129/37. The decision expires at the end of 2025, although the Irish Government has launched a campaign for its extension, and has informed the Nitrates Committee accordingly, see [Comitology Register](#). There is an interesting contrast with the derogation granted to the Netherlands which created a sliding scale reducing the application from 230kg to 170kg from 2022 to 2025 – see Commission Decision 2022/2069, [2022] OJ L 277/195.

compliance with the Nitrates Directive.”¹⁷⁵ The Report acknowledges the key importance of the Directive to the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources and its contribution to the Green Deal and the Biodiversity and the Farm-to-Fork strategies of reducing nutrient losses whilst preserving soil fertility.¹⁷⁶

In December 2023, the Commission launched a public consultation on ‘Protecting waters from pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources’ which closed in March 2024; the overall evaluation of the Nitrates Directive is due by the end of 2025. The Report on the consultations noted the need for the Directive to keep up with scientific and technological advances in agriculture, with particular reference being made to fertilisers emerging from the RENURE process (REcovered Nitrogen from manURE).¹⁷⁷ Use of these products would reduce nitrate losses in water when compared with animal manure and the JRC Report on the subject concluded “The implementation of RENURE as part of manure management systems enables a progression towards a more circular economy and an avenue for increased resource efficiency in the EU food production system.”¹⁷⁸ A period of further consultations began in April 2024 on a Commission proposal which would have allowed Member States to authorise the use of RENURE by 100 kg above the maximum level of 170kg set in the Nitrates Directive subject to certain conditions relating to contaminants and pathogens.¹⁷⁹ Some of the responses received by the Commission were critical of the proposal suggesting that it was not consistent with the objectives set out in the Water Framework Directive and environmental law more generally.¹⁸⁰ However, a subsequent academic study suggests that application of RENURE could contribute to realising the environmental objectives of the Farm-to-Fork strategy i.e. a 20% reduction in fertiliser use.¹⁸¹ The proposal was then subject to discussion in the Nitrates Committee.¹⁸² No consensus was found at the June 2024 meeting with a number of concerns being raised, notably the need for further environmental assessment to ensure that its adoption would not lead to additional water pollution and, echoing responses from the consultation exercise, doubts on whether the

¹⁷⁵ COM (2021) 1000, Report from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament on the implementation of Council Directive 91/676/EEC concerning the protection of waters against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources based on Member State reports for the period 2016–2019, p. 11.

¹⁷⁶ Ibid, p 1.

¹⁷⁷ Available at [Protecting waters from pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources - Evaluation](#).

¹⁷⁸ See JRC Report, Huygens, D et al, Technical proposals for the safe use of processed manure above the threshold established for Nitrate Vulnerable Zones by the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) (2020), p 4. See also Vingerhoets, R et al, “Economic potential for nutrient recovery from manure in the European union” (2025) 215 *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.108079>.

¹⁷⁹ See [Nitrates – updated rules on the use of certain fertilising materials from livestock manure \(RENURE\)](#).

¹⁸⁰ See responses available at [Nitrates – updated rules on the use of certain fertilising materials from livestock manure \(RENURE\)](#).

¹⁸¹ See also Vingerhoets, R et al, “Economic potential for nutrient recovery from manure in the European union” (2025) 215 *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2024.108079>, section 4.

¹⁸² See for example, Report of 96th meeting (May 2024) available at [Comitology Register](#)

proposal exceeded the powers conferred on the Commission under the Nitrates Directive.¹⁸³

The lack of progress in adopting the proposal was noted by the Commission when, in December 2024, it published a proposal for the simplification of Good Agricultural and Environmental Condition (GAEC) standards amending Regulations 2021/2115 and 2021/2116 as part of a range of further measures to address the protests by farmers throughout 2024.¹⁸⁴ In the context of water pollution caused by Nitrates, the proposal did not address GAEC 4 - the creation of buffer strips alongside watercourses in which fertilisers and plant protection products cannot be applied – despite proposals by some Member States, as the Commission maintained that such changes would hamper the realisation of the CAP's objectives.¹⁸⁵ In some ways, this was not surprising as although GAEC 4 provides that the buffer strips must be a minimum of three metres wide unless the Nitrate Action Plan created by the Member States sets a wider width; a survey of the NSPs revealed that thirteen Member States have set a width greater than three metres with variation between Member States on the definition of watercourses.¹⁸⁶ The development of technologies and products such as RENURE or P2Green fertilisers suggests that GAEC 4 could be reviewed (and amended) provided there is evidence that a smaller buffer zone would suffice but as noted above a larger buffer zone operates in a large number of Member States.

5.3 Organic Agriculture

The Report on Strategic Dialogue on the Future of Agriculture in the European Union, requested by the Commission President and published in September 2024, contains a common theme of embedding sustainability within agricultural practices.¹⁸⁷ In this context, it suggested that the Commission should publish the long-promised Integrated Nutrient Management Plan and continued:¹⁸⁸

¹⁸³ See Report of the 97th Meeting of the Nitrates Committee (June 2024), available at [Comitology Register](#).

¹⁸⁴ Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL amending Regulations (EU) 2021/2115 and (EU) 2021/2116 as regards good agricultural and environmental condition standards, schemes for climate, environment and animal welfare, amendments to CAP Strategic Plans, review of CAP Strategic Plans and exemptions from controls and penalties, COM (2024) 139 final/2, p 12.

¹⁸⁵ Ibid, i.e. farms certified as entirely organic will be automatically considered to comply with a number of the GAECs, including GAEC 4.

¹⁸⁶ See Ecorys, Metis and Agrosynergy, *Mapping and analysis of CAP strategic plans: Assessment of joint efforts for 2023-2027* (2023, European Commission), Tables 53 and 55. See also Table 54 on rules regarding tillage and permanent vegetation (p 357).

¹⁸⁷ Strategic Dialogue on the future of Agriculture in the European Union (European Commission, 2024).

¹⁸⁸ Ibid, p 62.

Such a plan should provide a fully fledged strategy that looks at fertilization from a holistic point of view, with the aim of promoting complementarity between mineral and organic sources. It should focus on practices that;

- ensure improved nutrient use efficiency and circularity;
- bring humanly consumed nutrients back to agricultural cycle in a safe and appropriate way;

“Green” fertilisers facilitate the transition to increased sustainable production.¹⁸⁹

Organic farming is highlighted as a prime example of a more sustainable farming practice and system.¹⁹⁰ While other related options are possible, e.g. agroecology, organic farming is the ‘the only sustainable production system regulated by EU legislation’.¹⁹¹ A clear benefit could be derived if organic farming permitted a wide range of environmentally friendly measures, including the use of green fertilisers, provided that the overarching objectives and principles of organic farming were upheld. The Strategic Dialogue document therefore indicates support for P2Green-style products to be used in organic farming in principle and highlights the need to examine whether the existing legislation enables such practices or not. The rules on organic production and labelling of organic products are laid out in Regulation 2018/848 which indicated that conditions should be laid down for the use of fertilisers in such production¹⁹²

Before answering the question about the use of human excreta as a fertiliser/soil improver in organic production it is important to provide context by examining the objectives and principles of such production. Article 4 of the Regulation sets out the ten objectives of organic production, and these include:

- (a) contributing to protection of the environment and the climate;
- (b) maintaining the long-term fertility of soils;
- (c) contributing to a high level of biodiversity;
- (d) substantially contributing to a non-toxic environment;

Among the General Principles set out in Article 5 of the Regulation for this sustainable management system, Articles 5(f) and (g) may be seen as particularly relevant:

¹⁸⁹ Ibid, pp 66 and 103.

¹⁹⁰ Ibid, pp 57, 63 and 103. See also the Farm-to-Fork Strategy which suggests that by 2030 that at least 25% of the EU’s agricultural land should be under organic farming, COM (2020) 381 and COM (2021) 141/final/2 Action Plan for the Development of Organic Production, p 3. A recent European Court of Auditors report suggests that this target is unlikely to be met, see *Organic farming in the EU Gaps and inconsistencies hamper the success of the policy* Special Report 19/2024.

¹⁹¹ Strategic Dialogue on the future of Agriculture in the European Union, p.63.

¹⁹² Regulation (EU) 2018/848 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 on organic production and labelling of organic products and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 834/2007 [2018] OJ L 150/1. The Regulation has been subject to frequent amendment, most recently by Commission Delegated Regulation 2024/2867, [2024] OJ L 2867/1.

- (f) the appropriate design and management of biological processes, based on ecological systems and using natural resources which are internal to the management system, using methods that:
 - (i) use living organisms and mechanical production methods;
 - (ii) practice soil-related crop cultivation and land-related livestock production, or practice aquaculture which complies with the principle of the sustainable exploitation of aquatic resources;
 - (iii) exclude the use of GMOs, products produced from GMOs, and products produced by GMOs, other than veterinary medicinal products;
 - (iv) are based on risk assessment and the use of precautionary measures and preventive measures, where appropriate;
- (g) the restriction of the use of external inputs; where external inputs are required or the appropriate management practices and methods referred to in point (f) do not exist, the external inputs shall be limited to:
 - (i) inputs from organic production; in the case of plant reproductive material, priority shall be given to varieties selected for their ability to meet the specific needs and objectives of organic agriculture;
 - (ii) natural or naturally-derived substances;
 - (iii) low solubility mineral fertilisers;

So, Article 5(g)(iii) restricts the use of external inputs to low solubility mineral fertilisers. This is echoed in Article 6 which sets out the specific principles applicable to agricultural activities as including “(b) the limitation of the use of non-renewable resources and external inputs to a minimum.” In this context it should be noted that paragraph (c) provides for “the recycling of waste and by-products of plant and animal origin as input in plant and livestock production.” Finally, Article 24 FPR allows the Commission to authorise the use of certain products and substances as fertilisers which may be used, for example, when necessary if the nutritional needs of plants cannot be met by organic plant production, tillage and cultivation practices.¹⁹³

An answer to the question of whether fertilisers/soil improvers made from human excreta may be acceptable for use in organic production must take into account Article 9 which indicates that the general production rules must be respected. This requires, for example, that “the entire holding shall be managed in compliance with the requirements of this Regulation that apply to organic production” and, citing Articles 24 and 25, it notes that “only products and substances that have been authorised pursuant to those provisions may be used in organic production, provided that their use in non-organic production has also been authorised in accordance with the relevant provisions of Union law and, where applicable, in accordance with national provisions based on Union law.”¹⁹⁴ Article 9(6)

¹⁹³ Ibid, Article 9(3)(c) provides that fertiliser may be authorised if “their use is essential for building or maintaining the fertility of the soil or to fulfil specific nutritional requirements of crops, or for specific soil-conditioning purposes.”

¹⁹⁴ Ibid, Article 9(3) allows a number of plant protection products, authorised under Regulation 1107/2009 on these products, to be used in organic production.

provides that “preventive and precautionary measures shall be taken, where appropriate, at every stage of production, preparation and distribution” and these are defined in Article 3(4) and 3(5) as follows:¹⁹⁵

(4) ‘preventive measures’ means measures that are to be taken by operators at every stage of production, preparation and distribution in order to ensure the preservation of biodiversity and soil quality, measures for the prevention and control of pests and diseases and measures that are to be taken to avoid negative effects on the environment, animal health and plant health;

(5) ‘precautionary measures’ means measures that are to be taken by operators at every stage of production, preparation, and distribution to avoid contamination with products or substances that are not authorised for use in organic production in accordance with this Regulation, and to avoid the commingling of organic products with non-organic products.

Article 28 develops the precautionary measures to be taken to avoid the presence of non-authorised products and substances which include to:

- (a) put in place and maintain measures that are proportionate and appropriate to identify the risks of contamination of organic production and products with non-authorised products or substances, including systematic identification of critical procedural steps;
- (b) put in place and maintain measures that are proportionate and appropriate to avoid risks of contamination of organic production and products with non-authorised products or substances;

Measures adopted and must be regularly reviewed and, if necessary, adjusted. Article 28 makes it clear that an operator who suspects the use of products that are not authorised should not market any products as organic until the suspicion is eliminated.¹⁹⁶ The Commission has adopted number of implementing acts dealing with the investigation of these suspicions.¹⁹⁷

Production rules for plants, livestock, algae and aquaculture animals are set out in Articles 13 to 15 of the Regulation and the plant production rules are further developed in Annex

¹⁹⁵ Ibid. An operator is defined in Article 3(13) as “the natural or legal person responsible for ensuring that this Regulation is complied with at every stage of production, preparation and distribution that are under that person’s control.”

¹⁹⁶ Ibid. See also Article 29 on measures to be taken in the event of the presence of non-authorised products or substances and Commission Implementing Regulation 2023/1195 laying down rules for the details and the format of the information to be made available by Member States on the results of official investigations concerning cases of contamination with products or substances not authorised for use in organic production ,[2023] OJ L 158/65.

¹⁹⁷ See for example, Commission Implementing Regulation 2021/279 laying down detailed rules for the implementation of Regulation 2018/848 on controls and other measures ensuring traceability and compliance in organic production and the labelling of organic products, [2021] OJ L 62/6.

II which makes it clear that mineral nitrogen fertilisers are not to be used.¹⁹⁸ However, a fertiliser which respects Article 3(4) and (5) and for which a risk assessment has been undertaken may be acceptable for organic production. Guidance here is offered by Commission Implementing Regulation 2021/1165 (as amended) which in Annex II offers a list of fertilisers, soil conditioners and nutrients that may be used in organic production, provided that they are compliant with the relevant legislation, both EU and that of the Member States.¹⁹⁹ Such fertilisers may also be used under point 1.9.6 of part I of Annex II to improve the overall condition of the soil (including nutrients in the soil) or the availability of nutrients in the crops.

The first four examples are farmyard manure, dried farmyard manure and dehydrated poultry manure, composted animal excrements and liquid animal excrement although there is an exclusion if such products come from factory farming.²⁰⁰ Equivalent material from humans is clearly excluded. The next example is of greater interest, as the Annex provides that a composted or fermented bio-waste may be used. Such waste is described as follows:

- product obtained from separate bio-waste collection at source, which has been submitted to composting or to anaerobic fermentation for biogas production:
 - only vegetable and animal bio-waste;
 - only when produced in a closed and monitored collection system, accepted by the Member State;
 - maximum concentrations in mg/kg of dry matter: cadmium: 0,7; copper: 70; nickel: 25; lead: 45; zinc: 200; mercury: 0,4; chromium (total): 70; chromium (VI): not detectable.²⁰¹

This offers some hope of flexibility initially, but the definition of bio-waste is tied to Directive 2008/98 (the Waste Framework Directive).²⁰² It is clear that human excreta does not come within the definition of “bio-waste” in Article 3(4) of the WFD, namely, “biodegradable garden and park waste, food and kitchen waste from households, offices,

¹⁹⁸ Regulation 2018/848 [2018] OJ L 150/1, Annex II, para 1.9. Part II of Annex II lays down livestock production rules with various restrictions on the use of fertilisers, e.g. on housing and husbandry practices (para 1.9.1.2, 1.9.2.2, 1.9.3.2 and 1.9.5.2). See also Article 31 which provides those fertilisers authorised under Article 24 “may bear a reference indicating that those products or substances have been authorised for use in organic production in accordance with this Regulation.

¹⁹⁹ [2021] OJ L 253/13 as amended by Commission Implementing Regulations 2023/121 ([2023] OJ L 16/24), 2023/2229 ([2023] OJ L 2229/1) and 2025/973 ([2025] OJ L 973/1).

²⁰⁰ For discussion of the concept of factory farming and its replacement see [Final report on criteria for the use of animal-derived fertilisers from conventional farming replacing the term “factory farming”](#). See also Case C-228/23, *Asociación AFAÍA* ECLI:EU:C:2024:829 (judgment of 4 October 2024) which addressed the concepts of ‘factory farming’ and ‘landless livestock production.’

²⁰¹ Interestingly, this specific category was introduced in 2023 by Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/2229 of 25 October 2023 amending and correcting Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/1165 authorising certain products and substances for use in organic production and establishing their lists. Replacing an earlier version that referred to household waste instead of bio-waste.

²⁰² This issue was addressed Czarnik et al, D3.7 “Scoping review” describing the status of the legislative framework 2023, P2Green Consortium. Accessible at www.p2green.eu

restaurants, wholesale, canteens, caterers and retail premises and comparable waste from food processing plants.”

Of the remaining categories, few are of relevance with the possible exception of the final example which is biochar. However, this is defined within the Regulation as a “pyrolysis product made from a wide variety of organic materials of plant origin and applied as a soil conditioner.”²⁰³ The Regulation continues by expressly noting that it is ‘only from plant materials...’. The accompanying description notes that, as from July 2022, the relevant limits for contaminants set in the FPR apply. The other category of note is recovered struvite and this product highlights the importance of the recommendations of the Expert Group for Technical Advice on Organic Production (EGTOP) which is mandated to examine, considering technical and scientific information, whether particular substances are consistent with the objectives, principles and the general rules laid down in Organic Products Regulation and thus be authorised for use under that Regulation.²⁰⁴ Requests for substances to be added to the list may be made by Member States, certifying bodies and the Commission.²⁰⁵ Before offering its reflections and conclusions EGTOP will consider the request by examining a range of factors including, the proposed material’s agronomic use; the necessity for intended use; origin of raw materials, methods of manufacture; environmental issues; animal welfare issues; human health issues; food quality and authenticity; traditional use and precedents in organic production; authorised use in organic farming outside the EU or international harmonisation of organic farming standards.

Recovered struvite, which would help to meet the phosphorous needs of plants thus reusing both phosphorous and nitrogen and preventing pollution of surface waters from these sources, was examined by EGTOP in 2016.²⁰⁶ In their consideration, EGTOP noted that there was a lack of data on the transfer of contaminants, viruses and microorganisms of human origin during the production process but nevertheless it concluded that if struvite was listed in the revision of the fertiliser regulation, it should be included as a fertiliser for use in organic production without the submission of a further dossier to the Group provided that the method of production ensured hygienic and pollutant safety.²⁰⁷ When Regulation 2019/1009 was enacted, struvite was mentioned in recital 19 which noted the market demand as a fertiliser for certain recovered wastes, under the Waste Directive, such as struvite, and indicated that once they complied with the Regulation, they would cease to be waste under the Waste Directive.²⁰⁸ Commission Delegated Regulation

²⁰³ Although it is possible to make biochar from animal products (manure) and municipal waste these were not considered by EGTOP in their 2018 report which evaluated biochar. See Final Report on Fertilisers III, available at [final-report-egtop-fertilizers-iii_en_0.pdf](#), p 8.

²⁰⁴ The Group was most recently established by Commission Decision 4 August 2021, C(2021) 5722.

²⁰⁵ Their latest report dated January 2025 is available at [23a9c1f3-f800-44cf-be0a-570f86f94195_en](#).

²⁰⁶ See Final Report on Fertilisers II, available at [EGTOP reports - European Commission](#), pp 12-14.

²⁰⁷ Ibid, p 14.

²⁰⁸ Article 42(2) of Regulation 2019/1009, above n 1, provides that “Without undue delay after 15 July 2019, the Commission shall assess struvite, biochar and ash-based products. If that assessment concludes that the criteria in point (b) of paragraph 1 are fulfilled, the Commission shall adopt delegated acts pursuant to

2021/2086 amended the Fertiliser Regulation, introducing CMC 12 which would include struvite.²⁰⁹ In 2022, EGTOP was asked to advise whether it could be authorised for use in organic farming at the request of Germany and it concluded that products would be authorised if they meet the requirements of the Fertiliser Regulation for products derived from waste materials except that animal manure derived from factory farming could not be a source material.²¹⁰ So, the inclusion of Struvite in the FPR facilitated its recognition as a fertiliser that could be used in organic agriculture.

In many senses, the exclusion (and lack of inclusion) of human excreta is regrettable given the objectives of the WFD listed in Article 1 as being to introduce measures to protect the environment and human health “by preventing or reducing the generation of waste, the adverse impacts of the generation and management of waste and by reducing overall impacts of resource use and improving the efficiency of such use, which are crucial for the transition to a circular economy and for guaranteeing the Union’s long-term competitiveness.” The 2016 EGTOP Report included a discussion of whether human excreta could be authorised and, if so, under what conditions. Whilst pointing out that its use would close nutrient cycles and long-term sustainability, the Group raised two major concerns – the presence of human pathogens and the wide range of contaminants (e.g. cosmetics, drugs and household chemicals) before concluding that if the risks from the former could be eliminated and the risks of the latter minimised, all human excreta products could be authorized. These concerns had resulted in the silence of the Organic Products Regulation on the inclusion of human excreta – it was noted that it did not specifically exclude them – and the report concluded that “there is no conflict in theory with their recycling in organic farming” subject to its meeting hygiene and pollutant standards.²¹¹ However, this discussion highlights the need to bring human excreta within the FPR given that it established an EU-wide regime which has uniform and robust criteria for both environmental and human safety.

In 2022, EGTOP issued a statement on the environmental contamination risk in organic farming which recognised that “organic farming has done pioneering work in keeping agricultural ecosystems as free of polluting substances as possible.”²¹² It went on to reference the importance of the role played by the circular economy in the principles governing organic production but recognised the challenge posed by contaminants, such

paragraph 1 to include those materials in Annex II.” Paragraph 1(b) indicates that for which there is scientific evidence that the material does not present a risk to human, animal or plant health, to safety or to the environment and that it ensures agronomic efficiency.

²⁰⁹ [2021] OJ L 427/120.

²¹⁰ EGTOP, Final Report on plant protection (VII) and fertilisers (V) available at [EGTOP reports - European Commission](#), pp 16-18. No dossier was presented and the Group analysed struvite production from wastewater from the food and pet food industry, bio-waste, processing residues from the production of bioethanol and biodiesel and animal by-products. See above n 14 for a re-definition of “factory farming”.

²¹¹ Ibid, p 18. See also Annex II Regulation 2021/1165, which provides the recovered struvite is an authorised fertiliser provided it meets the requirements of the FPR and the animal manure as a source material does not have a factory farming origin.

²¹² Ibid, p. 24.

as microplastics, heavy metals or veterinary drugs, to consumer expectations about the quality of organic products. Although clearly undesirable, if kept to a minimum such contaminants should not prevent recycled materials being approved for organic production. This was especially the case given the Green Deal target of increasing the area devoted to organic production, but this goal brought with it issues of the co-existence of different types of production. EGTOP went on to suggest that the burden of proof for “the environmentally friendly practices should not be solely on organic farmers” and that “the applicants submitting their dossiers for the evaluation of the EGTOP should put all effort in demonstrating that the inputs intended in organic production are ecologically sustainable.” The Group merely recommended that the risks posed by contaminants should be “continuously monitored and preventively managed” and indicated that it “would welcome harmonization, among EU member states, of control practises and on actions taken in case of detections of residues of non-allowed products on organic products and in organic farms.”

Organic production is encouraged on the assumption that it is environmentally friendly, hence the encouragement to increase the percentage of EU farming devoted to this form of production. 2025 presents a significant opportunity to influence the scope of the next EU strategy for Organic Production and the content of post-2027 National Strategic Plans of the Member States under the CAP. In this context, it is worth noting the recent approval of calcium phosphate recovered from incinerated sewage sludge ash as a fertiliser for use in organic agriculture (RevoCaP); another example of a fertiliser being allowed under the FPR that can be used in organic farming. The product was developed by a Swedish company EasyMining which is part of the Swedish environmental group Ragn-Sells.²¹³ Shortly after its approval, construction began in Germany of a phosphorus recovery plant in Schkopau, Saxony-Anhalt.²¹⁴

Whilst the Organic Production regime allows the use of animal excreta as a fertiliser with its application being subject to the obligations set out in the Nitrates Directive, none of the measures so far discussed treats human excreta in the same way. However, there is one piece of legislation allowing for the use of human excreta, in the form of sewage sludge, to be applied to agricultural land.

5.4 Sewage Sludge

The European Parliament noted in its discussion of the 2022 Commission communication on fertilisers that:²¹⁵

²¹³ See [EU approves recycled phosphorus for use in organic farming](#) .

²¹⁴ See [Germany breaks ground on first full-scale phosphorus recovery plant](#). The news item notes that from 2029 all German sewage treatment plants will be required to reclaim phosphorus from sewage sludge.

²¹⁵ Resolution of 16 February 2023, [2023] OJ C 283/12, para 58.

... human waste currently represents one of major unclosed loops in the nutrient cycle, as the nutrients from sewage are mostly not returned to agricultural soils; calls on the Commission to further incentivise techniques that help retrieve nutrients from sewage sludge, including by introducing end-of-waste criteria for materials that can be recovered from sewage treatment plants, and by developing criteria for their safe application to agricultural soils

Sewage Sludge, which was not covered by existing waste legislation, was addressed in Directive 86/278 which in Article 1 listed its objective as being “to regulate the use of sewage sludge in agriculture in such a way as to prevent harmful effects on soil, vegetation, animals and man, thereby encouraging the correct use of such sewage sludge.”²¹⁶ An expansive definition of sludge is offered in Article 2(a) with Article 2(b) offering a definition of “treated sludge” as being “sludge which has undergone biological, chemical or heat treatment, long-term storage or any other appropriate process so as significantly to reduce its fermentability and the health hazards resulting from its use.”²¹⁷ Whilst encouraging the use of sewage sludge in agriculture, the Directive in its Annexes sets limits for the concentration of seven heavy metals before the sludge may be used for agricultural purposes; however, Member States are able to set more stringent requirements.²¹⁸

In 2022, the Commission published an *Implementation Report of the Sewage Sludge Directive 86/278/EEC* which noted that all but two Member States had implemented the Directive with a number of bans on the use of sewage sludge being in place.²¹⁹ Article 5 of the Directive allows Member States to prohibit the use of sludge if the limits values set out in Annex 1A are exceeded with the Report also noting that 20 Member States indicating that they had adopted measures stricter than those set out in the Directive; separate limits were set by Member States for the heavy metal concentration of sludge that may be applied to agricultural land.²²⁰ The Report noted that only five Member States allow the use of untreated sewage sludge in agriculture whilst this is prohibited in nineteen Member States.²²¹ The Report concluded that the Directive had been effectively

²¹⁶ [1986] OJ L 181/6. The Directive has been amended by Directive 91/692, [1991] OJ L 377/48, Regulation 807/2003, [2003] OJ L 122/36 and Regulation 219/2009, [2009] OJ L 87/109. Reporting under the Directive is now governed by Regulation 2019/1010, [2019] OJ L 170/115.

²¹⁷ No further definition is offered of treatment. Under Article 6(a), Member States may allow farmers to use untreated sludge if it is injected or worked into the soil.

²¹⁸ The metals are cadmium, chromium, copper, lead, mercury, nickel and zinc. No limits were set for chromium.

²¹⁹ Available at [Support to the evaluation of the Sewage Sludge Directive - Publications Office of the EU](#), p 9. The Report noted that annually the amount of sewage sludge produced was between 7 and 8 million tonnes with 2 to 3 million tonnes being used in agriculture (p 42).

²²⁰ Ibid, p 24 noted that all Member States except Cyprus, Greece and Spain have set national limits on heavy metals below those set in the Directive. All Member States using sewage sludge indicated that it was treated for pathogen removal, e.g. E. coli and Salmonella (pp 35-36). The limits are set in Annex IA – heavy metals in the soil; Annex IB – heavy metals in sludge; and Annex IC – maximum annual quantities of heavy metals that may be added to the soil.

²²¹ Ibid, p 37.

implemented across the Member States with progress being made in a number of areas, for example, the length of time during which it is forbidden to use sludge on grassland.²²²

Building on the responses which had generated the 2022 Implementation Report, in 2023 the Commission published an Evaluation of the Sewage Sludge Directive noting that despite technological changes, it had not been substantially revised and that the regulatory environment had changed notably since then (e.g. the new Fertiliser Products Regulation) as had the policy environment (e.g. the Farm-to-Fork strategy, the Biodiversity strategy and the Circular Economy Action Plans).²²³ The Evaluation would assess the Directive against five criteria, namely, effectiveness, efficiency, coherence, added value and relevance. On the first of these criteria, the Evaluation indicates that it has been effective in harmonising the use of sewage sludge in agriculture but it was not possible to conclude that the Directive had safeguarded agricultural soils from pollution.²²⁴ It goes on to indicate that other legislation has facilitated the recovery of sludge referencing, for example, the Landfill Directive and the WFD. With respect to the latter, the Commission noted that differences between criteria in the Member States on “end-of-waste” constituted a barrier for the development of sludge processing technologies.²²⁵ However, end-of-waste criteria is provided for in the FPR; other negative factors affecting effectiveness include the competition arising from other organic waste (e.g. manure, bio-waste) and other possible uses of sludge.

In terms of efficiency, the Evaluation addressed the direct costs (e.g. treatment, transport, storage and applications) and benefits of the use of sewage sludge in agriculture leading to the conclusion that “provided that environmental and health protection is safeguarded, encouraging sludge use in agriculture brings significant financial benefits to both UWWTP operators (or the end beneficiaries of saving made on treatment) and farmers, by allowing significant savings.”²²⁶ Whilst there were a number of positive externalities arising from the use of sewage sludge (e.g. climate change), there were a number of negative externalities, in particular pollution arising from contaminants not regulated by the Directive such as pharmaceuticals and microplastics. These could be addressed in any revision of the Directive which would also address its legal base allowing it to be changed from the supporting the internal market to the protection of the environment and human health. Both of these would address the coherence of the Directive with policy and

²²² Ibid, p 52. Under Article 7 of the Directive there are circumstances in which sewage sludge may not be used in farming. These are “on grassland that is going to be grazed by animals or on forage crops to be harvested, unless a minimum of 3 weeks has elapsed; on fruit and vegetable crops during the growing season. This rule does not include fruit trees; and on soil used to grow fruit and vegetable crops that are usually in direct contact with the soil and eaten raw.”

²²³ COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT EVALUATION Council Directive 86/278/EEC of 12 June 1986 on the protection of the environment, and in particular of the soil, when sewage sludge is used in agriculture [2023] SWD/2023/0157, p 4. See also European Commission: Directorate-General for Environment, IMDEA, Ricardo, Trinomics, Tyrsky and Wood, *Support to the evaluation of the Sewage Sludge Directive – Final study report* (Publications Office of the European Union, 2022).

²²⁴ Ibid, p 19.

²²⁵ Ibid, p 23.

²²⁶ Ibid, p 32.

regulatory changes made since its adoption in 1986, including the Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, the Zero Pollution Action Plan and the Soil Strategy. It is worth noting here that the public consultation exercise revealed differing answers on whether the Directive was coherent with the Waste Framework Directive and the FPR with some stakeholders arguing that a more explicit link between these pieces of legislation should be made more explicit, for example by adopting/expanding end-of-waste criteria.²²⁷

An opportunity to promote greater coherence between the Directive and other regulations was afforded by changes to the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) adopted in 2024. There is a contrast in the definitions of sludge in both Directives. The Sewage Sludge Directive offers the following definition of sludge in Article 2(a):

- (i) residual sludge from sewage plants treating domestic or urban waste waters and from other sewage plants treating waste waters of a composition similar to domestic and urban waste waters;
- (ii) residual sludge from septic tanks and other similar installations for the treatment of sewage;
- (iii) residual sludge from sewage plants other than those referred to in (i) and (ii).

In contrast, the UWWTD in Article 2(15) indicates that sludge means “organic and inorganic residue resulting from the treatment of urban wastewater from an urban wastewater treatment plant, excluding grit, grease, other debris and any other screenings and residues from the pre-treatment step.”²²⁸ Article 14 on discharges of non-domestic waste water provides in paragraph 3 that Member States are to ensure that all appropriate measures are taken to “identify, prevent and reduce as far as possible the sources of pollution in non-domestic wastewater” in a number of situations which includes when “sludge arising from urban wastewater treatment is to be used in accordance with” the Sewage Sludge Directive.²²⁹ The revised UWWTD also reflected developments in scientific knowledge in relation to pharmaceuticals and microplastics and the opportunity was taken to “update” the treatment of sludge, in relation to the latter.²³⁰ Also, of note here is Article 20 on sludge and resource recovery under which Member States are encouraged to promote “the recovery of valuable resources and take the measures necessary to ensure that sludge management conforms to the waste hierarchy provided

²²⁷ Ibid, p 39.

²²⁸ Directive (EU) 2024/3019 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 November 2024 concerning urban wastewater treatment (recast) [2024] OJ L, 2024/3019

²²⁹ Ibid, Article 14(3)(b). Sub-paragraph (c) deal with a situation arising when the treated waste water is to be used under the Water Reuse Regulation (Regulation 2020/741); see also Article 15 on Water reuse and discharge of urban wastewater.

²³⁰ Ibid, recital 42 noted “When reusing sludge in agriculture particular attention should be paid to microplastics. Microplastics should therefore be systematically monitored when sludge is reused in agriculture. This information is indispensable for the safe management of sludge in agriculture and any possible review of relevant Union policy.” See also Article 23(1) and (3) on Monitoring.

for” in the WFD.²³¹ The Commission has until January 2028 to adopt delegated acts that would specify “a combined minimum reuse and recycling rate for phosphorus from sludge.”²³² The UWWTD has effectively updated the SSD to improve the quality of sludge produced by wastewater treatment plants which will be further enhanced by these recycling rates. As the Preamble to the UWWTD proclaims: “The proper and safe recovery of nutrients and their reuse in agriculture should be encouraged in order to support the resilience and sustainability of the agricultural sector and contribute to the strategic autonomy of the Union fertiliser industry.”²³³

Returning to the Evaluation of the SSD on the question of the EU added value, the Report noted that there was “an ongoing need for the use of sludge in agriculture to be regulated in order to ensure that it is carried out safely and without harm to the environment.”²³⁴ However, some Member States have adopted more stringent rules thus frustrating the level-playing field which the Directive sought to promote, especially in relation to the environment and human health and it is suggested that the FPR is “a more effective regulatory framework ensuring the free movement of sewage sludge derived fertilisers” especially as the contaminant levels set in the Regulation are considerably stricter than those in the Directive.²³⁵ A re-framing of the Directive in terms of the environment and human health rather than the free movement of goods would allow for the Directive to be aligned more effectively with changes in the EU regulatory and policy framework. It is not therefore surprising that the Evaluation concludes that the Directive remains of continuing relevance though it could be more integrated within the existing sustainable development efforts.

5.5 The Fertilising Products Regulation

Article 4 requires that an EU fertilising product shall:

²³¹ Ibid, it continues to note that such sludge management is to “(a) maximise prevention; (b) prepare for reuse, recycling and other recovery of resources, in particular phosphorus and nitrogen, taking into account national or local valorisation options; and (c) minimise the adverse effects on the environment and human health.”

²³² Ibid, see also Article 30(1)(j) which provides that in the Evaluation of the Directive, which is to be carried out by the Commission by 31 December 2033, it shall consider “ the feasibility and appropriateness of setting Union minimum reuse and recycling rates for nitrogen from sludge or from urban wastewater, or both.”

²³³ Ibid, Recital 42.

²³⁴ COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT EVALUATION Council Directive 86/278/EEC of 12 June 1986 on the protection of the environment, and in particular of the soil, when sewage sludge is used in agriculture [2023] SWD/2023/0157, p 45.

²³⁵ Ibid, p 46. See NMI Report (below n 241) which, after noting the evaluation of the Directive, concluded that it “did not seem opportune” to include sewage sludge within the FPR as it was already regulated by the Directive. It did point to the “risk of soil contamination with pathogens, persistent organic contaminants and microplastics” from the use of sewage sludge. (p. 57).

- (a) meet the requirements set out in Annex I for the relevant product function category;
- (b) meet the requirements set out in Annex II for the relevant component material category or categories; and,
- (c) be labelled in accordance with the labelling requirements set out in Annex III.²³⁶

These are complex cumulative criteria. By virtue of Article 3, such products are to enjoy free movement within the EU (with a CE-mark), and significantly Article 19 also provides for end-of-waste status in accordance with Article 6 WFD for any waste recovered and used within such products. Article 5 provides that the products are only to be made available on the market if they comply with the Regulation, and according to Article 6 a manufacturer must ensure that the product has been designed and manufactured in accordance with the requirements in Annexes I and II and have carried out the relevant conformity assessment procedure outlined in the Regulation.

Although the FPR does not apply to derived products which are subject to the requirements of the ABPR, it does allow the Commission to determine that if these products have reached an end point in the manufacturing process, and so are not a threat to animal or human health. If this is the case, they would no longer be subject to Regulation 1069/2009 and would fall within the scope of the FPR. Article 3(d) of Regulation 2023/1605 provides that processed manure fulfilling the requirements set out in Section 2 of Annex XI to Regulation 142/2011 are to be considered as reaching the end point as organic fertilisers and soil improvers.²³⁷ As a result of this 2023 Regulation, processed manure, having reached its end point, could now contribute to the production of a fertiliser under a number of CMCs.²³⁸ By way of contrast sewage sludge is expressly excluded from the scope of three of these CMCs²³⁹ but, providing it is approved by a Member State, it can still be spread on agricultural land.

Turning to the activities of P2Green in the pilot regions, it is clear that fertilising products produced from human excreta (specifically urine and/or faeces) face numerous challenges. These include identifying a suitable PFC category—linked to the intended function of the product—and assessing compliance with the corresponding PFC-specific criteria, such as minimum nutrient content, limits for contaminants and pathogens, and any applicable process requirements. An assessment of the compliance of P2Green products in terms of nutrient content with PFC1 (fertilisers) is provided in the scoping review (D3.7).²⁴⁰ Aurin® (German pilot region) does not meet the requirements for

²³⁶ Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products and amending Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003 [2019] OJ L 170/1

²³⁷ [2023] OJ L 198/1. This applies only if manufactured in a fertiliser plant approved under Regulation 1069/2009 and does not apply if the derived product is imported into the EU.

²³⁸ For example, CMC3, CMC5, CMC10, CMC12, CMC13, CMC14 and CMC15.

²³⁹ i.e. CMC 3, 5 and 14. However, there are some limited avenues to use sewage sludge to create inputs under CMCs 12 and 13.

²⁴⁰ A detailed analysis can be found in Chapter 8.3.3 in Czarnik et al, D3.7 “Scoping review” describing the status of the legislative framework 2023, P2Green Consortium. Accessible at www.p2green.eu

classification as an organic fertiliser due to very low content in organic carbon. It can neither be an inorganic fertiliser because its total nutrient content (6.8%) falls slightly below the minimum threshold of 7% for the sum of nutrients. One corrective option would be to increase the concentration of the relevant nutrients to meet the required limit. Alternatively, if justified by the product's mode of action, placing the product on the market under a different PFC category, such as a soil improver, could be explored. Granurine pellets (Swedish pilot region) can be categorised as a "Compound solid inorganic macronutrient fertiliser". Finally, the fecal compost (German pilot region) does not contain sufficient quantities of macronutrients to qualify as a fertiliser, although it is rich in organic carbon. A more suitable classification would be as a soil improver under PFC 3. Our conclusions are validated by the findings of the Interim Report²⁴¹ of the "Technical study to support the inclusion of new materials and processes under the FPR" carried out by NMI, in which these products were evaluated.

It is also worth considering whether the P2Green products could be classified as fertilisers under PFC1 or as soil improvers under PFC3 based on parameters beyond nutrient content. Additional criteria relevant to each PFC - such as contaminants, organic matter content, process requirements, and safety specifications - would need to be assessed to determine full compliance.

As noted, the identification of a suitable CMC is also essential and this is the most obvious hurdle for P2Green-style products, with no individual CMC clearly applicable. A preliminary analysis of potential Component Material Categories (CMCs) applicable to human excreta was already provided in the scoping review (D3.7).²⁴²

Noticeably, human excreta are not treated in the same way as animal excreta (e.g. manure): greater consistency of approach to the treatment of all excreta irrespective of its origins offers the potential to bring human excreta within the scope of the FPR. There are a few potential options for reform here, including:

- Under CMC 1 – Virgin material substances and mixtures – under this CMC the excluded matter includes, for example, "waste within the meaning of Directive 2008/98" and "substances or mixtures which have ceased to be waste in one or more Member States by virtue of the national measures transposing Article 6 of Directive 2008/98." If it were determined that human excreta in some circumstances were not waste under the Waste Framework Directive, then such human excreta could potentially qualify as a substance under CMC1. Note however that by-products are excluded from CMC 1, so the applicability would

²⁴¹ [Van Schöll L and Riechelmann W, Technical study to support the inclusion of new materials and processes under the Fertilising Products Regulation \(FPR\); Lot 2: Material and processes under the FPR First interim report; Assessment of market perspective, \(2025, Nutrient Management Instituut BV, Wageningen\), Report NMI 2002.N.23\(II\)](#), accessed on 6th November 2025

²⁴² A detailed analysis can be found in Chapter 8.3.2 in Czarnik et al, D3.7 "Scoping review" describing the status of the legislative framework 2023, P2Green Consortium. Accessible at www.p2green.eu

depend on the nature of any amendment to, or official interpretation of, the Waste Framework Directive.²⁴³

- Under CMC3 – Compost – under this CMC the input materials include bio-waste “resulting from separate bio-waste collection at source.” As noted, Article 3(4) of Directive 2008/98 defines bio-waste as “biodegradable garden and park waste, food and kitchen waste from households, offices, restaurants, wholesale, canteens, caterers and retail premises and comparable waste from food processing plants.” If this were to be amended to encompass human excreta, then it is possible that it could qualify as an input material to compost. An alternative here would be an amendment to paragraph 1(c) which currently provides:

living or dead organisms or parts thereof, which are unprocessed or processed only by manual, mechanical or gravitational means, by dissolution in water, by flotation, by extraction with water, by steam distillation or by heating solely to remove water, or which are extracted from air by any means, except:

- (i) materials originating from mixed municipal waste;
- (ii) sewage sludge, industrial sludge or dredging sludge, and
- (iii) animal by-products or derived products within the scope of Regulation 1069/2009.

However, as mentioned, processed manure that has reached the end point in the manufacturing chain and no longer falls within the scope of Regulation 1069/2009 is now capable of being an input material to a fertiliser, including under CMC3. To ensure coherence and consistency of regulatory treatment, potential reforms could be to permit treated human excreta and also sewage sludge as input materials in CMC3. These potential changes to CMC3 could also be applied to CMC5 which is the anaerobic equivalent of the aerobic process outlined in CMC3. However, a key consideration in undertaking such changes would be to ensure environmental and human health safety, highlighted by the significance of the end point for processed manure. It might be necessary to include conditions within any amended CMC of compliance with specific standards, found in that CMC, in existing legislation (e.g. within the EQSD) or in new legislation created in parallel (e.g. legislation specifically focussed on human excreta).

However, most of the existing CMCs, including CMC3, remain relatively inflexible regarding the processes and treatments that may be used, as they prescribe specific permitted process steps rather than focusing solely on whether the final product meets defined safety and quality standards. For example, composting requires compliance with a prescribed time–temperature profile. It is unclear whether a two-step composting process—where the first step achieves the required hygienisation profile and the second

²⁴³ Products containing CMC1 materials follow conformity assessment Module A, which relies on self-assessment of the manufacturer without the involvement of a notified body. For this reason, regulators would likely consider this pathway inappropriate for human excreta-derived materials.

involves adding additional materials followed by further composting—would be considered acceptable under the current framework.

It is possible that the changes noted above could also be used in other CMCs but given that these involve particular processes (for example, precipitation in CMC12 or thermal oxidation in CMC13) they are not of great relevance to P2GreeN activities. With this conclusion, it is suggested that perhaps the best course of action to accommodate P2GreeN activities within the FPR is the creation of a new CMC or CMCs addressing human excreta.

In the first interim Report published by NMI a number of proposals were addressed for possible inclusion as a new CMC, the inclusion of new input materials and new raw materials into an existing CMC and the inclusion of new treatments in existing CMCs.²⁴⁴ The Report considered source-separated urine as a material for a new CMC pointing to the wide range of actors making proposals as evidence of a “broad interesting in recovering nutrient from human waste.”²⁴⁵ The Report noted that a urine-based fertiliser is already available within the EU – Aurin – which was approved in Austria and subject to mutual recognition in France and Germany (and also in Switzerland and Liechtenstein). However, it also recognised that the FPR does not allow source-separated urine as an input material for fertiliser products and the NMI Report noted there is some discussion as to whether it falls under UWWTD²⁴⁶ It concluded that two treatments could be considered – nitrification (used in the production of Aurin) and alkaline drying treatment (used in the production of Granurine) – and that further evaluation of its agronomic efficiency and environmental and health safety was necessary before any recommendation could be made.²⁴⁷

The interim Report also considered whether human excreta more generally could be considered as a new input material; this would cover for example, faeces from dry or water-saving toilets or this material mixed with urine, toilet paper and dry materials.²⁴⁸

However, it is understandable that the priority lies in materials that are well known and/or already established on the EU market. Whilst national laws can also apply to regulate products locally, for certain materials (such as those derived from waste, secondary raw materials, human excreta) national authorities often lack the tools or resources to thoroughly assess their safety and regulate them and they advise to just follow the FPR if possible. As a result, these materials may be excluded from the market although they have potential. Moreover, without market access due to legal constraints, promising technologies cannot be upscaled, and as a result, they remain excluded from future regulatory updates, thus creating a continuous, self-perpetuating loop. This essentially

²⁴⁴ See n241 above.

²⁴⁵ Ibid, p 48.

²⁴⁶ Ibid, p. 70.

²⁴⁷ Ibid, p 52. The Report went on to suggest that calcium phosphate from source-separated urine would fall under CMC12.

²⁴⁸ Ibid, p 61.

leads to circular exclusion, rather than a circular economy – innovators need legal certainty and a pathway for economic viability.

There is a clear need to develop further CMCs, but also to amend the existing ones, e.g. to enable a broader range of inputs and processes. Greater flexibility should be allowed regarding production processes and treatments, provided that the final product is demonstrated to be safe for both the environment and human health. Human excreta should be allowed broadly in an existing CMC, or possibly a new CMC. While there is some potential scope for human excreta and their derivatives to be included within a CMC, for example, under CMC12 and CMC13, these are limited and unclear. It would be feasible and desirable, as a means of implementing the circular economy, to facilitate the use of human excreta more generally as part of a CMC. This should be undertaken expressly, most likely in one or more new CMCs, thereby providing legal certainty. To ensure a high standard of environmental and human health protection, as well as to offset any concerns, general criteria could and should be included regarding relevant standards and, for instance, a link to the EQSD. This would reflect the approach across the FPR and the content could also be informed by the WRR and its provisions on drafting Risk Management Plans, which are linked to a range of other EU law.

In conclusion, there is some incoherence between, for instance, the potential to use animal manure as an ingredient, but not to use the equivalent from humans. While these substances are not identical, similar nutritional benefits and environmental and health concerns and benefits arise. It is possible to also include criteria and controls to ensure that any reasonable concerns are addressed. Significantly, enabling the use of human excreta as a CMC, subject to suitable conditions, would help the reclamation of valuable nutrients from human waste and thereby the implementation of the circular economy. It would simultaneously help reduce costs for municipalities treating wastewater and reduce the reliance on livestock manure and chemical fertilisers (including imported fertilisers).

5.6 National Fertiliser Regulations

The EU's FPR operates in parallel to a range of national/domestic regimes across the Member States. For the main part, they each have prior authorisation regimes.²⁴⁹ Innovators therefore have, in principle, the option of seeking authorisation within one Member State and then applying for mutual recognition in one or multiple other Member States. The discussion below outlines some of the key components of these regimes across the regions, with the exception of Spain as the domestic fertiliser regime is of less relevance for P2Green's activities there compared to the WRR.

²⁴⁹ Sweden is a prime exception here, although this does not mean that there are no applicable rules.

Many of the domestic regimes mirror, or at least bear strong similarities to, the FPR regime. While the focus of this section is on the domestic regimes that similarity is an important consideration for the FPR regime. First, if it is considered that the EU regime is shaping the national regimes, then this means the nature and content of the FPR is even more important. Second, the approach to developing the FPR, for example, through introducing new CMCs, appears to be heavily dependent on an examination of products that are already authorised domestically. This leads to a counterproductive situation that excludes the potential for innovative products not already foreseen and provided for by the FPR's existing provisions and negates the valuable option of updating those provisions – if a product is not able to obtain the CE-mark under the FPR, it is unlikely to be authorised in Member States with parallel domestic regimes, which simultaneously weakens the case for amending the FPR due to the current focus on market demand and existing authorisations.

5.6.1 Germany

In June 2024, the Bundestag approved changes to the German Fertiliser Act but within the next month, the Bundesrat had rejected those changes leading to a reference by the Government to the Mediation Committee to find an agreed solution.²⁵⁰ Changes to the legislation appear inevitable, especially as in November 2024 the Commission on the Future of Agriculture noted that “the current fertiliser law with its diverse documentation requirements is too complicated for many farms and can hardly be monitored by the authorities. In addition, it must be questioned whether the detailed documentation contributes to achieving the objectives at all.”²⁵¹ The Commission recommended that fertiliser policy should be manageable.²⁵² So, pending these change the relevant legislation remains the 2009 Fertiliser Act which has a number of purposes, the most relevant of which from a Mutual Recognition perspective is “to prevent or avert dangers to human and animal health as well as to the ecosystem that may arise from the manufacture, placing on the market or use of fertilisers, soil additives, plant aids and growing media or other fertilisation measures.”²⁵³

Article 2 of the 2009 Act offers various definitions of the scope of fertilisers which are viewed as “substances, other than carbon dioxide and water, which are intended to: a)

²⁵⁰ For further details see, [BMLEH - Plant production - Fertilisation](#)

²⁵¹ See The future of agriculture. A common agenda in difficult times - Strategic guidelines and recommendations of the Commission on the Future of Agriculture, p. 17 available at [ZLK report November 2024](#).

²⁵² Ibid, 18. See also Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture *2035 Arable Farming Strategy: Prospects for Productive and Diverse Crop Farming* (2025) available at [2035 Arable Farming Strategy](#).

²⁵³ Text available at [Fertiliser Act - unofficial table of contents](#). Article 1(5) of the Act provides that its purpose was “to implement or implement legal acts of the European Community or of the European Union that concern the subject areas of this Act, in particular on the marketing or use of fertilisers.”

provide crops with nutrients to promote their growth, increase their yield or improve their quality, or b) maintain or improve soil fertility.” Article 2(10) also defines “placed on the market” as “offering, keeping in stock for distribution, holding for sale and any distribution.” Further guidance on this is promised via Statutory Instrument enacted by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Regional Identity with Article 5 providing that fertilisers.²⁵⁴

... which are not designated as 'EC fertilisers' may be placed on the market only to the extent that they are suitable to:

1. to significantly promote the growth of crops,
2. significantly increase their yield,
3. significantly improve their quality, or
4. maintain or sustainably improve the fertility of the soil, in particular the humus content typical of the site and use,

and which, when used properly, do not harm the health of humans and animals and do not endanger the natural balance.

This can be achieved via domestic authorisations or mutual recognition.

In 2012 the Federal Ministry promulgated an Ordinance on the Placing on the Market of Fertilisers, Soil Additives, Growing Media and Plant Aids, which effectively implements Article 5 of the 2009 Act.²⁵⁵ Annex 1 lists the type of fertilisers subject to the Ordinance, with Article 3 of the Ordinance indicating that such fertilisers are to be authorised provided “they do not harm the fertility of the soil, the health of humans, animals and crops and do not endanger the natural balance when used properly.”²⁵⁶ Section 1 of the Annex offers requirements for mineral fertilisers which include fertilisers made with Nitrogen, Phosphates, Potassium, Lime and those from secondary nutrients. The section offers requirements on minimum grade, type-determining components, information on nutrient evaluation; essential composition including methods of production and special provisions. Similar details are offered in Section 2 for Mineral Compound fertilisers i.e. various combinations of Nitrogen (N) Phosphate (P) Potassium (K) (NP, NK, PK and NPK) with Section 3 setting out requirements for organic and organic-mineral fertilisers. Thresholds and limit values for a range of ingredients are listed in Annex 2; in Table 1 these include limit values for secondary ingredients such as Nitrogen, Phosphate, Potassium and a

²⁵⁴ Article 7a of the 2012 Ordinance on the Placing on the Market of Fertilisers, Soil Additives, Growing Media and Plant Aids (Available at [DüMV - unofficial table of contents](#)) provides that anyone using this provision must ensure that it is marketed in German and be clearly legible, indicating that it is in accordance with the requirements of the country in which it was lawfully manufactured or lawfully marketed.

²⁵⁵ Available at [DüMV - unofficial table of contents](#).

²⁵⁶ Ibid, Article 4(1) indicates that farm manure, if not placed on the market as fertilisers, may only be placed on the market if “when used properly, they do not harm the fertility of the soil, the health of human, animals and crops and do not endanger the natural balance.”

number of other chemical elements; the Table requires marking of a percentage and tolerance levels.²⁵⁷

A range of pollutants is listed in Table 1.4 including arsenic, lead, cadmium, chromium and mercury amongst others. It also lists the starting materials for various types of mineral fertilisers including wastewater treatment, aerobic and anaerobic treatments; for example, the starting materials for phosphate fertilisers may include the incineration of substances of animal origin and sewage sludge.²⁵⁸ Animal by-products are listed as a possible main ingredient of a fertiliser in Table 7.2.1 with Table 7.4.3 listing sewage sludge as a possible main ingredient and organic waste (i.e. bio-waste) being listed in Table 7.4.4. In contrast to Regulation 2019/1009, the requirements for pathogens, toxins and other harmful agents are listed in Article 5 which not only includes salmonella but also reference the protective measures to be taken under Directive 2000/29 to prevent the introduction into the EU of organisms harmful to plants or plant products.²⁵⁹ Compliance with the provisions of the Ordinance is monitored by the Official Fertiliser Market Control Authority.²⁶⁰

5.6.2 Sweden

Sweden may be regarded as an outlier when it comes to fertilising products for although it lacks a tailored regime focused on fertilising products, nonetheless it does have a range of applicable laws and a requirement for registration.²⁶¹ A point to note at the start is the sheer difficulty in trying to identify and understand the legal obligations for anyone, especially those seeking to engage with the market for the first time – this is the case for both placing products on the market for the first time and for mutual recognition.

There are general environmental rules regarding the use of fertilisers and other products on agricultural land, which includes limits regarding the amount of certain nutrients that can be applied over a set period.²⁶² Some controls exist regarding the treatment of

²⁵⁷ Ibid, Article 8 also offers guidance on tolerances.

²⁵⁸ For further discussion see *Sewage Sludge Disposal in the Federal Republic of Germany* (2018) available at [Sewage Sludge Disposal in the Federal Republic of Germany](#).

²⁵⁹ Ibid, Article 5(2)(c) lists various fungal pathogens. Directive 2000/29 ([2000] OJ L 169/1) has been replaced by Regulation 2016/2031 ([2016] OJ L 317/4) which was last updated by Regulation 2024/3115 ([2024] OJ L 3115).

²⁶⁰ See also Article 10 of the 2009 Act which created a Scientific Advisory Board to offer advice on fertilisation issues and may offer recommendations for the authorisation of new fertilisers having considered their “agronomic efficacy, environmental sustainability and consumer protection. See For details see [BMLEH - Advisory Boards - Scientific Advisory Board on Fertiliser Issues](#).

²⁶¹ E.g. [Gödsmedelsproduktion i Sverige - Aktuella initiativ, tekniker och förutsättningar](#), section 5.2.1 on p.72, accessed 28 October 2025.

²⁶² E.g. [SJVFS 2004:62 Statens jordbruksverks föreskrifter om miljöhänsyn i jordbruket vad avser växtnäring](#) (The Swedish Board of Agriculture's regulations on environmental considerations in agriculture

fertilisers derived from animal by-products and also the use of sewage sludge on land, due to the corresponding EU legislation.²⁶³ There are also controls on the use of chemicals, in particular, cadmium.²⁶⁴ Ammonium carbonate fertilisers are also prohibited, as per EU law on emissions. While there is some considerable flexibility for minor operations or those on one's own land or for non-commercial use, once a product is imported or to be used commercially, it appears that the body/company must register with the Swedish Board of Agriculture²⁶⁵ and also potentially register the product with KEMI.²⁶⁶

It is worth noting that there is a slightly bizarre situation arising in Sweden, with respect to product development and commercialisation. Research activities are relatively easy to undertake and, in principle, fertiliser production in Sweden should be easily able to be upscaled and placed on the market, but the very lack of a domestic fertiliser authorisation regime actually creates greater challenges for P2GreeN-style products. This is in part due to acceptability issues and difficulties in demonstrating to the public/farmers/stakeholders the safety and environmental advantages of such products, and also in part because of there being no clearcut path to end-of-waste status.²⁶⁷ Yet mutual recognition is an option in principle.

There is, in parallel, the potential to apply for and receive voluntary certifications, e.g. via Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE). While there is no obviously relevant certification

with regard to plant nutrition). For discussion of the rules (somewhat outdated), please see: "[Actions against Plant Nutrient Losses from Agriculture](#)".

²⁶³ E.g. see [Gödselmedelsproduktion i Sverige - Aktuella initiativ, tekniker och förutsättningar](#) section 5.2.2 on p.75, referring, for instance, to 'Föreskrifter (SNFS 1994:2) om skydd för miljön, särskilt marken, när avloppsslam används i jordbruket' on sewage sludge. See also the Board of Agriculture's report at pp.94-5.

²⁶⁴ See generally, the rules set by the Swedish Chemical Agency, KEMI, "[Rules on reporting to the Swedish Products Register](#)". These note that the marketing of fertilisers containing more than 100gm of Cadmium per tonne of phosphorous is normally prohibited.

²⁶⁵ See [Trade with soil and fertiliser](#).

²⁶⁶ See n264 above. Of note, for instance, Kemikalieinspektionens föreskrifter (KIFS 2017:7) om kemiska produkter och biotekniska organismer, 14§ means that companies that manufacture, import or place fertilizers on the Swedish market must report cadmium levels to the Swedish Chemicals Agency's product register in accordance with the Swedish Chemicals Agency's regulation. The Board of Agriculture's report in 2023 "[Gödselmedelsproduktion i Sverige - Aktuella initiativ, tekniker och förutsättningar](#)" https://www2.jordbruksverket.se/download/18.7dcc8c181886a656b837d93/1709117085578/ra23_9.pdf, at p.99 provided some basic information regarding current fertilisers on the Swedish market.

²⁶⁷ Board of Agriculture's 2023 Report, "[Gödselmedelsproduktion i Sverige - Aktuella initiativ, tekniker och förutsättningar](#)", at Section 1.5.5 on p.95 notes that there is no relevant end of waste criteria in Sweden. Instead, there is guidance from the Swedish EPA on when waste ceases to be waste: <https://www.naturvardsverket.se/vagledning-och-stod/avfall/bedomning-av-nar-avfall-upphor-att-vara-avfall/>. This places the core responsibility on the operator to self-assess as to whether waste has ceased to be waste as per chapter 15, section 9(a) of the Environmental Code. The relevant supervisory authority then reviews the operator's assessment, but does **not** issue a decision. There is either a statement of non-compliance/disagreement with the operator's assessment or a quasi de facto decision, but the EPA have actively decided not to make a decision – saying that the assessment could change, e.g. depending on the market context.

currently in use, previous ones such as SPCR 178 could provide a foundation for developing new, more tailored, certificates.²⁶⁸ These can be useful for marketing and complying with retailers' requirements,²⁶⁹ and potentially for a pathway to 'end-of-waste' status, but also for the purposes of obtaining further approval as organic products or under the related KRAV regime. This regime provides labels for organic food produced without chemical pesticides and so, is dependent on the EU Organic Products Regulation, which currently poses considerable challenges.

5.6.3 France

Fertilisers are regulated primarily under the Code Rural et de la Peche Maritime (CRPM), but with links to other laws such as those in the Code de l' Environnement, the Code de la Consommation and EU laws. A substance may only be sold or used as a fertiliser if it complies with specific criteria, which typically involves a prior authorisation process. The key pathways to be approved are via (i) the EU FPR as discussed earlier in the legislative report (and previous scoping review),²⁷⁰ (ii) domestically or (iii) via mutual recognition. While the EU FPR is inadequate for P2Green purposes currently, the other two pathways are potentially viable.

L255 of the CRPM is the key provision addressing authorisation of fertilisers, which is then supplemented by R255-1 to R255-14 of the CRPM and the Arrêté of 1st April 2020.²⁷¹ L255 sets out the broad approach to authorisation of fertilisers and the requirements to seek approval from the relevant national competent authority, Agence nationale de sécurité sanitaire (ANSES). L255-2 provides that importation, use, sale, distribution etc is conditional on authorisation obtained in accordance with the conditions outlined in L255-7. This applies even where the fertiliser is entirely composed of substances that are themselves authorised fertilisers.²⁷² L255-4 provides that experimentation is conditional on permission in accordance with L255-8 (subject to the provisions of L255-9).²⁷³ Before

²⁶⁸ See for instance "[Five projects granted seed funding at SLU Urban Futures](#)" accessed 28 October 2025.

²⁶⁹ E.g. Ekane, Nelson & Barquet, Karina & Rosemarin, Arno. Resources and Risks: Perceptions on the Application of Sewage Sludge on Agricultural Land in Sweden, a Case Study. (2021) *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*. 5. 647780. 10.3389/fsufs.2021.647780. Accessed 28 October 2025.

²⁷⁰ This also is provided for under L255-5 of the CRPM.

²⁷¹ [Arrêté du 1er avril 2020 fixant la composition des dossiers de demandes relatives à des autorisations de mise sur le marché et permis de matières fertilisantes, d'adjuvants pour matières fertilisantes et de supports de culture et les critères à prendre en compte dans la préparation des éléments requis pour l'évaluation](#) [2020] JORF n°0085 du 7 avril 2020. The 2020 Order repealed a previous 1998 Arrêté, but care should be taken as several official websites still continue to refer to the 1998 Arrêté

²⁷² L255-6. However, L255-6 does provide for exceptions, e.g. where it complies with conditions set by order by the minister for agriculture that ensure it does not harm human health, animal health or the environment.

²⁷³ L255-9 provides for a potential exemption linked to conditions set by decree of the Conseil d'Etat that guarantee absence of harm to human health, animal health and the environment.

considering those conditions, L255-5, in particular, provides for some substances to be exempted. These include fertilisers that comply with a standard made compulsory by an order based in Décret n° 2009-697 du 16 juin 2009 relatif à la normalisation pris pour l'application de la loi n° 41-1987 du 24 mai 1941 relative à la normalisation and fertilising materials that comply with specific criteria approved by regulation, guaranteeing their effectiveness and safety. There is therefore the option already existing in French law for orders or regulations to provide tailored criteria for fertilisers and their ingredients, including ones that encompass P2GreeN products/materials. Alternatively, applications can be undertaken on a case-by-case basis in accordance with L255-7.

L255-7 provides that the authorisation is to be issued by ANSES (the authority designated under L1313-5 of the Public Health Code) following an assessment, which under the prescribed conditions of use, demonstrates both an absence of harmful effects on human health, animal health and the environment and simultaneously the effectiveness (depending on the individual substance) regarding plants and plant products or soils. L255-8 provides similarly regarding experimentation. L255-13 then provides for the Conseil d'Etat to set the relevant conditions by decree.

This brings us to R255-1 to R255-14 (codified originally by decree) and also the 2020 Arrêté. These provisions outline the procedures, timelines and details of what the applicant and agency must undertake – all linked back to L255-7 and the ideas of efficacy and harmlessness. R255-13 provides for the Minister for Agriculture to create an 'arrêté' or order (based on the proposal of the director general of ANSES) that determines the content and composition of dossiers submitted in applications for authorisations/permits under the chapter. R255-14 provides similarly, but the order would contain guidelines identifying criteria to be taken into account in the context of L255-7 and L255-8.

The 2020 Arrêté²⁷⁴ implements R255-13 and R255-14 and provides clearer details regarding the specific procedures and evidence to be provided. Article 2 indicates that a dossier must be provided that includes a letter, form and complementary evidence to demonstrate that the criteria in the subsequent articles are fulfilled. For authorisation to place on the market, Article 3 requires that this includes information regarding traceability, composition, the process for making the fertiliser, analysis reports, reports regarding safety (for humans, animals and the environment), reports on effectiveness etc.²⁷⁵ It is worth noting that Article 3 requires the inclusion of the safety data sheet for the product and all raw materials, as per Article 31 of Regulation 1907/2006 - the REACH Regulation. The Arrêté's annex addresses trace metallic elements, trace organic compounds and microbiological criteria²⁷⁶ – these are not absolute limits for the fertilisers, but, if exceeded, the applicant/operator must justify why they are exceeded and why the substance should nonetheless be authorised. Cumulative effects are considered, taking into account conditions of use, to ensure absence of harmful effects. In contrast with the EU regime,

²⁷⁴ See n271 above.

²⁷⁵ Article 3. Articles 4-6 address other authorisation requests.

²⁷⁶ Some of these are derived from European guidance documents, as noted in the Annex.

these documents do not mandate specific levels regarding nutrients or specific ingredients, thereby providing greater flexibility to operators (and, indeed, ANSES).

Subsequent provisions in the CPRM (L255-14 to L255-18) address issues of monitoring of effectiveness, emergency measures and controls and sanctions. Furthermore, once authorised in France, operators could then seek mutual recognition in other EU Member States, providing evidence of domestic authorisation, processes, standards etc. However, while mutual recognition is based in EU law, there is no guarantee that other Member States will be willing to facilitate it.

Linking back to the issue of waste and the EU's general waste regime: L255-12 provides for a substance authorised as a fertiliser domestically to cease to be waste, provided that it meets the conditions of L.541-4-3 of the Code de l' Environnement.²⁷⁷ This ties directly to, and would appear to fulfil, the conditions outlined under Article 6 of the WFD and 'end-of-waste' status. Therefore, if an operator received approval in France for human excreta to be used in a fertiliser in France, it could cease to be waste domestically and also under EU law. However, each product would need to be examined carefully on a case-by-case basis. This would potentially enable its transport across the EU without triggering laws regarding transboundary waste, subject to the relevant authorities in the receiving Member State not objecting to this.²⁷⁸ The approach here is also worth highlighting as the basis to inform amendments to the EU level and specifically to the CMCs in the FPR, as the French approach is currently more flexible.

It is also worth noting that an exception from prior authorisation is provided under L255-5, which has the potential to be relevant to P2Green type activities and products. It provides that wastes, residues or effluents from specific installations provided for under the environmental code, where they are spread on agricultural land for the purpose of fertilising and where the plan for spreading guarantees the absence of any harmful effects on human or animal health or the environment.²⁷⁹ This raises three key questions: does the installation in question fall within the scope; what counts as wastes, residues or effluents for these purposes; what treatments/changes are permitted or requires to the wastes, residues and effluents; and how could such a plan guarantee no harmful effects.

²⁷⁷ L541-4-3 is complemented then by Articles D541-12-4 to D541-12-14, introduced by décrets.

²⁷⁸ Provided for under L.541-4-3 of the Code de l'Environnement and reflected (to a large extent) in the discussions in chapter 3 above regarding transboundary shipments of waste. Part IV therein states: '-Les substances ou objets ayant cessé d'être des déchets au titre du présent article restent soumis au régime des déchets pour l'application des dispositions du règlement (CE) n° 1013/2006 du Parlement européen et du Conseil du 14 juin 2006 concernant les transferts de déchets, sauf si l'exportateur apporte la preuve que l'autorité compétente de destination au sens de ce règlement, sollicitée sur la classification de la substance ou de l'objet faisant l'objet du transfert, n'a pas émis d'objection.'

²⁷⁹ 'Sont dispensés des obligations prévues aux articles L. 255-2 à L. 255-4 :..... Les déchets, résidus ou effluents issus des installations définies aux articles L. 214-1 et L. 511-1 du code de l'environnement dont l'évacuation ou le déversement sur des terres agricoles en tant que matières fertilisantes fait l'objet d'un plan d'épandage garantissant l'absence d'effet nocif sur la santé humaine et animale et sur l'environnement'.

5.6.4 Italy

The key sources for this information include: the National Phytosanitary Service²⁸⁰ (an official state body), legislative decree No. 75 of 29 April 2010²⁸¹ (the main source of applicable law, supplemented by EU and national/domestic laws),²⁸² and the Ministry of Agricultural, Food and Forestry Policies (which keeps a Register of Fertilizer Manufacturers and a Registry of (national) Fertilisers - with a section each on fertilisers for use in conventional farming and organic farming).²⁸³ The information is largely in Italian and likewise documentation must generally be in Italian.

Registration on both Registries is essential before placing a fertiliser on the market and must be confirmed annually. A manufacturer must first register as a manufacturer before they try to register a fertiliser. The Ministry provides a detailed outline of the procedural steps involved.²⁸⁴ Legislative Decree No.75 of 29 April 2010 is the applicable national law. It governs the marketing of both national and EU fertilisers (and related products). It contains definitions, and obligations regarding quality, efficacy, safety levels etc, alongside requirements regarding aspects such as labelling and testing. The Annexes provide further details, including Annex 1 in particular.²⁸⁵ Article 8 is the provision mandating registration of manufacturers and products. Registration is free, although requests to include new types of fertilisers or to amend the Annexes costs €3,000 (and must be accompanied by relevant documentation once more).²⁸⁶ According to a preliminary investigation the Italian decree does not include human-excreta derived fertilisers and an application to include a new type must be submitted which can take up to 8 years. Further hurdles exist if the fertilisers are to be used in organic farming.²⁸⁷

²⁸⁰ The website of the NPS is the following: <https://www.protezionedellepiante.it/fertilizzanti/>.

²⁸¹ [DECRETO LEGISLATIVO 29 aprile 2010, n. 75 Riordino e revisione della disciplina in materia di fertilizzanti, a norma dell'articolo 13 della legge 7 luglio 2009](#), n. 88. (10G0096) (GU Serie Generale n.121 del 26-05-2010 - Suppl. Ordinario n. 106)

²⁸² *ibid.* Previously also decree of 28 June 2016 doing similarly. [LEGGE 28 dicembre 2015, n. 221, disposizioni in materia ambientale per promuovere misure di green economy e per il contenimento dell'uso eccessivo di risorse naturali](#), which amends the fertiliser legislation with respect to corrective fertilisers and also the use of compostable plastics.

²⁸³ E.g. [Registro fabbricanti di fertilizzanti e registro fertilizzanti](#).

²⁸⁴ You can find more information [here](#).

²⁸⁵ [Annex I](#) (accessed 14 November 2025).

²⁸⁶ See Article 14 and Annex 10 of the Decree. For further procedural information, see the [website](#) of the National Phytosanitary Service.

²⁸⁷ See for instance the relevant section of the Registry of Fertilisers and the document on the [Supplemental admission criteria for the Italian Input List \(2019\)](#).

5.6.5 Greece

The Greek legislative framework concerning fertilising products includes two main product categories; fertilisers and other non-fertilising products that are used in agriculture. The basic Law for fertilisers is Law No 1565/85 (Official Gazette A'164) named "Fertilisers", as modified and applies²⁸⁸. According to Par 1 of Art. 1 (Definitions) of Law No 1565/85 "Fertilisers are considered to be organic and inorganic substances which, when used in crops, enhance plant growth, increase yield, and improve product quality".

In section A "Categories" of Par. 1 of Article 1 the categories of products used in agriculture are described, specifically: a. fertilisers, b. soil improvers, c. growth media and d. plant growth promoting substances, along with their subcategories. At the end of this section the following is stated: "In the categories of cases (a) to (d) in this paragraph waste, such as wastewater, sludge, slurry, and other similar products, are not included if they have not undergone appropriate treatment and have not been enriched with nutrients." The Greek Joint Ministerial Decision sewage sludge in agriculture²⁸⁹, as per the SSD, defines specifications and treatment requirements to be used as is in agricultural land. However, there are no relevant laws or ministerial decisions on how materials like wastewater, slurry or other similar products can be treated to be accepted as ingredients in fertilisers. Also, in the mandatory labelling requirements the following is included: "If the product contains raw materials from municipal or industrial waste, a relevant phrase must be included on the label."

Until the 10th of March 2025, fertilisers being placed on the market under the national framework needed to first be authorised by the ministry of Rural Development and Food and were called new type fertilisers. The procedure of the authorisation is described in the Joint Ministerial Decision No 291180/11034/02 (B' 1274)²⁹⁰. On the 10th of March, Ministerial Decision No 50424 (FEK B' 1074/10.03.2025) was published²⁹¹. The purpose of the decision is:

- The definition of the types of fertilisers that can be circulated in the country and the elements that identify them

²⁸⁸ National legislative acts and relevant documents are available at the [website](#) of the Hellenic Ministry of Rural Development and Food.

²⁸⁹ [Υπουργική Απόφαση ΥΠΕΝ/ΔΔΑ/41828/630/2023 \(ΦΕΚ 2692/Β' 21.4.2023\) "Μέτρα, όροι και διαδικασίες για τη χρησιμοποίηση επεξεργασμένης ιλύος στη γεωργία και στην αποκατάσταση του εδάφους - Συμμόρφωση προς τις διατάξεις της Οδηγίας 86/278/ΕΟΚ του Συμβουλίου της 12ης Ιουνίου 1986 «σχετικά με την προστασία του περιβάλλοντος και ιδίως του εδάφους κατά τη χρησιμοποίηση της ιλύος καθαρισμού λυμάτων στη γεωργία», όπως τροποποιήθηκε με τον Κανονισμό \(ΕΕ\) 2019/1010 του Ευρωπαϊκού Κοινοβουλίου και του Συμβουλίου της 5ης Ιουνίου 2019 και αντικατάσταση τη υπ' αρ. 80568/4225/1991 \(B' 641\) κοινής υπουργικής απόφασης."](#)

²⁹⁰ See n288 above

²⁹¹ Ibid

- The determination of the terms and conditions for the circulation of products that are not considered fertilisers for the purpose of their marketing and use in agriculture

This decision introduces Annexes that specify a) permitted raw materials, b) approved manufacturing processes, c) additional requirements, such as minimum nutrient content for each fertiliser category. Products (either fertilisers or non-fertilising products) that contain allowed materials and meet all specified criteria may be placed on the Greek market without prior authorisation from the Ministry of Rural Development and Food. However, if a product is not covered by the Ministerial Decision, the company must submit an application to request the inclusion of the new material or product in the Annexes.

Under the previous regulatory framework, the allowed materials were not explicitly defined, and each fertiliser had to be individually evaluated by the Ministry and the Technical Expert Committee before receiving authorisation for market placement. Consequently, the P2Green products would have required prior examination, and the companies involved would have needed to submit a technical dossier for approval.

Under the new framework, the requirements are more structured. For the Swedish (pellets) and German (Aurin) fertilisers, we examined Annex I, Part II – Inorganic Fertilisers, specifically Section A – Straight Inorganic Fertilisers and Section B – Inorganic Compound Fertilisers of Primary Nutrient Elements.

This category includes products produced through chemical processes or physical mixtures, without the inclusion of organic substances of animal or plant origin, containing at least 3% of one of the elements N, P₂O₅, or K₂O, and less than 1% organic carbon, except when derived from specific sources such as inhibitors. These must be solid products or solutions obtained through chemical synthesis or physical blending of components.

An analysis of compliance of P2Green fertilisers, with the nutrient limits showed that Granurine pellets (Swedish pilot region) could be considered as a compound solid NPK fertiliser. Aurin (German pilot region) could not be considered as a compound liquid fertiliser as the sum of nutrients did not reach the required limit in none of the combinations (NPK, NP, NK). Regarding the compost produced at the German pilot region (KIT), the nutrient specifications are not enough to be deemed a fertiliser. Annex V which lists the allowed soil improvers and contains all types of allowed composts does not include faecal compost, only manure compost and compost from plant sources, so this product would not be currently allowed in Greece.

Concluding, the only product that fulfilled the nutrient specifications of this MD is the Swedish product. However, another unclear point is if it meets the requirement of the manufacturing process since only “solid products or solutions resulting from chemical synthesis or the physical mixing of their components” are allowed. This needs to be clarified with the Greek authorities.

Finally, for products not covered by the new Greek MD, an application to include the materials or product specifications in the Annexes would have to be performed by submitting a technical dossier. Verbal communication with the competent authorities under the previous regime indicated that companies were encouraged to submit a technical dossier for such fertilisers so that the Technical Advisory Committee could review and evaluate them. The competent authority concerning the placing of fertilising products on the Greek market is the Ministry of Rural Development and Food and specifically the department of fertilisers and soil science.

5.6.6 Hungary

The Hungarian legislative framework regarding fertilising products consists of Decree No. 36 of 2006 (V. 18.) FVM²⁹² of the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development concerning the authorization, storage, marketing and utilization of yield enhancing materials. It includes 10 product categories based on function and origin of materials: Inorganic fertilisers, Organic fertilisers, Mineral fertilisers, Composts, Earthworm humus, Soil improving substances, Growing media, Microbial products, Soil-conditioners and Plant conditioners. Every yield enhancer (fertilising product) must be authorised before its placement on the market. The authorization procedure according to the national legislation is under the responsibilities of Nemzeti Élelmiszerlánc-biztonsági Hivatal (NÉBIH), the National Food Chain Safety Office.

The definitions provided for the fertilisers and compost are the following:

- Fertiliser: an industrially produced, chemically produced crop-enhancing substance that supplies nutrients to plants.
- Organic fertiliser subject to authorisation: a yield-enhancing substance with a defined content, industrially processed from organic material of plant or animal origin, serving to supply plants with nutrients or improve soil structure.
- Mineral fertiliser: an industrially produced, mineral-based crop-enhancing substance that serves to supply plants with nutrients and improve soil structure.
- Compost: a crop-enhancing substance produced from organic, inorganic and mineral materials through composting in accordance with the requirements of separate legislation, serving to improve the nutrient supply of plants and the nutrient-supplying capacity of the soil.

The urine-derived fertilisers produced in Sweden and Germany do not contain organic carbon and do not come from minerals, so they would be categorised as “fertilisers” according to the definitions noted above. However, as fertilisers are defined as “chemically produced,” it is necessary to further assess whether the processes

²⁹² [36/2006. \(V. 18.\) FVM rendelet a terméshnövelő anyagok engedélyezéséről, tárolásáról, forgalmazásáról és felhasználásáról](#)

implemented within the pilot regions could be interpreted as chemical production under this definition.

The data and studies needed for the application to receive a marketing authorisation, depend on the category assigned to the product and include physicochemical information, heavy metals, phytotoxicity potential, organic contaminants (PAHs, PCB), biological effect testing (efficacy trials), quantification of human pathogens. However, if waste is used to produce the products, then additional toxicological, ecotoxicological and other tests may be ordered, depending on the quality of the waste. In the section about compost some examples of the testing regarding ecotoxicology are mentioned (Daphnia test, fish test, algae test).

As far as specifications are concerned: in the category named “Fertilisers,” there are certain subcategories depending on whether the product is straight or compound, macronutrient or micronutrients, liquid or solid, etc. For simple fertilisers (solid or liquid), specific chemical substances are listed under the table stating the tolerance rules for nutrients, such as urea, superphosphate, and potassium sulphate. In contrast, the table for compound fertilisers does not include specific substances. No minimum nutrient content is specified for fertilisers or mineral fertilisers. However, certain quality specifications exist for compost, including a minimum of 25% w/w organic matter and 1% total nitrogen (criteria that are met by the fecal compost produced in the German pilot region).

Compost is also regulated under Government Decree No. 559/2023 (XII. 14.) on activities to prevent the generation of biodegradable waste, on detailed rules for waste management activities related to biodegradable waste and on rules for the classification of compost produced from biowaste. According to the definition compost is “waste according to Annex 1, as well as green waste generated in households and kitchen green waste, produced during home and community or farm composting using auxiliary materials, a humus-like material with a high organic content, rich in plant nutrients – defined in separate legislation – whose waste status has ceased”. Annex 1 provides certain allowed waste types along with their designations from the European Waste Catalogue²⁹³. For example, it includes “wastes from agriculture, horticulture, aquaculture, forestry, hunting and fishing, food preparation and processing“, such as animal-derived excrements. It also includes “wastes from waste management facilities, off-site wastewater treatment plants, and drinking or industrial water supply“, such as waste from anaerobic waste treatment and unspecified waste from sewage treatment plants. Another category is “Municipal waste (household waste and similar commercial, industrial, and institutional waste), including separately collected fractions“, such as kitchen waste, cooking oils, paper, garden and park waste, mixed municipal waste.

²⁹³ Commission Decision of 3 May 2000 replacing Decision 94/3/EC establishing a list of wastes pursuant to Article 1(a) of Council Directive 75/442/EEC on waste and Council Decision 94/904/EC establishing a list of hazardous waste pursuant to Article 1(4) of Council Directive 91/689/EEC on hazardous waste [2000] OJ L 226

It appears that none of these categories explicitly cover human excreta. However, further investigation is required to determine whether separately collected human excreta falls under the definition of waste in the WFD and whether it could be assigned a specific waste code under the European Waste Catalogue.

An interesting point is that green waste and kitchen waste may be collected and composted at the community level, where collection is carried out by property users residing in residential buildings, and pre-treatment and composting are jointly performed by apartment buildings, housing cooperatives, or small communities. Furthermore, the Decree establishes end-of-waste criteria for biodegradable waste, applicable to both agricultural and non-agricultural uses of the resulting compost.

Finally, the Hungarian legislative framework is particularly strict, with authorities placing strong emphasis on public health and environmental protection requiring additional information for waste-derived materials, so it is likely that human excreta-derived products would not be easily accepted by the national authorities.

5.7 Mutual recognition

This part of the Report is divided into two sections: an examination of the rules on mutual recognition set at the EU level and an outline of the approach taken by a range of Member States to this concept. We would highlight that there is very limited publicly available information regarding Sweden and further investigation is needed to confirm approaches.

5.7.1 The European Union

Inspired by the jurisprudence of the Court of Justice of the EU, the process of harmonisation of the laws of the Member States on various products took a major step forward with recognition of the principle of mutual recognition.²⁹⁴ Restrictions on goods lawfully produced in one Member State would not be allowed subject to the exceptions listed in Article 36 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU or on the basis of overriding concerns of public interest/mandatory requirements identified in the Court's jurisprudence.²⁹⁵ A further step forward in this area was made with the new approach

²⁹⁴ See case 120/78 *Rewe-Zentral AG v Bundesmonolverwaltung für Branntwein* [1979] ECR 649, para 14.

²⁹⁵ *Ibid*, these include effective fiscal supervision, protection of public health, commercial fairness and consumer protection. On the latter, see for example, Case C-525/14 *European Commission v Czech Republic*, EU:C:2016:714. See also, for example, Case C-573/12 *Ålands Vindkraft AB*, EU:C:2014:2037 and Case C-329/03 *Commission v Austria*, EU:C:2005:684 adding environmental protection to the mandatory requirements.

adopted by the Commission in its 1985 White Paper entitled *Completing the Internal Market* heralding the beginning of the Single Market project.²⁹⁶ However, a 2020 study recognised that this is “never a finished project” with 18% of internal trade in goods falling outside harmonised categories and it is in these goods that mutual recognition is relevant.²⁹⁷

At the heart of the drive towards mutual recognition is Regulation 2019/515 whose aim is “to strengthen the functioning of the internal market by improving the application of the principle of mutual recognition and by removing unjustified barriers to trade.”²⁹⁸ Article 4 of the Regulation provides for a Mutual Recognition Declaration (MRD) – a voluntary declaration of the producer of the goods to the competent authorities in one Member State that the goods have been lawfully marketed in another Member State.²⁹⁹ Article 5 of the Regulation deals with the assessment procedure to be used by the competent authorities in a Member State as they decide whether the goods, in the words of Article 5(1) “adequately protect” the legitimate public interests under national technical rules. If a declaration under Article 4 has not been supplied, the competent authorities may, under Article 5(5), request the information necessary for an assessment, in particular on the characteristics of the goods in question. Once a decision is made, the competent authority must notify the economic operator, the Commission, and other Member States within twenty working days. Article 5(11) provides that the decision must state:

- (a) the national technical rule on which the administrative decision is based;
- (b) the legitimate public interest grounds justifying the application of the national technical rule on which the administrative decision is based;
- (c) the technical or scientific evidence that the competent authority of the Member State of destination considered, including, where applicable, any relevant changes in the state of the art that have occurred since the national technical rule came into force;
- (d) a summary of the arguments put forward by the economic operator concerned that are relevant for the assessment under paragraph 1, if any;

²⁹⁶ COMPLETING THE INTERNAL MARKET: WHITE PAPER FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN COUNCIL (MILAN, 28-29 JUNE 1985), COM (1985) 310, paras 77-79.

²⁹⁷ See [Legal obstacles in Member States to Single Market rules](#), pp 15 and 49. The previous review (Atkins, W, *Technical Barriers to Trade, study for the Single Market Review*, Office of Official Publications, 1997) set the percentage at 25%.

²⁹⁸ [2019] OJ L 91/1. The Regulation is larger than its predecessors; Regulation 764/2008, [2008] OJ L 218/21 and Decision 3052/95, [1995] OJ L 321/1. See also Commission Implementing Regulation 2020/1668, [2020] OJ L 377/7 setting up and Information and Communication System for Market Surveillance to improve the application of Regulation 2019/515. A guidance document on the Regulation is available at [Mutual recognition of goods - European Commission](#). The document was promised in COM (2020)94 *Long term action plan for better implementation and enforcement of single market rules*, p. 6.

²⁹⁹ The format for the declaration is set out in Parts I and II of the Annex to the Regulation. Article 4(6) provides that “For goods subject to a Union act mandating an EU declaration of conformity, the mutual recognition declaration may be attached to the EU declaration of conformity.”

- (e) the evidence demonstrating that the administrative decision is appropriate for the purpose of achieving the objective pursued and that the administrative decision does not go beyond what is necessary in order to attain that objective.

The decision must also indicate the available remedies and that economic operators may use the problems solving procedures set out in Article 8, which includes SOLVIT, an on-line service run by national administrations.³⁰⁰

There is a possible assessment by the Commission under SOLVIT on the compatibility of the decision with EU law and to date six Opinions have been published. In its first Opinion, the Commission indicated that as a Regulation, Regulation 2019/515 was directly applicable in all Member States so did not generally require the adoption of national implementing measures.³⁰¹ It pointed out that the procedure in Article 5 must be followed if an economic operator claims the application of the Regulation and that this includes the possibility that the operator could supply a MRD. On the decision of the competent authorities, it was pointed out that the “administrative decisions should be appropriate to achieve the public interest objective, such as public health, and should not go beyond what is necessary to attain that objective.”³⁰² It emphasised the principle of proportionality in the application of national technical rules suggesting that the competent authority should opt for a measure that is “less restrictive from the perspective of the free movement of goods.”³⁰³

Four of the remaining Opinions relate to fertilisers and thus are of interest with respect to P2Green activities.³⁰⁴ The first of these related to an application for authorisation of a product which had been lawfully marketed in Spain; the application was ultimately rejected on the basis that the information submitted did not allow for a decision that harm to consumers could be excluded as a strain of micro-organism in the product could not be properly identified.³⁰⁵ Whilst the economic operator argued that the micro-organism was consider safe under the FPR, the French authorities argued that the Regulation did not expressly state that it was safe. Responding to the arguments, the Commission indicated that the competent authority must request the information necessary for a decision to be made as to whether the legitimate public interests protected by the national

³⁰⁰ See COM (2020) 94, above n 298, Action 18 would make SOLVIT the default tool for single market dispute resolution. See also Article 9 on Product Contact Points and Regulation 2018/1724 establishing a single digital gateway to provide access to information, to procedures and to assistance and problem-solving services, [2018] OJ L 295/1 – the *Your Europe* portal.

³⁰¹ C(2021) 6950, at p.3. The Opinion recognised that some of its provisions nonetheless may necessitate implementation measures, and it cited case C-645/19 *Facebook Ireland Ltd*, EU:C:2021:483, paras 109 and 110. This confirms the long-standing jurisprudence of the Court on the legal nature of regulations under both the TFEU and previous Treaties.

³⁰² *Ibid*, p 5.

³⁰³ *Ibid*, it suggested in this instance labelling rather than restricting or denying market access.

³⁰⁴ In 2011, the Commission issued a Guidance document on *The application of the Mutual Recognition Regulation to fertilisers and growing media*, available at [Mutual recognition of goods - European Commission](#).

³⁰⁵ C(2022) 398.

rules were adequately protected.³⁰⁶ As this did not happen, Article 5 of Regulation 2019/515 had not been complied with by the French competent authority. The remaining Opinions, all issued on 20 January 2023, deal with refusals to grant mutual recognition by the competent authority in France to fertilisers lawfully marketed in Belgium and in each of them the Commission concluded that the French competent authority had not fully complied with Article 5.³⁰⁷ For example, in the third Opinion, the Commission emphasised the need to the principle of proportionality to be respected.³⁰⁸ In the fourth Opinion, the Commission noted that the decision did not provide full reasoning based on the scientific evidence demonstrating that the product was a risk to public health or the environment nor did it “mention the technical or scientific evidence on the basis of which the national technical rule set the maximum authorised content in France.”³⁰⁹

Reflecting on the Opinions, it is clear that the competent authority in the Member State must ensure that any decision reached is fully in accordance with the Regulation; if further information is necessary, then it should be requested from the economic operator and the Commission seems to be encouraging the competent authority to request a MRD. The Opinions also suggest that any conditions imposed by the competent authorities should be consistent with the discretion afforded to Member States under EU law.³¹⁰ There is also a potential lesson here for the EU in that if the scientific evidence is stricter than that imposed by EU law, for example on contaminants such as those listed in Regulation 2019/1009, then this represents an opportunity for the EU to revise its scientific evidence having sought expert opinion, for example from the European Food Safety Authority. Finally, the decision of the competent authority must be proportionate considering the risk it is seeking to address; so, measures which are less restrictive of the free movement of goods within the EU are to be encouraged.

The 2020 study, *Legal obstacles in Member States to Single Market rules*, indicated that mutual recognition is seriously underused and suggested harmonisation for specific sectors in which barriers could not be easily overcome.³¹¹ On fertilisers, the Report suggests that Regulation 2019/1009 represents further harmonisation with mutual

³⁰⁶ Ibid, p 5.

³⁰⁷ See C (2023) 359, the fifth opinion which in essence repeats the reasoning of the second opinion.

³⁰⁸ See C(2023) 371, p 4.

³⁰⁹ C (2023) 370, p 5. On this point see Directive 2015/1535 laying down a procedure for the provision of information in the field of technical regulations, [2015] OJ L 241/1. See also Case C-194/94 *CIA Security v Signalson* [1996] ECR 2201.

³¹⁰ See, for example, Article 7 of Directive 86/278, the Sewage Sludge Directive, which provides: “Member States shall prohibit the use of sludge or the supply of sludge for use on: (a) grassland or forage crops if the grassland is to be grazed or the forage crops to be harvested before a certain period has elapsed. This period, which shall be set by the Member States taking particular account of their geographical and climatic situation, shall under no circumstances be less than three weeks; (b) soil in which fruit and vegetable crops are growing, with the exception of fruit trees; (c) ground intended for the cultivation of fruit and vegetable crops which are normally indirect contact with the soil and normally eaten raw, for a period of 10 months preceding the harvest of the crops and during the harvest itself.” [1986] OJ L 181/6.

³¹¹ Above n 297, p 11 and 54. One of the areas was food contact materials.

recognition issues being much reduced, however, continuing references to national fertilisers in the Regulation fragments the Single Market.³¹² The study concluded:³¹³

... the root cause of many (though indeed not all) mutual recognition problems has to be identified first: the positioning and mindset of the Member States, be it a few specialised officials, rigid consumer organisations (sometimes going beyond or irrespective of science), lobby interests or local traditions. When discussing mutual recognition, it sometimes seems that Member States claim a kind of absolute "right" to protect citizens, workers and the environment in their way as if other Member States doing it differently are, by definition, doing it wrong.

Perhaps rather than being "wrong", national competent authorities just have different perceptions of the risks facing public health and/or the environment.

In practice, it may be useful to first identify Member States whose national legislative frameworks already provide a basis for the authorisation of human excreta-derived products. Subsequently, consideration can be given to those Member States with well-defined or less administratively demanding mutual recognition procedures, which may facilitate smoother market entry and gradual expansion within the Union.

The European Commission began evaluating the Mutual Recognition Regulation at the end of 2023 to assess how well it supports the free movement of goods and reduces unjustified barriers³¹⁴. The results, expected in the second quarter of 2026, will inform future policy improvements to the system.

5.7.2 Germany

Germany's 2012 Ordinance on the Placing on the Market of Fertilisers, Soil Additives, Growing Media and Plant Aids, discussed above regarding authorisations, provides that fertilisers that have been lawfully manufactured or lawfully marketed in another Member State of the EU, Turkey or a Member State of the European Free Trade Association and the Agreement on the European Economic Area, and meets "the requirements for protection against hazards to human or animal health or the ecosystem in the same way as domestic substances" may be placed on the market.³¹⁵ Statutory Instruments enacted by the Federal Ministry under Article 5(2) of the Fertiliser Act may offer, for example,

³¹² Ibid, p 61.

³¹³ Ibid, p 56.

³¹⁴ A call for evidence and a public consultation were published on the [Have Your Say portal](#).

³¹⁵ The 2012 Ordinance Article 3(1)(1) and 1(2).

detailed requirements for placing on the market or to prohibit/restrict certain categories of fertilisers from being placed on the market.³¹⁶

5.7.3 Spain

The Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food³¹⁷ has published a national procedure³¹⁸ for the implementation of Regulation (EU) 2019/515 concerning the placing on the Spanish market of fertilising products originating from other Member States. The procedure defines the documentation required to support an application. As the competent authority for fertilising products, the Ministry has designated the *Subdirección General de Medios de Producción Agrícola y Oficina Española de Variedades Vegetales* as the national contact point for the reception of Declarations of Mutual Recognition.

Required documentation includes:

- (a) Declaration of Mutual Recognition, in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2019/515;
- (b) evidence demonstrating that the product is available to end-users in the Member State of origin (e.g. sales invoices, delivery notes, etc.); and
- (c) the original product label, with a sworn translation in Spanish, together with the version intended for the Spanish market, allowing verification that the product is placed on the market under equivalent conditions.

All documentation must be accompanied by official translations into Spanish.

5.7.4 Sweden

Information on mutual recognition in Sweden is challenging to obtain, but it appears that Sweden is generally open to applying mutual recognition once the appropriate documentation is provided to the relevant body – this may be the Jordbruksverket (Agricultural Board) or the Kemikalieinspektionen (Kemi/Chemical Inspectorate) depending on the nature of the product. No accessible documentation was available regarding fertilisers per se, but Kemi provides guidance regarding mutual recognition for

³¹⁶ Ibid, Article 5(3) indicated that these Ordinances may include provisions on approved starting materials; method of production; composition according to main and minor components, in particular with regard to nutrient content, nutrient form and type and content of secondary components; nutrient availability; effect of secondary components; external characteristics, in particular grain size, grinding fineness, sieve passage or colouring; and other requirements that are important for the preparation, application or effect of the substance.

³¹⁷ Ministerio de agricultura, pesca y alimentación (MAPA) (<https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/>)

³¹⁸ [Procedimiento para la aplicación del Reglamento \(UE\) 2019/515 relativo al reconocimiento mutuo, para la puesta en el mercado español de productos fertilizantes procedentes de otros estados miembros](#)

other related products that could provide insights for fertilising products.³¹⁹ Recognition will typically be granted unless there are objective justifications for a refusal, e.g. based on environmental or health risks. One example would be if the maximum permitted cadmium levels were breached. Further investigation is required regarding this regime.

5.7.5 France

The Code Rural et de la Peche Maritime (CRPM) enables the application for mutual recognition in France following authorisation in another Member State. The legal provisions are similar (and linked), with the core provisions being found in R255-17 of the CRPM and the Arrêté of 1st April 2020. As with local authorisation in France, the application is made to ANSES, this time with evidence to prove that the substance has been legally put on the market in the originating 'reference' Member State.³²⁰ Article 3(II) of the 2020 Arrêté outlines the information that must be provided, including the full composition of the product, the original authorising decision, details regarding use (e.g. crops, dosages, timing etc) and the safety data sheet for the product and all raw materials, as per Article 31 of the REACH Regulation (Regulation 1907/2006). The product contact point (under the mutual recognition Regulation 2019/515) for France is the Directorate General for Enterprise, which is a department of the Ministry for Economy and Finance. This PCP can provide operators with further information and guidance on mutual recognition regarding specific products, including fertilisers.³²¹

5.7.6 Italy

As elsewhere, mutual recognition is largely regulated for by Regulation 2019/515,³²² with the 2010 Italian decree on fertilisers providing for its implementation in this field.³²³ The Italian National Phytosanitary Services (NPS) body provides an outline of the procedure involved.³²⁴ Crucially, they note that the request must be submitted to the relevant office (DIRS V) at the Ministry, in Italian, via certified email to the email address noted.³²⁵ This,

³¹⁹ 'GUIDANCE ON PLANT PROTECTION PRODUCTS Guidance for applications for mutual recognition in Sweden' (accessed 23rd October 2025).

³²⁰ R255-17.

³²¹ E.g. see <https://www.entreprises.gouv.fr/en/echanges-commerciaux-et-reglementation/free-movement-goods/product-contact-point-pcp>.

³²² Depending on the precise nature of the product, it might fall under Article 40 of Regulation 1107/2009 on plant protection products instead.

³²³ Decreto Legislativo 29 aprile 2010, n. 281, discussed above.

³²⁴ The outline can be found [here](#).

³²⁵ 'Tale richiesta è presentata all'Ufficio DISR V – Servizio Fitosanitario Centrale, produzioni vegetali, unicamente tramite PEC: aoo.cosvir@pec.politicheagricole.gov.it, in lingua italiana, unitamente agli

unhelpfully, is somewhat different from the details in the applicable domestic legislation, e.g. with a different email address included as the Ministry has changed since the relevant decree was adopted. The NPS also notes a list of information that must be included:³²⁶

- Declaration on Mutual Recognition;
- The Member State certificate attesting that the product is legally marketed in the Member State, on the basis of which mutual recognition is requested, in Italian or another document attesting to the marketing of the product;
- The technical rule (national legislation), according to which the product is marketed in the Member State;
- Copy of the original label or original accompanying document of the product placed on the market in the country where it is legally marketed;
- Copy of the label or accompanying document of the product placed on the market in the country where it is legally marketed in Italian;
- The detailed list of raw materials used and information on their origin;
- Brief description of the production process;
- A recent product analysis certificate issued by an accredited laboratory (if a non-Italian laboratory, attach a copy of the authorization issued by the competent authority) indicating the official analysis method; the analyses must concern the agronomic parameters and the relevant contaminants (heavy metals, microorganisms and organic contaminants);
- The intended purpose(s), dosage(s) and instructions for use;
- Where applicable, all documents certifying that the product complies with the Animal By-Products Regulation and any other European legislation on the protection of humans, animals and the environment;
- The contact details of the production site and any storage site, located in Italy and/or any other country;
- Attachment 1 completed.³²⁷

In Italy, before obtaining a registration through the MR process, the manufacturer — or the Italian distributor — must be registered in the Italian fertilizer manufacturers' database.³²⁸

5.7.7 Greece

elementi di seguito indicati' (source: <https://www.protezionedellepiante.it/fertilizzanti/#1714993609753-814e4f0e-974a>). The Ministry's Directorate General for Rural Development has broader responsibility in this field and relevant focus points and contact details are available [here](#).

³²⁶ The content that follows is an unofficial translation of the contents of the NPS website, via the automatic translation on the browser.

³²⁷ The attachment can be found through the [link](#) provided via the NPS website.

³²⁸ The database can be accessed through the following link:
<https://www.sian.it/vismiko/jsp/indexConsultazione.do>.

The Hellenic Ministry of Development and Investments is the national contact point for products and has a dedicated website³²⁹ where one can find information about the role of the Product Contact Point, the implementation of Regulation (EU) 2019/515 on the mutual recognition of goods, as well as the problem-solving procedures in case of disputes concerning the free movement of goods. Also, a search for the national legislation applicable to products in Greece can be performed there. Information can be requested through an online form about the products a company is interested in, such as electronic copies of the national technical rules and administrative procedures in force, or electronic access to those rules and procedures, as well as information on whether the products in question are subject to prior authorization under national legislation.

On the website of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food, the responsible competent authority for fertilising products, there is not a published procedure for Mutual Recognition of fertilising products in Greece under the section of the national legislative framework³³⁰.

Under the previous national framework, even if the fertiliser was already authorised in another Member State, it needed to follow the procedure of authorisation in Greece, as a prior authorisation condition. After the publishing of the new Ministerial Decree, products do not require prior authorisation before being placed on the market anymore but must be covered by the Annexes and be compliant with the specifications defined therein to be placed on the Greek market.

5.7.8 Hungary

The rules governing the mutual recognition of fertilising substances in Hungary are defined in Article 5 of the Decree No. 36 of 2006 (V. 18.) FVM³³¹ of the Ministry of Agriculture. Since the national legislation has been duly notified in accordance with Directive (EU) 2015/1535, the technical specifications established in the FVM Regulation apply during mutual recognition procedures, pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2019/515. All information about the Mutual Recognition procedure can be found on the website of Nemzeti Élelmiszerlánc-biztonsági Hivatal (NÉBIH), the National Food Chain Safety Office³³².

³²⁹ Information about the Product Contact Point can be found in the following link: <https://pcp.ggb.gr/>

³³⁰ National legislation for fertilising products can be found in the [website](#) of the Hellenic Ministry of Agricultural Development and Food.

³³¹ [36/2006. \(V. 18.\) FVM rendelet a terménynövelő anyagok engedélyezéséről, tárolásáról, forgalmazásáról és felhasználásáról.](#)

³³² <https://portal.nebih.gov.hu/termesnovelok>

In the context of a mutual recognition application, and to ensure equivalent levels of protection, the competent authority may request the submission of any missing data and require additional testing in accordance with Annex II of the FVM Regulation.

The documents to be submitted include: a) The completed application form provided in Annex I of the FVM Regulation and b) The relevant test results as listed in Annex II. Applications, together with all required annexes (e.g. test reports), must be submitted electronically via a platform³³³ or in the case of applicants without a representative office in Hungary, applications may alternatively be submitted by post.

Hungarian law is very strict, and mutual recognition is possible only if equivalence of protection is proven (i.e. same or higher protection level as mandated by the national Hungarian law). From our experience as regulatory consultants and the feedback from various experts, obtaining a license to market a fertilising product under Mutual Recognition in Hungary is very difficult.

5.8 Conclusions on fertilising products

A lack of coherency and lack of forward-looking provisions mark the broad regulatory landscape for fertilising products at EU and national level, despite what appears initially to be the availability of multiple options for authorisation and marketing. Of note is the two-way linkage between the EU's FPR and the Member States' own authorisation regimes, with the review of the FPR looking to what happens in Member States and the domestic regimes frequently mirroring the FPR. This creates considerable issues where the FPR is already too rigid. Yet, variations exist and there are still options for innovators now and in the future.

It is essential for P2Green actors and those undertaking similar activities to identify which fertiliser authorisation regime might suit them best, based on current requirements, availability of mutual recognition and how feasible it would be to introduce changes to the regimes –domestically or at the EU level. In countries such as Sweden in particular, the development of voluntary certification standards and then abiding by these could prove beneficial on multiple fronts. Elsewhere may depend on the adaptation of lists of permitted inputs, as in the case of the FPR and Member States such as Germany. From a reform perspective, there is a need to adapt the FPR and equivalent domestic regimes, to embed greater flexibility and coherency.

³³³ [e-Paper Customer Portal](#)

6 Conclusions and areas of potential reform

P2Green and similar products and activities have significant potential to contribute to the circular economy, zero pollution and food security, all of which are essential goals of the EU. Yet, for P2Green and other actors seeking to undertake such activities and develop these types of products, their very innovative nature can open some doors within the laws but also create further obstacles. A key element that is reflected throughout much of this interim legislative report is that human excreta is not a major express focus of EU law. For instance, there appears to be a general working (non-legal) presumption that it is normally and potentially always part of 'wastewater', but without clearly and definitively addressing this within waste law. Further, historically excreta, whether from animals or humans, has been recognised as a valuable source of nutrients for agriculture,³³⁴ but a shift has occurred within society to use a range of fertilisers other than human excreta and simply to see human excreta as a source of pollution that needs to be treated. As a result, there are limited pathways supporting the use of human excreta in agricultural production in EU or domestic legislation. What was traditional became obsolete and now innovative developments, which build on the traditional approaches but in a safer, more environmentally friendly manner, face further hurdles in a highly regulated society. There are several issues across the three key areas examined that might be suitable for potential reform.

6.1 Waste

The waste regime poses several significant challenges, including the lack of certainty regarding whether faeces is excluded from the EU waste regime or not, the scope of 'waste waters', the impact of the lack of discharges, the potential for 'waste water' to be collected privately via large-scale systems, and in what circumstances can a product cease to be waste where there are no express applicable criteria. Besides the lack of certainty, there is the very limited implementation of Article 6 of the WFD at the EU level or domestically and more fundamental questions about whether the term 'waste' should be applicable at all or not in the circumstances.

While the CJEU might clarify the interpretation of the EU laws in future, Member States are for the moment left with considerable scope to adopt their own approaches and, effectively, interpretations, as seen above. This leads to considerable flexibility, but also the potential for inertia or avoidance of decision-making. The lack of EU-level or even national criteria for Article 6 of the WFD also leads to an over-reliance on case-by-case

³³⁴ E.g. [L. Zeldovich, 'A History of Human Waste as Fertilizer', 18 November 2019, JSTOR Daily](#); and [Y. Shirai, S.J. Leisz and K. Kyuma, 'A Short History of the Utilization of Nightsoil in Agriculture', \(2023\) 7\(2\) Sanitation 1](#)https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/sanitation/7/2/7_00002/pdf.

decisions, which do not provide certainty to innovators or investors. Reflecting the potential for avoidance of decision-making, Article 6 'decisions' are sometimes more a *de facto* acceptance by the national authorities of the holder's own opinion that a substance is no longer waste, which may be temporarily useful domestically but provides little reassurance to other Member States considering the import and mutual recognition of a product.

6.2 Water reuse

More positively, the EU has now established a coherent legal framework for water reclamation through the WRR, providing a harmonised set of minimum requirements and a governance structure intended to ensure safety, transparency and public trust. While the Regulation is relatively new and some implementation pathways are still maturing, it nonetheless creates a clear regulatory backbone upon which Member States and stakeholders can build. This framework is further supported by a range of complementary guidance documents aiming to facilitate the practical uptake of water-reclamation technologies.

However, the option given to Member States to opt out of applying the Regulation introduces variability and potential fragmentation in the EU's approach to water reuse. Given that even traditionally water-abundant regions are now encountering episodes of scarcity, the opt-out mechanism would benefit from stronger procedural safeguards. A requirement for Member States to provide a scientific and socio-economic robust justification for opting-out, subject to periodic review, could enhance accountability and ensure that non-participation is based on evidence. Moreover, developing a national strategy for water reuse, whether or not a Member State initially opts out, could help maintain long-term readiness and ensure rapid deployment of reuse solutions.

A further issue highlighted in stakeholder discussions within the context of P2GreeN is the persistent stigma associated with reclaimed water. Farmers willing to use reclaimed water often prefer not to disclose it due to public misconceptions that equate reclaimed water with contaminated water or "waste." Targeted legal clarification, especially regarding the status of reclaimed water as "not-waste" and its suitability for use in organic farming, would help resolve ambiguities and could be an important step toward normalising reuse in the agri-food sector.

Looking ahead, the Water Resilience Initiative, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the experience of pioneering Member States such as Spain and Cyprus point to the potential for expanding water reuse beyond agricultural irrigation. Non-potable urban uses (e.g. irrigation of green public spaces), industrial applications (e.g. cooling), and potentially other sectors represent logical areas for future regulatory evolution. Expanding the scope of reuse would not only increase Europe's adaptive capacity but also contribute

to circular-economy objectives by valorising reclaimed water as a stable resource of water rather than an exceptional measure.

Finally, for P2GreeN, in particular for the Spanish pilot region, there is a strategic opportunity to collaborate more closely with EU and national bodies such as WISE, the JRC, or CEDEX. Providing data, methodologies, and real-world evidence on safe and effective reuse practices could position the project as a model for integrated monitoring and implementation. In doing so, P2GreeN can contribute meaningfully to the evolving landscape of EU water governance and help shape best practices that can be replicated across Europe.

6.3 Fertilising products

The EU regime on the use of excreta as a fertiliser reflects the dichotomy between animal and human excreta with the former being more acceptable than the latter. Nevertheless, the restrictions imposed by some Member States on the use of sewage sludge suggests that attitudes to the use of excreta in agriculture are still controversial. However, it is clear from the first Circular Economy Action Plan through a series of policy papers since then that these attitudes need to change and these changes must assure the public that the use of human excreta (and indeed animal excreta) is both environmentally safe and not a danger to human health – provided that suitable controls are applied and measures taken.

One approach here would be to incorporate human excreta within the scope of the FPR by amending one or more of the existing CMCs to allow the use of human excreta (both faeces and urine) as input materials for fertilisers. The framework it provides should reassure the public that the resulting fertiliser is acceptable from both an environmental and human health perspective. Alternatively, it might be more appropriate to develop one or more CMCs to allow for the use of human faeces and/or urine as input materials to reflect the emerging technologies in this area.

Having canvassed how EU law addresses animal excreta and contrasting that treatment with that applicable to human excreta, another approach would be to adopt a consistent approach across the board to the use of both animal and human excreta in agriculture in a new Regulation. This approach would address the Animal By-Products Regulation and the Directives on Nitrates and Sewage Sludge. The goal would be to create a fertiliser that could be used in organic production given the emphasis placed on such production not only as European agriculture moves to become more sustainable but also, more generally, in response to the challenges posed by climate change.

Further, as noted, many of the national fertiliser regimes bear a striking resemblance at times to the FPR. Where they do, they crystallise the rigidity with respect to P2GreeN-

style products and exacerbate the challenges posed by the FPR – with options at both national and EU-level thereby limited. This is not the case uniformly and, indeed, Sweden provides an example of potentially excessive flexibility and resulting ambiguity and lack of assurance for users/consumers. Together, they do raise questions about what way the regulatory landscape should look like across the EU and Member States, and what the relationship should be between the domestic regimes and the FPR.

6.4 Next Steps

Throughout this document we have flagged numerous issues, suggestions for innovators in the field and points that merit potential law reform or addressing by other means. There are some elements which would benefit from further investigation, e.g. where multiple interpretations of the law are possible, which we hope to develop for D3.10 (the final legislative report). This is also the case where legislative reform is currently taking place, e.g. following the adoption of the revised UWWTD or the European Water Resilience Strategy, the reviews of the FPR (through technical studies aimed at incorporating more materials/processes, the simplification omnibus, the evaluation), the discussions regarding the proposed EU Circular Economy Act, updates in EU water law more generally, and developments on implementing the WRR within the Member States (including France and Spain).

Finally, while we have identified numerous issues with the law, great care must be taken with suggestions for potential law reform, due in particular to the potential for unintended consequences or countervailing risks. Consequently, we will subsequently identify and tease out potential law reforms, engaging with our P2GreeN partners and Advisory Board once more, before including these within the final report (D3.10).

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